

D 3.1 GUIDANCE NOTES ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO ENERGY EDUCATION

*WP3 – Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance
Women in Energy Transition*

Contributors	Aleksandra Wagner Tadeusz Rudek Paulina Sekuła Marta Warat
Reviewers	Marco Cellini, Fabiola Letizia Falconieri, Valentina Tudisca
Delivery date	31/07/2024
Dissemination level	Public

A large, faded version of the gEneSys logo is positioned at the bottom of the page. It features the text "gEneSys" in white on a light green background, with the atom and tree icons also faded.

<i>Project Acronym</i>	gEneSys
<i>Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Project Full Title</i>	gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe

Deliverable Information

<i>Deliverable Name</i>	
<i>Dissemination level</i>	Public (PU)
<i>Funding Scheme</i>	Horizon Europe
<i>Grant Agreement number</i>	101094326
<i>Contractual date of delivery</i>	31 07 2024
<i>Deliverable Leader</i>	Jagiellonian University
<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	Jagiellonian University
<i>Keywords</i>	Textbooks, energy education, primary and secondary schools, gender, energy, energy transition
<i>Abstract</i>	Report on the integration of the gender-energy nexus into basic education at primary and secondary level in selected European countries. The aim was to demonstrate how social representations of energy issues, and in particular socio-technical imaginaries related to energy transitions, can work through education to achieve gender equality in energy systems. The synthesis is based on the four national reports prepared by the four research teams. The results show that the gender-energy nexus cannot be communicated in popular school textbooks due to the specificity of teaching about energy with them. Despite the observed differences between European education

© Genesys 2023 This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

GeneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326.

Guidance Note

	<p>systems, in all analysed countries, energy topics are scattered among different subjects, presented mainly through economic and technological lenses, without a human-centred approach. The textbooks analysed do not encourage female students to develop their interest in further studies or future careers in energy fields. There is no or very little information about new job opportunities created by the energy transition, while social practices are limited to marginal examples of the use of electrical appliances or energy saving. The introduction of a people-centred and gender-innovative approach in curricula and textbooks could help to overcome the existing bias in the social perception of technologies in relation to gender.</p>
--	--

Document history

Date	Version	Authors
15/07/2024	Draft	Aleksandra Wagner, Tadeusz, Rudek, Paulina Sekuła, Marta Warat
Date	Version	Reviewers
21/07/2024	Draft	Fabiola Letizia Falconieri
15/07/2024	Draft	Marco Cellini
19.07/2024	Draft	Valentina Tudisca

TABLE OF CONTENT

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
1 INTRODUCTION.....	5
1.1 European Energy transition as a Great Multidimensional project. (Common goals vs diverse energy transition paths as a challenge in the European Union)	5
1.2 Diverse educational systems in Europe as a challenge for learning energy transition and sustainable development.....	6
1.3 Why energy– gender nexus matters in education? Rationale, aims and scope of analysis	7
2 METHODOLOGY	8
3 ENERGY EDUCATION DIMENSIONS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS.....	11
4 KEY MISSING THEMES	12
5 LANGUAGE- PROBLEMATISING "GENDER NEUTRALITY"	14
6 INCLUSIVE GENDER–ENERGY TEACHING RECOMMENDATIONS.....	14
REFERENCES	17
APPENDICES.....	19
APPENDIX 1. GENDER IN THE TEACHING OF ENERGY IN SECONDARY EDUCATION TEXTBOOKS IN ENGLAND, UK.....	19
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	19
1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH.....	20
1.1 The UK Education System.....	20
1.2 The Key Stages	22
1.3 Compulsory Education Qualifications	23
1.4 The National Curriculum and Energy Education in Secondary School.....	23
1.5 Use of Textbooks in Secondary Schools in the UK.....	29
2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS.....	32
3 METHODS FOR DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS.....	33
3.1 Textbooks.....	33
3.2 Sample characteristics.....	33
3.3 Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook.....	36
4 ENERGY AND GENDER IN UK TEXTBOOKS	36
4.1. Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections	36
4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames	39
4.3 Energy.....	39
4.4 Climate Change.....	41

4.5 Energy security and poverty	41
4.6 Gender and energy technology	43
4.7 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)	43
4.8 Gender and energy labour market.....	44
4.9 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)	44
4.01 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy	44
4.02 Gender and energy governance	45
5 TEMPORALITIES.....	45
6 LANGUAGE.....	46
7 MISSING THEMES.....	46
8 OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES.....	46
9 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM.....	47
REFERENCES	47
APPENDIX 2. GERMAN NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS.....	51
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	51
1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH.....	52
1.1 Educational system in a country-brief characteristic	52
1.2 Energy education	53
2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS.....	55
3 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS	56
3.1 Corpus of Text	56
3.2 Sample Characteristics	56
3.3 Qualitative Data Analysis Driven by the Codebook.....	57
4 RESULTS.....	57
4.1 Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections	57
4.2 Energy – gender nexus through frames.....	58
4.3 Gender and energy technology	58
4.4 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)	58
4.5 Gender and energy labour market.....	58
4.6 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.).....	59
4.7 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy	59
4.8 Gender and energy governance.....	60
5 TEMPORALITIES.....	60

Guidance Note

6	LANGUAGE.....	61
7	MISSING THEMES.....	62
8	OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES.....	62
9	RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM.....	62
	SOURCES.....	65
	APPENDIX 3. ITALIAN NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS.....	67
	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	67
1	CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH.....	69
	1.1. Educational system in Italy - brief characteristics	69
	1.2. Energy education in Italy.....	70
2	MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS.....	71
3	METHODS OF DATA COLLECTING AND ANALYSIS	72
	3.1. Corpus of texts	72
	3.2 Sample characteristics.....	74
	3.3 Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook	75
4	RESULTS.....	76
	4.1. Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections	76
	4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames	76
	4.3 Gender and energy technology	76
	4.4 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)	76
	4.5 Gender and energy labour market.....	76
	4.6 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)	76
	4.7 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy.....	77
5	TEMPORALITIES.....	77
6	LANGUAGE.....	77
7	MISSING THEMES.....	81
8	OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES.....	82
9	CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM.....	97
	REFERENCE LIST	98

APPENDIX 4. POLISH NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN THE SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS.....	100
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	100
CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH.....	100
1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH.....	102
1.1 Educational system in a country- brief characteristics.....	102
1.2 Energy education.....	103
2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS.....	104
3 METHODOLOGY.....	104
3.1 The logic of research design.....	104
3.2 Corpus of texts.....	105
3.3. Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook.....	107
4 RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS.....	108
4.1 Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections.....	108
4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames.....	111
4.3 Gender and technology or energy resources.....	112
4.4 Gender and energy labour market.....	114
4.5 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.).....	116
4.6 Gender and energy governance.....	118
5 TEMPORALITIES.....	118
6 LANGUAGE.....	120
7 MISSING THEMES.....	121
8 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM.....	122
REFERENCES.....	127

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this report is to show how the gender perspective is implemented in energy education in school textbooks. The analysis includes purposively selected textbooks dealing with energy-related topics. Four European countries were selected for qualitative content analysis: Germany, Italy, Poland and the United Kingdom, and the national reports are the basis for the Guidance Notes.

The results indicate a lack of consideration of the energy-gender nexus in textbook content in all analysed samples. Even when the energy issue is presented in its social, economic and environmental context the nexus with gender related themes or challenges is never investigated, leaving no room for education on gendered energy practices. A noteworthy missing item is energy as a professional sector. The document makes several recommendations for integrating an innovative gender approach to energy education in primary and secondary schools.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 European Energy transition as a Great Multidimensional project. (Common goals vs diverse energy transition paths as a challenge in the European Union)

The energy transition in the European Union (EU) represents a profound shift from traditional fossil fuels to sustainable energy sources (Eurostat, 2024; Alagoz, Alghawi 2023). This transition is not just a technical change, but a multidimensional project with economic, social, environmental and political dimensions (Dall- Orsoletta et al, 2022). The EU's commitment to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 requires an integrated approach that considers the complexities and interdependencies of this transformation. It is a major political project that aims to unite the citizens of the different Member States around the common goal of becoming the first climate-neutral continent (Wagner, forthcoming)

In addition to the economic (investment and innovation, economic growth, market competitiveness and job creation) and environmental (emission reductions, phasing out of fossil fuels, protection of biodiversity, water management) dimensions, the social dimension of the energy transition is key for the future of the EU, aiming at creating a better, more inclusive and just society whose empowered citizens can live in safe and healthy conditions.

This highly normative visionary project faces many challenges in the implementation process. One of these is that each country has a unique energy profile, economic structure and social context, making a consistent approach complex. There are profound differences between EU Member States in terms of energy needs and levels of dependence on fossil fuels. The diversity of energy transitions in terms of investment capacities, technology and infrastructure gaps, different skill distributions, but also cultural and geopolitical factors, requires a set of policy tools to coordinate what may be the most challenging experiment in human history. These normative ideas of just transition, European solidarity, etc. are then translated into concrete policy tools to

mitigate some of the challenges: financial or security concerns, regulatory gaps, etc. What is crucial, however, is to respond to the demands of a changing world by developing symbolic resources.

The people-centred approach “recognizes the importance of putting people first in planning and policymaking for clean energy transitions. These are not just words. It will require innovative, focused policy design and implementation. Real community involvement takes time, effort and skill.” (World Economic Forum, 2024). In a broader understanding, this approach, including the reinvented patterns of thinking about human-nature, but also about human – human relations, must be integrated into the socialisation mechanisms across Europe. One such mechanism is institutionalised education.

1.2 Diverse educational systems in Europe as a challenge for learning energy transition and sustainable development

The primary and lower secondary education (ISCED levels 1 and 2) is obligatory in all education systems in Europe. They can however have different forms. In our analysis we based on the case studies including all three systems.

Single Structure Education: From the start to the end of compulsory education, all students follow a unified curriculum offering a general education. There is no transition phase between primary and lower secondary education (Poland).

Common Core Curriculum Provision: Upon completing primary education (ISCED level 1), all students move on to lower secondary education (ISCED level 2) and continue with the same general core curriculum (Italy, UK).

Differentiated Lower Secondary Education: After finishing primary education, students enter distinct educational pathways or specialized programs at the beginning or during lower secondary education. These pathways lead to different certificates upon completion (Germany).

Not only does the organisation of education structures differ between European countries, but also the historical, political, economic and cultural factors that influence the content and conditions of education. Education systems are often tailored to the specific needs of each society, such as responding to labour market demands, integrating immigrant populations and promoting social cohesion. On the other hand, there has been an increased focus on global education, which could address planetary challenges, promote shared values and provide skills to help students navigate an increasingly interconnected world. This is particularly important in a process as complex as the transition to sustainable economies and was recognised as a priority by the European Commission. “Integrating energy transition-related topics into mainstream education and training is a challenge across the EU. This could hamper the deployment of clean energy technologies and hinder the growth and competitiveness of the sector” (Digitalising the Energy System, European Commission).

Traditionally, energy issues have been associated with STEM education, with limited contribution from life sciences and even less from social sciences and humanities (SSH). Students' interest in STEM education is formed relatively early and becomes

Guidance Note

conscious around the age of 11-12 (Alam et al. 2021). At the same time, boys' and girls' career expectations are influenced by their confidence in science (PISA, 2015). Formal education of all stages remains one of the most important educational environments. Recently, the increasing need of Education for Sustainability has been recognised as a key priority in schools, which is motivated by necessity of finding a balance between environmental, social, cultural, political and economic imperatives that affect our future (Taylor et al. 2015, Watson 2017). In June 2022, the Council of the European Union (EEA, 2022) adopted a Recommendation on integrating sustainability into education and training for the green transition and sustainable development. This policy urges Member States to prioritize learning about the climate crisis and sustainability in both formal and non-formal education. It recommends:

- Prioritizing sustainability in education policies and programs
- Providing all learners with opportunities to learn about sustainability and the climate crisis.
- Investing national and EU funds in green and sustainable educational resources and infrastructure.
- Supporting educators in developing the skills to teach about sustainability and address eco-anxiety.
- Creating supportive, hands-on, and interdisciplinary learning environments relevant to local contexts.
- Involving students, staff, local authorities, youth organizations, and the research community in sustainability education.

Also in 2022, the European Commission published The European Sustainability Competence Framework to promote learning for environmental sustainability. This document defines "sustainability competence" as "enabling learners to embody sustainability values and to consider complex systems in order to take or request actions that restore and maintain the health of ecosystems and enhance equity, and to generate visions for sustainable futures" (Bianchi et al. 2022).

1.3 Why energy– gender nexus matters in education? Rationale, aims and scope of analysis

The energy sector and education pathways are interlinked. One of the underlying factors of underrepresentation of women in energy sector is gender imbalance in STEM education, especially in Engineering and ICT studies (Czako 2020) and much has been so far discussed about the need to integrate a gender perspective in the higher education curricula (for a review see Pailam, de Groot 2022). While it is higher education that directly feeds the pipeline of skilled professionals in the energy sector, it is necessary to acknowledge the impact of earlier educational stages on women and men's choices about their educational and professional paths (Clancy & Feenstra, 2019, IRENA 2019, Czako 2020):

"Decision about studying Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths (STEM) are formed early and become progressively more difficult to change as children grow older with girls losing interest earlier than boys which reduces the pool of talent to enter the RE sector." (Clancy & Feenstra, 2019: 9).

The curriculum, textbooks and other learning materials, alongside teachers and teaching strategies, are factors that influence the learning process and girls' participation and performance in STEM as they may perpetuate gender bias and curb their future career aspirations (UNESCO 2017). Therefore, teaching should be gender sensitive, i.e. consciously designed to recognise and acknowledge the evidence that boys/men and girls/women may bring different cultural baggage to their learning experience. It should consider the varied experiences, needs, interests, learning styles and motivations of students of different genders and diverse demographic backgrounds (Mills et al. 2008; UNESCO 2017, Czako 2020), without emphasizing one over the other (Sinnes, & Løken 2014). It is necessary that a curriculum builds on the prior experience and knowledge of students and encourage practical real-life applications (Mills et al. 2008; Grünberg 2011). At the same time, however, care should be taken not to convey stereotyped images of men and women and biases on notions of who energy professionals are, what knowledge is valued and what the roles of men and women in society and energy sector are (Sinnes, & Løken 2014; Pailman, de Groot 2022), since both the language and images used in school textbooks and teaching materials influence students' perceptions of social norms.

Gender inclusive curriculum also enables students to respond to the needs and values of society, fosters open-mindedness and a greater acceptance of diversity (Grünberg 2011).

Against this background the aim of the research carried out in four European countries (England, Germany, Italy and Poland) was to analyse how energy is taught in schools and map existing energy curricula and teaching materials from a gender perspective. A specific focus was placed on verifying whether the content of the textbooks used in compulsory education in any way encourages or discourages pupils to think about further education or careers in the energy sector. The analyses in four countries were driven by the following research questions:

- 1) Whether and, if so, how content related to energy education, i.e. processes of energy production, storage, use and management, is presented in a gender-sensitive way?
- 2) Whether representation of energy issues creates equal opportunities for students to develop their activities in energy-related sectors?
- 3) Whether and, if so, how the content related to the energy transition encourages women to participate in it?

This led to some observations about energy in the popular textbook, which is treated as a possible reference point for teaching processes, but also as a reflection of institutional thinking about how energy should be taught. The results then serve as a basis for formulating recommendations for all those involved in educational policy.

2 METHODOLOGY

Taking into account the diversity of education systems, we have used the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 11 as a universally adopted scheme for collecting global education statistics. It covers two main variables: educational attainment levels and fields of education and includes additional dimensions such as general/vocational/pre-vocational orientation and the transition from education to the labour market.

Guidance Note

The choice of subject for further analysis needs to be understood. The textbooks of different subjects were included in the country reports due to the different broader contexts in a broader context of the educational systems in England, Germany, Italy, and Poland and their unique structures and characteristics.

Across the UK, the education system is divided into five stages: early years, primary, secondary, Further Education (FE), and Higher Education (HE). Education is mandatory for all children from the ages of 5 (4 in Northern Ireland) to 16. FE, which is optional, includes non-advanced courses available at further education colleges and higher education institutions (HEIs). The final stage, HE, involves study beyond GCE A levels or their equivalents, typically pursued by full-time students at universities and other HEIs (https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/219167/v01-2012ukes.pdf)

Education in England is overseen by the Department for Education, with policy responsibilities devolved to local authorities. The national curriculum, mandatory for maintained schools but optional for academies and free schools, covers subjects such as English, Mathematics, and Science. Secondary education culminates in the General Certificate of Secondary Education (GCSE), followed by options for further education including A-Levels, apprenticeships, or vocational training.

Germany's educational system is highly decentralized, with significant variations across its federal states. Education is divided into primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. After primary school (up to grade 4 or 6, depending on the state), students choose among different secondary schools based on their academic performance and career aspirations: *Mittelschule*: Focuses on practical skills and vocational training. *Realschule*: Offers a broader education with technical and administrative subjects. *Gymnasium*: Prepares students for the Abitur and higher education. Education is mandatory up to grades 9 or 10, again depending on the state.

The Italian education system also follows a three-tier structure: primary, secondary, and tertiary education. Primary education lasts five years, followed by three years of lower secondary school and five years of upper secondary school. Students can choose different tracks in upper secondary school, such as *liceo* (focused on academic subjects), *istituto tecnico* (technical institutes), or *istituto professionale* (vocational schools). Education is compulsory until age 16.

Poland's education system is centralized, governed by the Ministry of National Education. Compulsory education starts at age 6 with one year of preschool, followed by primary education (lasting eight years). Secondary education includes general high schools, technical high schools, and vocational schools. Students in general and technical high schools take the matura exam, which is necessary for university admission. Vocational schools prepare students for specific trades and crafts. Education is compulsory until age 18. The possibility to obtain the Matura certificate is also open to graduates of the Stage II sectoral vocational school.

In all four countries, education is compulsory, but the age range varies. England mandates education from age 5 to 18, Germany and Italy from 6 to 16, and Poland from age 7 to 18. School Structure: England and Germany have more differentiated secondary education systems with multiple types of schools catering to different

academic and vocational paths. Italy and Poland have more streamlined paths but still offer vocational and technical education options. Curriculum and Exams: England and Germany emphasize standardized exams like GCSEs and the *Abitur*, while Italy and Poland have national exams like the *matura*. These exams are critical for higher education admission. Governance: Germany has a decentralized system with significant state autonomy, Poland is more centralized, while Italy, whose school system is based on the subsidiary principle, and England fall somewhere in between, with local authorities and various types of schools enjoying different levels of autonomy

Subsequently, this guide has been written on the basis of four country reports (attached as *Annexes 1, 2, 3 and 4*) prepared by the national teams. Each national team started with a contextual analysis, describing and mapping the educational landscape of the country (Italy, UK, Poland and Germany). This step was crucial because the education system varies significantly between EU countries, but also within countries (UK, Germany). After the analysis, we decided to capture the moment when children are deciding about their future educational path and when they are thinking about future careers (ISCED 2,3).¹We argue that this period is crucial in deciding whether to push for a more SSH or STEM career.

Table 1. Sample description

N.	Country/region	Subjects	Age of kids considered	ISCED level	Number of analysed textbooks
1.	UK (England)	Geography, Science, Design and Technology	11-16	2,3	16 textbooks
2.	Germany (Bavaria, Berlin)	Geography, Social Sciences, General Sciences, Nature and Technology and Biology	10-16	2,3	17 textbooks
3.	Italy	Science and Technology, Geography, Technology, Technical Drawing, Science, Life on Earth, Human Body, Science - Earth, Geography	9-16	1,2,3	15 textbooks
4.	Poland	Physics, Geography, History, Social Studies, Safety Education, Entrepreneurship, Chemistry, History and the present	12-16	2,3	16 textbooks

In England, the Imperial College team analysed 3 subjects (Geography, Science, Design and Technology) using the 16 textbooks designed for 11–15-year-olds. The selection of the analysed sample was based on the examination of the National Curriculum for England, which showed that energy and related issues (e.g. climate;

¹ In Italy some primary schools textbooks were considered additionally

climate change; sustainability) are covered in science (biology; chemistry; physics; but generally, as a physical phenomenon), in design and technology (minimally) and in geography (most and in depth).

In Germany, the Fraunhofer team analysed 5 subjects (Geography, Social Sciences, General Sciences, Nature and Technology and Biology) from a total of 17 textbooks for children aged 10-16 in two regions, Bavaria and Berlin. A preliminary scan of all textbooks for the selected subjects, grades and federal states was carried out via the websites of the three major publishers (Cornelsen, Westermann and Klett). For those textbooks that appeared to mention the energy sector, visits were made to the infopoints for a more detailed examination. After identifying the relevant books dealing with energy, climate change and related topics, these books were either scanned at the Infopoints or donated for further analysis.

In Italy, the ENEA team analysed 9 subjects (Science and Technology, Geography, Technology, Technical Drawing, Science, Life on Earth, Human Body, Science - Earth,) consisting of 15 textbooks. The selection of the analysed sample was based on subject relevance, published popularity, date of publication and availability due to lack of budget (for more details see Annex X).

In Poland, the team from the Jagiellonian University analysed 16 textbooks from the 8 subjects (physics, geography, history, social studies, safety education, entrepreneurship, chemistry, history and the present) for children aged 12 to 16. The selection of the analysed sample was done by analysing the most recent core curriculum for subjects in primary school (grades 7 and 8) and secondary school in order to assess whether certain keywords were included. These keywords were: energy, environment, resources, electricity, nuclear, atomic and electric.

The exact sampling method is described in detail in each country report (for more details: see *appendix 1,2,3,4*).

3 ENERGY EDUCATION DIMENSIONS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

We found similarities between countries in terms of general characteristics, but there are also differences in terms of more detailed content and what is taught. Particularly important is the introduction of new topics and the approach to teaching energy.

The key observation in all countries analysed is that rare occurrences of gender codes do not provide a basis for further comments. Despite careful analysis at different levels, textual and visual, the gender elements were marginal, and it was not possible to reconstruct an energy-gender nexus in the content. The language is used as gender-neutral even in German or Polish, which are gendered in grammar and lexicon.

The observed (rare) reference to gender can be found in the more general framework of STEM. Technical experts are more often represented by male professionals, while a more diverse gender picture can be found in social activism. It could have consequences for energy sectors: in the landscape of employment, jobs that centre on innovation and technology are predominantly occupied by men. This trend

underscores a gender disparity that continues to pervade high-tech and innovative roles, hinting at the need for more inclusive recruitment and development strategies.

Conversely, roles focused on energy use show a more diverse representation of individuals. This diversity reflects a wider range of perspectives and experiences, which can be critical in addressing the multifaceted challenges of energy use and management.

The energy sector still suffers from a lack of a people-centred approach. Policies and initiatives are often designed and implemented without adequate consideration of the needs, behaviours and insights of the communities they affect. This gap can lead to inefficiencies and missed opportunities for more effective and equitable energy solutions. It is reflected in the way energy is taught- in the context of physical, biological and chemical phenomena, in the social world related to economy and technology. Both are presented however as systemic environment that includes rather consumers or final users, than subject whose action shape the system structures. This deterministic pattern of thinking identified in the textbooks is surprising in the context of the people-centred approach highlighted in the research agenda (Broto et al. 2017) and prioritised in recent energy policies (IEA, 2024).

Furthermore, the link between energy initiatives and sustainability goals, particularly the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), remains tenuous. While the efforts to increase renewable energy deployment, energy efficiency and energy accessibility are mentioned, and climate change topic is clearly related to energy sources, these are not consistently integrated into a broader sustainability framework. The exception is Italy, where STEM teachers are tasked with contributing to the sustainability area of teaching of civic education, a transversal subject that includes issues such as energy, climate change and the UN AGENDA 2030. In general, however, the link between energy policies and the SDGs needs to be strengthened to ensure that progress in the energy sector contributes meaningfully to global sustainability targets.

4 KEY MISSING THEMES

The review of chosen European textbooks revealed significant gaps in the coverage of critical energy-related topics. These omissions are of concern as they hinder the development of informed and proactive citizens who can contribute to sustainable energy practices and decision making.

Table 2. Gaps in energy-related topics

Theme	Definition	Current Coverage	Implications
Energy Citizenship	Engaging individuals in energy decision-making and fostering community involvement.	Notably absent. Some recommendations for sustainable routines exist, but comprehensive discussions are missing. Again, the exception is Italy, where the debate about nuclear energy is mentioned, also the development of environmental movements.	Students are less likely to become engaged citizens participating in energy-related community decisions and initiatives.
Energy Independence	The ability of a country or community to produce its own energy, reducing reliance on external sources and disruptions.	Focus on energy dependence, with little to no exploration of strategies for achieving energy independence.	Students are unprepared to understand and address the importance of developing independent energy systems that enhance resilience.
People-Centred Energy Practices	Encompasses sustainable practices such as recycling, water conservation, and energy-efficient dietary habits.	Insufficiently covered in the reviewed materials.	Students may not adopt or advocate for sustainable practices crucial for long-term environmental stewardship.
Energy Availability	Understanding the factors influencing the supply of energy and its impact on society.	Almost not addressed in the schoolbooks.	Students do not comprehend how energy availability affects economic stability, societal development, and quality of life.
Security	Security is understood in the context of energy affordability related to access to grids, infrastructure, cost of energy etc.	Security-related aspects of energy, such as protecting infrastructure and ensuring access, are completely neglected.	Students are unaware of the critical role that energy security plays in national safety and economic stability.
Energy as a Professional Field	Understanding energy careers and their gender implications.	Completely absent. No information or conceptual tools are provided for considering energy careers.	Students, especially girls and those interested in SSH, are left unaware of possibility of career in energy sectors
Energy poverty	It occurs when individuals or households are unable to afford the necessary energy services to maintain a decent standard of living. This includes the inability to adequately heat or cool their homes, power necessary appliances, and access clean cooking facilities.	Almost absent. No information provided about the factors influencing energy poverty or conceptualising energy poverty as a social problem	Educating students is a key step in raising broader public awareness. Without it, energy poverty remains an invisible issue to many, reducing the societal impetus for change. Ignoring energy poverty in education contributes to the perpetuation of social inequality.

5 LANGUAGE- PROBLEMATISING “GENDER NEUTRALITY”

While gender neutrality in energy education aims to create an unbiased learning environment, it can also lead to gender blindness, where the specific needs and challenges of different genders are ignored. Balancing gender neutrality with explicit awareness and discussion of gender issues can help create a more inclusive and equitable education system. This approach ensures that all students are prepared to engage with energy issues in a way that recognizes and addresses the diverse experiences and contributions of all genders.

Gender-neutral language, which is the preferred approach in all of the textbooks analysed, meets contradictory criteria described above and as such is problematic and requires further research.

6 INCLUSIVE GENDER–ENERGY TEACHING RECOMMENDATIONS

Stanford's Gender Innovation Approach (GIA, 2024) emphasizes the integration of gender perspectives and inclusive practices in innovation and research. Applying this approach to energy education in schools can have several benefits and contribute to a more inclusive and equitable understanding of energy issues.

The inclusive gender – energy curriculum can create the chain of skills supporting achieving the goals of sustainable transition (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The chain of skills in sustainable transition

Source: own elaboration

These challenges are then translated into more specific, practical recommendations for inclusive gender energy education:

Guidance Note

1. Educating students about how energy poverty disproportionately affects women, who may rely more on traditional cooking methods that produce harmful smoke, can highlight the health and safety implications of energy access.
2. Ensuring that energy education materials and examples include diverse gender perspectives can help students see themselves and their communities in the curriculum. This inclusivity can inspire more students, especially girls, to take an interest in energy-related fields.
3. Including gender-related case studies and examples in the curriculum can provide a more balanced view of how energy issues affect different demographic groups, highlighting the social dimensions of energy use and policy.
4. Discussing gender-related energy issues encourages critical thinking about how societal norms and policies affect different groups differently, promoting a more nuanced understanding of energy issues.
5. Teaching students to consider gender in energy solutions can lead to more innovative and inclusive approaches. For example, designing energy-efficient technologies that meet the needs of both men and women can improve adoption rates and effectiveness.
6. Including stories and examples of women and gender-diverse individuals who have made significant contributions to the energy sector can inspire students. Schools can invite women and non-binary energy professionals to speak and act as mentors.
7. Actively encouraging girls and gender-diverse students to pursue STEM subjects and careers in the energy sector can help close the gender gap in these fields. Providing support and resources tailored to their needs can boost their confidence and interest.
8. Promoting SSH as providing the necessary and useful knowledge for socially responsible energy governance and the creation of energy citizenship can open up new career opportunities for students interested in this field, but also create more comprehensive societal responses to the challenges posed by the complexity of the energy transition.
9. Educating students about how energy poverty disproportionately affects women, who may rely more on traditional cooking methods

that produce harmful smoke, can highlight the health and safety implications of energy access.

10. Teaching about how energy access can empower women economically—by enabling new business opportunities and reducing the time spent on household chores—can illustrate the broader social benefits of equitable energy distribution.
11. Integrating discussions about gender-inclusive energy policies can prepare students to think about and advocate for policies that consider the needs of all genders. This includes policies related to energy access, affordability, and employment in the energy sector.
12. Equipping students with the skills to analyze and advocate for gender-sensitive energy policies can empower them to become future leaders and change-makers in the field.
13. Providing information about career opportunities in the energy sector, with a focus on the importance of gender diversity, can encourage more students to consider these paths. Highlighting the benefits of diverse teams in driving innovation can further motivate students.

Proposed recommendations are going to be discussed with students and practitioners in the next step of the research.

Acknowledgements

This report is the result of extensive analysis carried out under WP3 of the gEneSys project - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems (101094326). The authors would like to thank the members of the teams that prepared the detailed national reports that form the basis of this guide. Their input at all stages of the work on the guidance analysis was crucial. The authors are also grateful to all the members of the consortium for the discussions on both the methodology and the interpretation of the data. Special thanks are due to the project leaders in the CNR team for their continued support and substantial help in reviewing and editing this document.

REFERENCES

- Alagoz E., Alghawi Y., (2023) The Energy Transition: Navigating the Shift Towards Renewables in the Oil and Gas Industry. *Journal of Energy and Natural Resources*. Vol. 12, No. 2, 2023, pp. 21-24. doi: 10.11648/j.jenr.20231202.12.
- Bianchi, G., Pisiotis, U. and Cabrera Giraldez, M., GreenComp The European sustainability competence framework, Punie, Y. and Bacigalupo, M. (2022) editor(s), EUR 30955 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-46485-3, doi:10.2760/13286, JRC128040.
- Broto, V. C., Stevens, L., Ackom, E., Tomei, J., Parikh, P., Bisaga, I., To, L. S., Kirshner, J., & Mulugetta, Y. (2017). A research agenda for a people-centred approach to energy access in the urbanizing global south. *Nature Energy*, 2(10), 776-779. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-017-0007-x>
- Clancy, J., Feenstra M. (2019). *Women, gender equality and the energy transition in the EU*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Czako, V. (2020). Employment in the Energy Sector JRC SCIENCE FOR POLICY REPORT, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Dall-Orsoletta, A., Cunha, J. Araújo, M., Ferreira, P. (2022). A systematic review of social innovation and community energy transitions, *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 88, 2022, 102625, ISSN 2214-6296, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102625>.
- Du, X., Kolmos A. (2009). "Increasing the diversity of engineering education—a gender analysis in a PBL context." *European Journal of Engineering Education* 34.5: 425-437.
- EEA [European Education Area], (2022). <https://education.ec.europa.eu/news/learning-for-the-green-transition-and-sustainable-development>
- European Commission / EACEA / Eurydice, (2023). The structure of the European education systems 2023/2024: schematic diagrams. Eurydice Facts and Figures. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- EA (2024), *Global Summit on People-Centred Clean Energy Transitions Framing Note*, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/global-summit-on-people-centred-clean-energy-transitions-framing-note>, Licence: CC BY 4.0
- Eurostat, 2024. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Energy_statistics_-_an_overview, data extracted in May 2024.
- GIA, (2024) Gender Innovative Approach, <https://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/what-is-gendered-innovations.html>, [access online 1.06.2024]
- Grünberg, L. (2011), Introduction. From Gender Studies to Gender IN Studies and beyond, in: L. Grünberg (ed.), *From Gender Studies to Gender IN Studies Case*

Studies on Gender-Inclusive Curriculum in Higher Education, Bucharest: European Center for Higher Education, 7-15.

IRENA (2019a). Renewable energy: A gender perspective. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2019/Jan/IRENA_Gender_perspective_2019.pdf

Mills, J.E., Ayre, M. E. & J. Gill (2008), Perceptions and understanding of gender inclusive curriculum in engineering education. 36th Annual SEFI conference 2-5 July, Aalborg, Denmark.

Pailman, W., de Groot J. (2022). Rethinking education for SDG 7: A framework for embedding gender and critical skills in energy access masters programmes in Africa. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 90, 102615.

Sinnes, A. T., Løken M. (2014). "Gendered education in a gendered world: looking beyond cosmetic solutions to the gender gap in science." *Cultural studies of science education* 9: 343-364.

Taylor N., Quinn F., Eames Ch. (eds.) (2015). *Educating for Sustainability in Primary Schools. Teaching for the Future*, Rotterdam: Sense Publishers.

Wagner A. forthcoming, Future in 3D narratives. A vision for Europe's future in the context of the energy transition: decarbonisation, democratisation and digitalization. Analysis of EU documents.

Watson, A. (2017), "Sustainability Education in Primary and Secondary Schools: Great Needs and Possible Solutions". Chancellor' Honors Program Projects. https://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_chanhonoproj/2026

World Economic Forum, (2024). <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2024/06/people-centred-approach-towards-equitable-energy-transitions/>

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1. GENDER IN THE TEACHING OF ENERGY IN SECONDARY EDUCATION TEXTBOOKS IN ENGLAND, UK**Gender in the Teaching of Energy in Secondary Education Textbooks in England, UK**

Yara Evans and Rocio Diaz-Chavez

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report centres on the analysis of gender in the teaching of energy in textbooks in secondary school level education in England. This report aimed at examining

- whether content related to energy education (i.e., processes of energy production, storage, use and management) is presented in a gender-sensitive way
- whether representation of energy issues creates equal opportunities for students to develop their knowledge and skills in energy-related sectors
- and whether and how content related to the various dimensions of energy transition may encourage young girls to develop a greater interest in energy and in energy related careers.

The analysis focuses on the upper stages of compulsory secondary education in England (Key Stage 3, 11-14 years old; and Key Stage 4, 14-16 years old), since these stages cover a common foundational programme that helps pave the way for future education choices for completing compulsory education (i.e., academic, or vocational).

Examination of the National Curriculum for England showed that the theme of energy and related themes (e.g. climate; climate change; sustainability) are covered in Science (Biology; Chemistry; Physics; but generally, as a physical phenomenon), in Design and Technology (minimally), and in Geography (to the most extent and in greater depth).

A literature review revealed a lack of mandatory textbooks for in use secondary schools and that textbooks are not a core teaching/learning resource either. Textbooks are generally selected by teachers or headteachers in response to publishers' recommendations, and recommended textbooks are geared towards examinations set by specific exam boards.

A total of 16 textbooks were selected for analysis, which revealed:

- a near total absence of 'gender' considerations in the teaching of energy and related topics, due largely to an embedded gender neutrality in the English language
- more evidence of a 'gender blindness' than 'gender bias'
- the occasional use of the word 'people' which could be challenged in some cases
- occasional use of plural nouns (we/us)

Addressing this lack of concern with gender would require:

- Integrating a gender perspective into all relevant secondary education disciplines in the National Curriculum that have a component on 'energy'
- Creating energy as a subject on its own right in the National Curriculum for secondary education and associated themes that integrates a gender perspective
- Highlight in textbooks the gendered contribution to the development of all subjects related to energy to encourage girls and young women to develop a greater interest on STEM fields and pursue them into higher education
- Making much greater use in textbooks of case studies drawn from scholar sources of energy to widen the scope for examining energy issues from a gender perspective

1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

This report centres on the analysis of textbooks for secondary school level education in England.

1.1 The UK Education System

The government in the UK is responsible for providing education to school-age children. Education has been a devolved policy area since 1999, leading to some differences in the education systems in England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales, to which are added those that reflect their own historical development (Roberts, 2021; Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021). In England, there is a Department for Education, which is responsible for: setting out the subject content for teaching and the exams syllabi for certification; the policy for mandatory education content to be taught at state-run schools; measures for evaluating school performance (Ofqual, 2020).

In England, children must start full-time education once they reach compulsory school age (5 years-old) on 31 December, 31 March or 31 August following their fifth birthday (whichever comes first). Education was compulsory for children from 5 to 16 years of age, but in 2015, it was extended to age 18. Figure 1 shows the four key phases of compulsory education along with the respective age groups for each of these stages.

Figure 1 The UK Education System (source: <https://jaybridge.cy/uk-education-system/>)

As can be seen, the education system is divided into four main phases: primary education, secondary education, further education, and higher education. Primary education starts at age 5 (year 1) and ends at ages 10-11 (year 6). Secondary education starts at ages 11-12 (year 7) and concludes at ages 15-16 (Year 11), with students taking mandatory texts to obtain their General Certificate of secondary Education (GCSE). Between ages 16-18 (Further Education), students have to choose from the following:

- stay in full-time education to study for advanced qualifications (A-Levels) for admission into university
- start an apprenticeship
- spend 20 hours or more a week working or volunteering, while in part-time education or training (to obtain vocational qualifications)

Beyond age 18, students may proceed to read for a degree at university (Higher Education) if they have obtained the necessary qualifications. The focus of the analysis here is on secondary education since it is still based on a common foundational programme (see below) that helps pave the way for future education choices for completing compulsory education (i.e., academic, or vocational).

Schools of a various types provide compulsory education in England. These include state-funded schools run by local authorities; academies; free schools; grammar schools (a type of selective state-funded secondary school where admission is based on academic ability, typically determined by performance in entrance exams); faith schools; and private and independent schools. School-age children may also receive 'home schooling', that is, education at home or a variety of places if not attending a school. Academies (state-funded schools independent of the local authority), and free schools (funded by the government but not run by the local authority) comprise a majority of secondary schools in England (Kulakiewicz et al, 2021).

1.2 The Key Stages

The four phases of compulsory education in England/the UK are further split into *key stages*, as follows: Key Stage 1 (5-7 years old); Key Stage 2 (7-11 years old); Key Stage 3 (11-14 years old); and Key Stage 4 (14-16). The National Curriculum (NC) sets out the programme that must be covered by state-run schools in each of these key stages. Other types of schools (e.g., free schools, and academies) do not need to follow the NC (although many do) but must then offer broad and balanced curriculum that covers English, Maths, Sciences and Religious Education (Roberts, 2021; Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021).

In the first two years of secondary education (Year 7, ages 11-12; Year 8, ages 12-13) all children must study English, Maths, Sciences, a Humanity subject, and a Modern Language. They may also choose from optional subjects, which are: Art, Music, Drama, Latin, Sport Science, Design Technology and Computer Science. Year 9 (ages 13-14) provides a foundation for the General Certificate of Secondary Education programme, and students continue to study the compulsory subjects and optional subjects that they are free to choose. These years correspond to Key Stage 3 (or Lower Secondary School).

In the last two years of secondary education (Year 10, ages 14-15; Year 11, ages 15-16) children take on the GCSE programme to prepare for exams, studying anything between nine and 12 subjects. English, Math, Sciences, History/Geography, and a Modern language are compulsory subjects. In addition, students can choose further subjects to study according to their interests and abilities. At the end of the GCSE programme, children sit exams on each of the subjects they studied, and on passing, receive the GCSE. This corresponds to Key Stage 4 (or for convenience, Upper Secondary School).

The GCSE grade results determine progress to Further Education. After passing the GCSE, students can start a two-year programme that leads to Advanced Level examinations (A-Levels), specializing subjects relevant to the degree subject they may wish to follow at university, being able to choose from around 80 subjects. After gaining A-Level certification, they are able to study at university. A-Levels are state-examinations that are recognized by all universities in the UK and also worldwide.

1.3 Compulsory Education Qualifications

The Office of Qualifications and Examinations Regulation (Ofqual) regulates qualifications, examinations, and assessments in England (academic and vocational). Ofqual designates which organisations can offer secondary school certification and sets out the regulations to that exam boards must follow. Exam boards develop, deliver, and mark the exam papers, and award the qualifications (Ofqual, 2020). Currently, there are four exam boards in England:

- AQA: the Assessment and Qualifications Alliance
- CCEA: Council for Curriculum and Examinations Assessment
- OCR: Oxford, Cambridge and RSA Examinations
- Pearson Edexcel

1.4 The National Curriculum and Energy Education in Secondary School

In England, state-funded schools must provide education to school-age children within the framework of the National Curriculum (NC). The NC was created in 1988. It was last revised in 2013-2014 (DfE, 2014a) and introduced in schools in September 2014, although the content of some subjects was modified later (e.g., English and Maths, 2016; and Science, 2016).

The new NC sets out the core knowledge children are expected to learn on different subjects up to age 16, around which teachers can develop lessons to promote the development of children's knowledge, understanding and skills as part of the wider school curriculum (Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021). It sets out the programmes of study and attainment targets for all four key stages of education around core and foundation subjects, which contain statutory guidance, outlining what schools and local authorities cover on each subject at each key stage to comply with the law. However, individual schools are expected to teach beyond the core set of information defined in programmes of study for each subject and level (DfE, 2014a; Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021). State-run schools must teach the NC but there is no requirement as to how they organise subject teaching and how much time may be spent on the teaching of any one subject, this is left totally to their discretion (Roberts, 2021). However, academies and free schools are not required to teach the NC, although many do (Kulakiewicz, et al, 2021). Table 1 illustrates the structure of the NC, showing the compulsory subjects that must be taught at each key stage. In addition, all schools must teach religious education at all key stages, whilst secondary school must provide sex and relationship education. After the age of 14, the arts, Design and Technology, humanities, and modern foreign language cease to be compulsory NC subjects, but all children in state-run schools must be able to study a subject in each of these four areas if they so wish.

Table 1 National Curriculum Structure

<i>Secondary school</i>				
	Key Stage 1	Key Stage 2	Key Stage 3	Key Stage 4
Age	5-7	7-11	11-14	14-16
Year groups	1-2	3-6	7-9	10-11
<i>Core subjects</i>				
English	Ü	Ü	Ü	Ü
Mathematics	Ü	Ü	Ü	Ü
Science	Ü			
<i>Foundation subjects</i>				
Art and design	Ü	Ü	Ü	
Citizenship			Ü	Ü
Computing	Ü	Ü	Ü	Ü
Design and Technology	Ü	Ü	Ü	
(Modern) Foreign Languages		Ü	Ü	
Geography	Ü	Ü	Ü	
History	Ü	Ü	Ü	
Music	Ü	Ü	Ü	
Physical education	Ü	Ü	Ü	Ü
Source: DfE (2014a)				

In the NC for secondary school (KS3 and KS4), the topic of energy is covered in different disciplines to varying extents, most notably in Science (which comprises Biology, Chemistry, Physics) and Geography, and to a lesser extent in Design and Technology. However, the analysis here focuses on *energy in use* (i.e., production, consumption, storage, and distribution) and associated topics rather than on energy as a physical phenomenon (which excludes large part of the Science curricula) or energy in the food context. Topics related to the climate, the environment and sustainability issues are covered in the Geography and to a lesser extent, in the Science curricula. In Geography, this includes study of the climate, how human and physical processes interact to influence and change landscapes, environments, and the climate. In science, this covers climate and ecosystems in Biology and Chemistry, including how human interaction with ecosystems impacts on biodiversity (Kulakiewicz et al, 2021).

On science education, the NC notes that the overall purpose is to build up a body of key foundational knowledge and concepts that encourage ‘children to recognise the power of rational explanation and develop a sense of excitement and curiosity about natural phenomena’ and encourage the use science to explain ‘what is occurring, predict how things will behave, and analyse causes’ (DfE, 2013a; 2014a, 2015a). Table 2 shows the subject content of interest that must be taught in each discipline as mandated by the NC.

Table 2 Coverage of Energy and Associated Themes in the National Curriculum for science at KS3 and KS4

Subject content that must be taught in each discipline - KS3	
Biology	
Photosynthesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the dependence of almost all life on Earth on the ability of photosynthetic organisms (e.g. plants and algae), to use sunlight in photosynthesis to build organic molecules that are an essential energy store and to maintain levels of oxygen and carbon dioxide in the atmosphere
Physics	
Calculation of fuel uses and costs in the domestic context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> fuels and energy resources
Energy changes and transfers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> burning fuels
Subject content that must be taught in each discipline - KS4	
Biology	
Ecosystems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the role of microorganisms (decomposers) in the cycling of materials through an ecosystem the importance of biodiversity positive and negative human interactions with ecosystems
Chemistry	
Chemical and allied industries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> life cycle assessment and recycling to assess environmental impacts associated with all the stages of a product's life the viability of recycling of certain materials carbon compounds, both as fuels and feedstock, and the competing demands for limited resources fractional distillation of crude oil and cracking to make more useful materials
Earth and atmospheric science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> evidence for composition and evolution of the Earth's atmosphere since its formation evidence, and uncertainties in evidence, for additional anthropogenic causes of climate change, including the correlation between change in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration and the consumption of fossil fuels, and describe the uncertainties in the evidence base potential effects of, and mitigation of, increased levels of carbon dioxide and methane on the Earth's climate

	<p>and how these effects may be mitigated, including consideration of scale, risk and environmental implications</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • common atmospheric pollutants: sulphur dioxide, oxides of nitrogen, particulates and their sources
Physics	
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • renewable and non-renewable energy sources used on Earth; changes in how these are used
Atomic structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • radioactive materials, half-life, irradiation, contamination and their associated hazardous effects; waste disposal • nuclear fission, nuclear fusion and our Sun's energy
Carbon dioxide and methane as greenhouse gases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the greenhouse effect in terms of the interaction of radiation with matter • the evidence for additional anthropogenic causes of climate change, including the correlation between change in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration and the consumption of fossil fuels, and describe the uncertainties in the evidence base • the potential effects of increased levels of carbon dioxide and methane on the Earth's climate and how these effects may be mitigated, including consideration of scale, risk and environmental implications
Sources: DfE (2013a; 2014a; 2015)	

Regarding the discipline of Geography, the overall purpose of education is to equip children with knowledge about diverse places, people, resources and natural and human environments, as well deep understanding of the Earth's key physical and human processes (DfE, 2014a, c, d). Table 3 shows the subject content of interest that must be taught in Geography as mandated by the NC.

Table 3 Coverage of Relevant Themes to Energy Transition in the National Curriculum for Geography at KS3 and KS4

Subject content that must be taught in Geography – KS3	
Human and Physical Geography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand, through the use of detailed place-based exemplars at a variety of scales, the key processes: • physical Geography relating to: geological timescales and plate tectonics; rocks, weathering and soils; weather and climate, including the change in climate from the Ice Age to the present; and glaciation, hydrology and coasts

Guidance Note

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • human Geography relating to: population and urbanisation; international development; economic activity in the primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors; and the use of natural resources • -understand how human and physical processes interact to influence, and change landscapes, environments and the climate; and how human activity relies on effective functioning of natural systems
Subject content that must be taught in Geography – KS4	
Physical Geography: processes and change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • changing weather and climate – • the causes, consequences of and responses to extreme weather conditions and natural weather hazards, recognising their changing distribution in time and space and drawing on an understanding of the global circulation of the atmosphere. • the spatial and temporal characteristics, of climatic change and evidence for different causes, including human activity, from the beginning of the Quaternary period (2.6 million years ago) to the present day
People and environment: processes and interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • global ecosystems and biodiversity – an overview of the distribution and characteristics of large scale natural global ecosystems. For two selected ecosystems, draw out the interdependence of climate, soil, water, plants, animals and humans; the processes and interactions that operate within them at different scales; and issues related to biodiversity and to their sustainable use and management • resources and their management –an overview of how humans use, modify and change ecosystems and environments in order to obtain food, energy and water resources. Detailed study of one of either food, energy or water, recognising the changing characteristics and distribution of demand and supply, past and present impacts of human intervention, and issues related to their sustainable use and management at a variety of scales.
Sources: DfE (2014a, c, d)	

In Design and Technology, the overall purpose of education is to develop in children their creativity and imagination to design and make products that solve real and relevant problems within a variety of contexts. They will acquire a broad range of

subject knowledge, drawing on various disciplines (e.g., Maths, Science, Engineering, Computing and Art) to develop a critical understanding of the impact of Design and Technology on daily life and the wider world (DfE 2103b; DfE 2015b). Table 4 shows the subject content in Design and Technology that must be taught in secondary school that covers themes relevant to the energy transition.

Table 4 Coverage of Relevant Themes to Energy Transition in the NC for Design and Technology at KS3 and KS4

Subject content that must be taught in Design and Technology – KS3	
Evaluate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test, evaluate and refine their ideas and products against a specification, taking into account the views of intended users and other interested groups • understand developments in Design and Technology, its impact on individuals, society and the environment, and the responsibilities of designers, engineers and technologists
Subject content that must be taught in Design and Technology – KS4	
Technical knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the impact of new and emerging technologies on industry, enterprise, sustainability, people, culture, society and the environment, production techniques and systems • how the critical evaluation of new and emerging technologies informs design decisions, considering contemporary and potential future scenarios from different perspectives, such as ethics and the environment • how energy is generated and stored in order to choose and use appropriate sources to make products and to power systems • the sources, origins, physical and working properties of the material categories or the components and systems, and their ecological and social footprint • the way in which the selection of materials or components is influenced by a range of factors, such as functional, aesthetic, environmental, availability, cost, social, cultural and ethical •
Designing and making principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • understand that all design and technological practice takes place within contexts which inform outcomes • investigate factors, such as environmental, social and economic challenges, in order to identify opportunities and constraints that influence the processes of designing and making

Guidance Note

Links to science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • life cycle assessment and recycling: the basic principles in carrying out a life-cycle assessment of a material or product; selection of materials and components based on ethical factors, taking into consideration the ecological and social footprint of materials • using materials: the main energy sources available for use on Earth (including fossil fuels, nuclear fuel, biofuel, wind, hydro- electricity, the tides and the Sun), the ways in which they are used and the distinction between renewable and non- renewable sources; understanding of how to choose appropriate energy sources
Sources: DfE (2014; 2013b; 2015b)	

Overall, no specific energy-related competencies are covered in the different disciplines that must be taught in secondary school under the NC framework.

1.5 Use of Textbooks in Secondary Schools in the UK

The 2014 NC in England specifies the minimum content to be covered by schools, and teachers and headteachers (as opposed to governing boards) have been largely responsible for determining the content of the curriculum to be taught, and the courses they offer and the content they cover (Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021).

There are no mandatory textbooks for use in secondary schools in the UK (i.e., no direct state approval or endorsement of any textbooks). However, textbooks that are commonly endorsed by organisations offering state-approved examinations and the choice of textbooks by schools is strongly linked to their choice of examination boards (Oates, 2014). Hence, schools may adopt textbooks from a variety of commercial publishers, where the content is tailored to specific exam board examinations (see section 2.1.3) or specific sections of the NC. Schools may select them, stock them up in their library and keep them in the classroom for children to use and share in class when necessary, and they may also recommend textbooks for home study and revision. These study resources may also be made available to children in digital form, alongside extra content (e.g., videos, audios) that can be accessed through specific platforms (e.g., Google Classroom) used by the school. The 1996 Education Act prohibits state-schools from charging for the supply of materials (including books and tablets) during school hours, but schools are allowed to charge for materials that the children's parent wishes them to own them, although schools may ask for parents' contributions to meet costs (DfE, 2018). A survey of headteachers in the UK showed that 28% thought that a schools' capacity to provide effective instruction was hindered by lack of educational materials (e.g. books and IT equipment), and 24% thought that it was hindered by the inadequate or poor quality of educational materials (Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021).

Teachers have great discretion in terms of the teaching materials and resources they use, as long as these help deliver the mandatory NC subject content (Sibieta and Jerrim, 2021). Commonly, teachers will draw lesson content from online sources and will also prepare worksheets for students to work on, during class, or as homework. Whilst textbooks are still used in schools in the UK, a 'textbooks have been on the decline for a long time in England's classroom' (DfE2017) and their use is seen as 'a controversial issue' (Oates, 2014: 5). This is clear, for instance, in the comments by the Minister of State for School Reform at the time of the 2014 NC review. The minister noted an 'ideological hostility to the use of textbooks', dating back to the 1970s, which led to their substitution with 'work sheets and hundreds of thousands of bespoke written lesson plans', which had increased teachers' workload, detracting on coherence and impacting on standards', although there was hope that the review would lead to 'the renaissance of intellectually demanding and knowledge-rich textbooks in England's schools' (Oates, 2014).

The study by Oates (2014) of over 200 textbooks, teacher guides and student workbooks for primary and secondary schooling from around the world (Hong Kong, Singapore, Finland, the US, England, and Canada) on central subjects (Maths, Geography, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, History, Literature and First Language learning) highlights the issues about textbooks in England. One central issue is that KS4 teachers (teaching students aged 14-16) have been conditioned by performance tables into developing a highly instrumental approach to learning that focuses on assessment outcomes. This approach has come to dominate 'curriculum thinking' in schools and has, in turn, conditioned publishers to produce textbooks and other resources that meet teachers' content demand. But their quality is seen to lag significantly behind that of resources produced in other countries. Oates (2014) also reports on country surveys on teachers' use of textbooks as either as core or supplementary in their teaching. Table 4 shows the results relating to two subjects, in England and two other countries.

Table 3 Students Whose Teacher Use Textbooks or Worksheets (%)

Subject	England	Finland	Singapore
<i>Maths</i>			
<i>Textbooks as a basis for instruction</i>	10	95	70
<i>As a supplement</i>	64	3	23
<i>Workbooks or worksheets as basis for instruction</i>			
<i>As a supplement</i>	11	37	71
	78	61	29
<i>Science</i>			
<i>Textbooks as a basis for instruction</i>	4	94	68
<i>As a supplement</i>	45	6	27
<i>Workbooks or worksheets as basis for instruction</i>			
<i>As a supplement</i>	4	40	69
	82	54	31
Source: in Oates (2014)			

Guidance Note

As can be seen, in England, textbooks are not used as core resources in teaching, in stark contrast to Finland and Singapore, which is explained by an underlying 'anti-textbook ethos' in England (Oates, 2014: 8). This ethos is seen to have contributed to a 'fundamental market failure in England', whereby lack of demand by teachers for good textbooks has meant that publishers neglect to supply high-quality books, and so only low-quality textbooks are used in classrooms, if any at all (DfE, 2017; Oates et al, 2021). This trend may be bucking, as a debate has raged in recent years about the importance of textbooks in children's education, and the need for their return to classrooms, with evidence to support the claim that top-performing countries have high-quality textbooks that work coherently with the curriculum (DfE, 2017; Leon, 2021; Oates et al, 2021). Nevertheless, it is still the case that textbooks are not widely used as a core teaching/learning resource. This is further illustrated by anonymised snippets of conversation found on social media about the use of textbooks in secondary schools in England, shown in Table 5.

Table 4 Excerpts from Social Media on the Use of Textbooks in Schools in England (2017-2024)

<i>Person A</i>	Hi all. Newbie here. My oldest child has just started secondary school and I'm surprised that he does not have any textbooks for any subject. I've been in touch with the school, and they have confirmed that they do not have them due to budgets ... Is this lack of textbooks the same for all schools? I want to buy some textbooks – any recommendations? He's at a state school ... I may sound really old school, but I think you need a good solid textbook for basics! Thanks
<i>Person B</i>	Yes, most state schools, in my experience, don't give out textbooks. Many subjects don't even use one regularly. Cost is a massive reason, imagine how much it would cost?
<i>Person C</i>	With KS4, you will need to know which exam board they are using as there are slight differences but most schools at this stage will recommend – even sell- students the relevant study/revision guides for the courses they are doing.
<i>Person D</i>	[My] Kids at state school, they have very few textbooks in KS3, mostly they were given worksheets. If they had any books, they were very old and often falling apart. But plenty of books to buy at your own cost for GCSE and A Levels
<i>Person E</i>	[I] Work in a Science dept in a secondary school. We have only the budget for textbooks to hand out in classrooms, not for kids to have them individually. However, all textbooks can be accessed online at home.
<i>Person F</i>	As for textbooks, schools use whatever the individual school or teacher may decide to buy and use. In some schools, for subjects like Maths, in particular, they do not use textbooks at all, but instead teachers will prepare lessons on their electronic whiteboards. At GCSE level, some exam boards may recommend certain textbooks for some subjects – and increasingly publish their own – but there is no compulsion on schools to use these (though most do).

<i>Person G</i>	The examination boards create syllabi and examinations that, to some extent, reflect the expectations of the universities. As far as I know, we do not “teach” particular books, there are no “set” books, unless a particular exam board requires a particular book
<i>Person H</i>	In my experience there are far fewer textbooks used than in the past, partly because of the expense of keeping up with the constant changes to the curriculum and because of the myriad of resources available on the internet.
<i>Person I</i>	The National Curriculum in England is a framework and, as such, has no dedicated textbooks. Teachers/subject leaders/schools decide how the elements of the curriculum will be taught and, at classroom level, that may very well depend on student ability levels. Teachers write most of their own materials in many subjects. That said, educational publishers ... have textbooks with programmes and exercises written in accordance with The National Curriculum
<i>Person J</i>	In secondary school you use textbooks for your exam board, or specific to your [subject] ... Personally, I would recommend [names two books] ... These are both concise and easily available all across the UK. Many schools also offer the same books at a reduced price from their own school shops. Generally, however, we don't use textbooks to do class work, just for personal revision purposes.
<i>Person K</i>	Pupils in primary and secondary schools in Britain typically have access to textbooks for various subjects, although the extent of their use may vary depending on the school and the specific curriculum being followed. In recent years, there has been a shift towards more digital resources and interactive learning materials, but traditional textbooks are still commonly used. The availability and quality of textbooks can vary between schools and regions, and may be influenced by factors such as funding, educational policies, and curriculum choices.
Sources: Compiled by the authors from various social media (2017-2024)	

2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the examination of gender approaches to the teaching of energy in secondary school in the UK through analysis of textbook content:

- Whether content related to energy education (i.e., processes of energy production, storage, use and management) is presented in a gender-sensitive way;
- Whether representation of energy issues creates equal opportunities for students to develop their knowledge and skills in energy-related sectors;
- Whether and how content related to the energy transition encourages women to participate in it.

3 METHODS FOR DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Textbooks

Identifying the textbooks for analysis entailed first reading up on literature on education and state education in England to establish whether any textbooks are mandatory with a view to selecting a sample for analysis. As from the previous discussion (section 2.1.5), it was found that, in England:

- there are no mandatory textbooks for in use secondary schools in KS3 and KS4
- textbooks are not a core teaching/learning resource
- any textbooks that are used are selected by teachers/headteachers in response to publishers' recommendations
- recommended textbooks are geared for examinations set by specific exam boards

The lack of mandatory textbooks left the scope for selecting textbooks rather open, so a preliminary search and brief review of a few textbooks was undertaken to check the content. The textbooks for inclusion in the sample were selected according to the following considerations:

- subject relevance (i.e., those that include the topic of energy as noted in the NC, except as a physical phenomenon, or in the context of nutrition)
- publishers' ranking/popularity (i.e., those more easily found in internet searches; see below)
- date of publication (i.e., those published more recently, or at least published from 2014 onwards which must comply with the new NC)
- costs (i.e., those more affordable, which may likely reflect the wider spending patterns by parents)

3.2 Sample characteristics

The textbooks were selected through a combination of approaches. Mostly this included internet searches on rankings of textbooks/publishers for the relevant subjects (e.g., 'most popular'), enquiries on social media, and recommendations by parents on social media. This combined approach helped narrow down the number of textbooks for each relevant subject, although more textbooks on Geography were reviewed than on other subjects as this is the subject where coverage is most extensive. Cost was also a consideration, since the textbooks had to be purchased, (they were not freely available). All textbooks (bar one) were purchased online, mostly as 'second hand', printed items, although publishers make available their online version following purchase as a first-hand item. Table 6 shows key information about the selected textbooks. The publishers' names were anonymised for consistency (only

one agreed to disclosure and allowed use of the source) and because there were issues about obtaining authorization for reproducing copyrighted content (for instance, publisher 7 clearly states at the bottom of each page of the textbook that 'photocopying this image is a breach of copyright law'). The number of pages analysed indicated the length of text related to energy issues and included in the analyses.

Table 5 England: Secondary Schools Textbooks - Sample Characteristics

Source Number	Publisher	Subject	Pub Date	School Year	Ages	Pages Analysed (N)	Content (unit of analysis)
<i>Key Stage 3 (Lower Secondary)</i>							
1	G	Geography	2024	7-9	11-14	32	text string (sentences; phrases)
2	A	Geography	2019	7-9	11-14	8	text string (sentences; phrases)
3	B	Geography	2015	7-9	11-14	15	Text string (sentences; phrases)
<i>Key Stage 4 (Upper Secondary)</i>							
4	A	Geography	2023	10-11	14-16	7	text string (sentences; phrases)
5	C	Geography	2023	10-11	14-16	64	text string (sentences; phrases)
6	F	Geography	2018	10-11	14-16	37	text string (sentences; phrases)
7	B	Geography	2017	10-11	14-16	10	text string (sentences; phrases)
8	E	Geography	2016	10-11	14-16	56	text string (sentences; phrases)
<i>Key Stage 3 (Lower Secondary)</i>							
9	A	Science	2023	7-9	11-14	17	text string (sentences; phrases)
10	B	Science	2022	7-9	11-14	2	text string (sentences; phrases)
<i>Key Stage 4 (Upper Secondary)</i>							

Guidance Note

11	B	Science	2017	10-11	14-16	23	text string (sentences; phrases)
12	D	Science	2017	10-11	14-16	21	text string (sentences; phrases)
13	C	Science	2016	10-11	14-16	16	text string (sentences; phrases)
<i>Key Stage 3 (Lower Secondary)</i>							
14	A	Design and Technology	2015	7-9	11-14	3	text string (sentences; phrases)
<i>Key Stage 4 (Upper Secondary)</i>							
15	B	Design and Technology	2017	10-11	14-16	4	text string (sentences; phrases)

The textbooks listed on Table 6 for each subject at both stages, by and large, cover broadly similar content to meet the requirements of the NC for each subject, although it may be organised and presented differently. Figure 2 shows a sample of the sections in Geography textbooks that cover issues on energy, although these may also be covered in other sections. Related topics such as climate change are also often covered on its own dedicated section or as part of other sections.

Figure 2 Energy Topics in Geography

<p>2 How do we use our planet as a natural resource?</p> <p>2.1 How do we use our planet as a natural resource? 22</p> <p>2.2 How are rocks and minerals used as a natural resource? 24</p> <p>2.3 How do the world's forests provide natural resources? 26</p> <p>2.4 Why are soils the root of life? 28</p> <p>2.5 Why is food a vital natural resource? 30</p> <p>2.6 Is there enough water for human needs? 32</p> <p>2.7 Why is the world so dependent on oil? 34</p> <p>2.8 What natural resources can be used to generate electricity? 36</p> <p>2.9 How can we use natural resources sustainably? 38</p> <p>2.10 How do we use our planet as a natural resource? Review 40</p>	<p>Contents</p> <p>about this book: Why is seeing the world today as a geographer so important? 4</p> <p>Enquiry 1: Living in Japan Why isn't Yuna able to play the sport she loves? 8</p> <p>Enquiry 2: Holes in the landscape Why should we be concerned about sinkholes? 26</p> <p>Enquiry 3: Is fracking all that it's cracked up to be? Is fracking a sustainable solution to the UK's energy security challenge? 42</p> <p>Enquiry 4: Almost Armageddon! Why did the earth nearly die at the end of the Permian period? 58</p> <p>Enquiry 5: Disasters and risky places Are Haiti and the Philippines risky places to live? 74</p> <p>Enquiry 6: Don't snatch! How is so-called 'land grabbing' affecting Africa? 92</p> <p>Enquiry 7: Olympic spirit Where should the 2022 Winter Olympics be held? 110</p>
<p>Topic 9 — Consuming Energy Resources</p> <p>Energy Resources 149</p> <p>Impacts of Energy Production 150</p> <p>Access to Energy 151</p> <p>Oil Supply and Demand 152</p> <p>Increasing Energy Supply 153</p> <p>Sustainable Energy Use 154</p> <p>Energy Futures 156</p> <p>Worked Exam Questions 158</p> <p>Exam Questions 159</p> <p>Revision Summary 160</p>	<p>Resource management</p> <p>80 The world's natural resources</p> <p>81 Variety and distribution</p> <p>82 Global usage and consumption</p> <p>Energy</p> <p>83 Production and development</p> <p>84 UK and global energy mix</p> <p>85 Impacts of non-renewable energy resources</p> <p>86 Impacts of renewable energy resources</p> <p>87 Meeting energy demands</p> <p>88 China and Germany</p>

3.3 Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook

Selected textbook pages were first scanned into PDFs and then had to be converted into OCR (Optical Character Recognition) to be readable by the MAXQDA software for qualitative data analysis, which could only be accessed as 'free trial' (i.e. not available at Imperial College). Text and images in these PDFs were coded using the codes drawn from the codebook put together by the research team. However, MAXQDA often could not read the OCR text, so the alternative was to use the image coding option (i.e. block coding), which prevents keyword searches that would give a good sense of the extent and breadth of specific thematic content. Hence, MAXQDA was dropped, and manual text coding and analysis carried out instead. At any rate, the study of the textbooks prior to coding had already revealed the virtual absence of any reference to gender in the textbooks in the sample.

4 ENERGY AND GENDER IN UK TEXTBOOKS

The analysis of the textbooks in the sample revealed that gender is generally conspicuous by its absence from the teaching of energy and associated topics in secondary education in England, and more so as regards the use of language than the use of imagery. This may be due, in good measure, to the fact that gender itself is not embedded in the English language, with some notable exceptions, such as, for instance, the case of vehicles and countries, that is, which are 'feminised' (i.e. 'she', 'her').

4.1. Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections

In general, there is no textual reference to gender in the teaching of energy and related topics in the textbooks analysed. One the rare occasions when reference to gender was found it, was in the Science textbooks, which is outside the scope of this analysis, as discussed earlier (see section 2.1.4). Still, it is useful to show how it illustrates the gender approach, as can be seen in the excerpts on Figure 3. The texts tell students to do a calculation on power, using the example of Al (a man's name) and Emma (a woman's name). Interesting, this approach suggests an effort to balance out any references to gender (i.e. one of each of the traditional binary gender division).

Figure 3 Reference to gender in Science textbooks

<p>Al weighs 800 N. He climbs 5 m vertically in 10 s when he runs up the stairs of an office block.</p> <p>a How much work does he do?</p> <p>b Calculate his power.</p>	<p>Emma decides to measure her personal leg power doing step-ups. The step is 10 cm high. Emma does 20 step ups in 30 s. Her mass is 60 kg. Calculate her leg power.</p>
--	--

Source: 11B

More commonly, it was in the use of imagery in science textbooks when discussing energy as a natural phenomenon that reference to gender was made, either directly

Guidance Note

or implied. Table 8 shows two household appliances used to illustrate an exercise on power and energy transfer and efficiency relating to the use of appliances, found on Science textbooks. Their use might again suggest an effort at balancing out references to gender, as it might be inferred that women will more commonly use the hair dryer, whereas men might more frequently use the electric drill (Example A). Such attempt at balancing out does not always happen (Example B). Also, sometimes there may be even an attempt to break with stereotypes (Example C, where a girl is shown manipulating a circuitry kit).

Figure 4 Imagery on gender in Science Textbooks

<p>State the energy transfers and stores when a kettle is used to heat water.</p> <p>Power and energy transferred</p> <p>Consider a hairdryer (Figure 7.2.35). The hairdryer receives 1500 J of energy each second from the mains supply; it transfers 1500 J of energy per second from the mains supply to two main energy stores: thermal energy stored in the air and kinetic energy in the moving air.</p> <p>The power is the amount of energy transferred each second. The units are joules per second, or watts (W). As the hairdryer transfers 1500 J each second, its power is 1500 W or 1.5 kW.</p> <p>Figure 7.2.35 A hairdryer</p> <p>Figure 7.2.36 An electric drill</p> <p>An electric drill (Figure 7.2.36) connected to the a.c. mains transfers 400 J every second.</p> <p>a Describe how the drill transfers energy and the stores it transfers energy to.</p> <p>b State the power of the drill.</p> <p>The amount of energy transferred by an appliance depends on its power and the length of time it is used. We can use this equation to calculate the amount of energy transferred.</p> <p>Electrical energy = power × time (in joules, J) (in watts, W) (in seconds, s)</p> $E = Pt$	<p>Example:</p> <p>Kat uses a hairdryer. Some of the energy is wasted as sound. The electrical energy input is 24 kJ. The energy wasted is 7 kJ. What is the efficiency of the hairdryer?</p> <p>First calculate the useful energy transferred.</p> <p>useful energy = total energy – wasted energy = 24 – 7 = 17 kJ</p> <p>Now calculate the efficiency.</p> $\text{efficiency} = \frac{\text{useful output energy transfer}}{\text{useful input energy transfer}} = \frac{17}{24} = 0.71$ <p>This decimal efficiency can be represented as a percentage by multiplying it by 100.</p> $0.71 \times 100 = 71\%$	<p>equation:</p>
A	B	C
Source: 11B	Source: 12D	Source: 12D

The use of such imagery in Science textbooks is limited and generally guarded, and this is commonly the case in textbooks on Design and Technology too. Yet, the examples depicted in Figure 5 points to exceptions. Example A shows two young men looking at a computer to illustrate the point about the use of data in Life Cycle Assessment which should be objective rather than subjective. Example B shows the side of girls or young women's faces looking at their mobile phone which is used to illustrate a point about ethical awareness about the negative and positive effects of products on society. In addition, whilst the young seem to be depicted as 'doing work', the young women seem to be depicted as 'being at leisure'. These images are drawn from two different sources, yet might potential convey 'subliminal' stereotypical views about the role of men and women as regards the use of scientific methods and technology.

Figure 5 Use of gender imagery on textbooks

Source: 11B (Science)

Source: 15B (Design and Technology)

Gender 'blindness' in the use of language is also pervasive in the textbooks. Often the word 'people' is used as a collective form of address when dealing with different facts of energy and associated themes, rather than differentiating on the basis of gender. The following quotes exemplify the 'undifferentiated' use of the word people:

- A) "Changes in climate change are already having an impact on people; but there could be more serious consequences in the future" (4A).
- B) "Some regions rely on traditional fuel sources. For example, in sub-Saharan Africa, energy networks are poorly connected, which means people have to rely on biomass such as wood for cooking and heating. There is very little development, so countries can't afford to exploit their own energy reserves or improve existing infrastructure" (4A).
- C) "Oil and gas companies bring investments and jobs to an area. For example, one oil company in Alaska has invested 4.5 million dollars into communities and employs over 1700 people" (4A).

In quote A, as can be seen, the text is about the impact of climate change on 'people', but arguably the text could incorporate a gender-differentiated approach, highlighting instances where the effects are felt more keenly by women than men (e.g. women and girls may have to travel farther to collect water and firewood, increasing threats to their safety, reducing productivity in other activities, such as farming, and reducing time available for schooling). Similarly, in quote B, the claim is about the greater dependence of 'people' on biomass for cooking and heating, rather than noting the key role of girls and women in providing such sources of energy. Quite clearly such 'blindness' could be challenged on the grounds that it has been well-documented that it is mostly girls and women who are tasked with providing and using such biomass. In example C, the passage notes that one of the economic benefits of increasing the supply of conventional energy (fossil fuel) is increased employment of people. Again, here, it would be appropriate to acknowledge that

historically the bulk of such jobs around the world have gone to men. Thus, there is clear scope for 'engendering' these kinds of statements to take account of energy-related gender experiences.

4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames

As already highlighted, gender is conspicuous by its absence in the textbooks in the three most relevant disciplines where energy is taught in England. Hence, in consequence, there is no gender consideration in any of the different energy frames proposed for analysis (e.g. energy in relation to economy, labour market, climate change, security, poverty, technology; governance). However, some of these frames do appear in some textbooks, usually in description of phenomena or processes, in statements about them, in the setting out of tasks, in tips for exams, or in prescriptions (e.g. what should be done to address problems). Some of these frames are discussed below, others are discussed in later sections.

4.3 Energy

The topic of energy itself is generally treated in Geography textbooks as an issue of resource management, entailing description and statements on the different types of energy, demand, supply, security, usage, strategies to increase supply, often with reference to regions and countries around the world. Some of the textbooks also discuss energy sustainability. For instance, in one textbook (7B), in the section titled 'The Challenge of Resource Management', under the subheading 'Energy 3', students are told that (after studying the section) they must be able to:

- Explain why sustainable energy supplies are important for the future survival of the planet
- Describe how energy usage by individuals and organisations can be designed to be sustainable
- Show how technology can be used to reduce energy usage

In another Geography textbook (4A), there is also discussion about the different attitudes that different groups in society have about two energy future scenarios: 'business as usual' and 'move to sustainability'. Below is a sample of statements about these different groups (our emphasis):

- Many **consumers** currently favour business as usual, as it provides a cheap, secure supply of energy. However, as supplies of fossil fuels run out, and environmental awareness increases, some consumers are beginning to favour a move to sustainability.
- Controlling oil reserves gives **Transnational Corporations** [TNCs] lots of power and wealth, which means they may lose money if there is a shift towards using more renewable energy sources. Sustainable energy needs more investment

than fossil fuels, so these TNCs would have higher costs and potentially lower gains – this means they may favour the business as usual scenario.

- **Governments** want to secure future energy supplies – fossil fuels are a cheap and reliable way of supplying energy in the short-term, but a more sustainable approach will need to be long-term.
- **Climate scientists** ... want to reduce reliance on fossil fuels in order to lessen the consequences of climate change, e.g. serious temperature increases and rising sea levels.
- **Environmental groups**, e.g. Greenpeace, want to stop people relying on fossil fuels for energy because their extraction and use damages the environment. They want people to reduce their use of fossil fuels and switch to renewable energy sources in line with the move to sustainability scenario.

In a third textbook (8E), a section on Meeting Energy Demands notes, for instance, the need for using and managing energy sources sustainably, and that this involves different groups with different views. It then notes the differing attitudes on fracking in the UK (our emphasis):

- **individuals** protest against the exploitation of shale gas due to its environmental impacts;
- **organisations** see fracking as a financial benefit, generating money for industry and services and supported by the UK government
- **pressure groups** such as Greenpeace are opposed to fossil fuels, fracking and nuclear energy, and want all energy produced by sunlight, wind, waves, tides and geothermal heat

In the Science textbooks, the focus is generally on description of different types of sources of energy (renewable and non-renewable) according to their physical and chemical properties their processing, transfer, dissipation/use or distribution (e.g. electricity from power stations to the national grid), and conservation. Often too there is discussion about advantages and disadvantages of different types of energy sources (e.g. availability, reliability) and a brief discussion about energy issues from a wider, societal perspective (see section 5.4 below).

In Design and Technology textbooks, energy is generally discussed as a resource used for the manufacturing of goods, which, depending on the source, can have negative environmental impacts. One passage in one of the textbooks (14A) notes that 'The more processes a material goes through, the more fossil fuels will be burnt in its manufacture. That means more polluting gases (e.g. carbon monoxide) are released into the environment. For example, an electroplated metal table needs more energy to make than a hand-built wooden one'. Similarly, a second Design and Technology Textbook (15B) discusses sources of energy in the section 'Design Considerations', noting that after studying the section, students must be able to:

Guidance Note

- describe how energy is generated, transferred and stored
- explain the appropriate use of renewable and non-renewable sources to power products and systems

4.4 Climate Change

On climate change, Geography textbooks focus on its description as a physical phenomenon, its causes (natural; anthropogenic, including fossil fuels), the evidence for it (long-term; short-term), management of its impacts (adaptation and mitigation), and difficulties with predicting climate change. As with Geography, in Science textbooks, the discussion on climate change is linked to the physical and chemical properties of the atmosphere, weather patterns, the links to global warming, and the effects of natural and anthropogenic changes. There is also discussion about the evidence for natural and anthropogenic causes of climate change and statements about the need for change in human behaviour, as in this passage in one Science textbook (13C):

'At the moment, most people and governments are convinced that lifestyles need to change, reliance on fossil fuels needs to be reduced, and rainforests need to be preserved in order to reduce the damage that climate change might cause'

In Design and Technology textbooks, climate change is treated implicitly, in content about the environmental damage from different manufacturing processes, materials and disposal with recommendations on how to 'help the environment' as in the following passage (14A):

- Designers can create products that need less energy to make and use
- Products can be made with recycled, or recyclable, materials
- Consumers can buy environmentally-friendly products and remember to recycle

4.5 Energy security and poverty

Energy security, insecurity are only addressed in Geography textbooks. Mostly, they are discussed as a macro-level issue (countries or above), or also at an abstract or general level. The emphasis is broadly on factors affecting energy supply (technology, physical, political, economic) but consequences are sometimes noted, as shown in Table 7 for one textbook in Geography.

Table 6 Impacts of Energy Insecurity

Impacts of Energy Insecurity	
Destroying natural habitats	As fossil fuels become scarcer, countries will be forced to extract resources from environmentally sensitive areas such as the Amazon Rainforest. Searching for fossil fuels also destroys environmentally sensitive areas.
Economic costs	Countries, especially those that rely on imports, may not have enough energy supply to meet demand. This affects individuals, businesses and industrial production and can damage the economy.
Environmental costs	An increase in biofuel use may result in woodland being cleared to grow the crops and trees needed to produce biofuels. Renewable energy sources, such as wind farms and hydroelectric reservoirs can spoil landscapes and ecosystems.
Food production	Because food production requires vast amounts of energy, energy insecurity could lead to food shortages and famine. Growing crops for biofuels also reduced the land available for growing food.
Potential for conflict	Energy insecurity can cause conflict in areas where energy is not evenly distributed. Conflict may also arise between countries competing for resources For example, Russia and Ukraine have an ongoing dispute over gas.
Source: 6F	

The concept of energy poverty only appears in one Geography textbook, at end of a three-page section on Energy management: global energy supply , in a section titled 'Retrieval'. The section is split into columns (left hand side) and answers (right hand side). Students are instructed to 'Learn the answers to the questions below, then cover the answers column with a piece of paper and write down as many as you can. Check and repeat'. A sample of relevant questions and answers here are shown in the Table 8.

Table 7 Energy security, insecurity, and poverty

Questions	Answers
What is meant by 'energy security'?	Uninterrupted availability of energy sources at an affordable price
What is meant by 'energy insecurity'?	Not having access to sufficient, reliable, and affordable energy supplies
What is energy (or fuel) poverty?	A household spending more than 10% of its income on fuel to maintain an adequate level of warmth
Source: 5C	

4.6 Gender and energy technology

There are no instances in any of the textbooks analysed of gender references in the context of energy technology for production and distribution. The frame of energy technology also appears in the textbooks, usually in Geography textbooks, and to a limited extent in the Science and in the Design and Technology textbooks too. Generally there is reference to the technologies used for producing the different types of renewable and non-renewable energy, and for distribution (grid). These are also covered in sections on resource management or energy management sections, and as elements in strategies for increasing energy production (e.g. the two scenarios: 'business and usual' or use of sustainable renewable alternatives).

4.7 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)

There is no mention at all in any of the textbooks analysed of gender in relation to the various energy sources. Generally, the content is a straight description of their origin, uses, environmental and health impacts, links to climate change, the pros and cons and costs and benefits of their production and use, and observations about increased consumption in line with population growth, economic development and technology (often noting the uneven distribution of these resources between the Global North and South).

One example is the section 'Design Considerations' in one Design and Technology source that provides such kind of description, highlighting that the student 'must be able to describe how energy is generated, transferred, and stored' and 'explain the appropriate use of renewable and non-renewable energy sources to power products and systems', making a key point that 'renewable energy sources can replenish themselves quickly and so will not run out' (15B). The section describes fossil fuels, naming coal, oil and natural gas as examples, and nuclear fuel, noting that 'making greater use of nuclear energy means there is less need for fossil fuels.' It also describes renewable energy sources, noting that they are 'sustainable and will not run out', citing wind, hydro, tidal and solar power as examples, and noting that 'agricultural crops can also be used to create biofuels' (15B).

Similar technical descriptions occur in Science and Geography textbooks, although energy in these is often also treated from a broader societal perspective. An example is the following passage in a Science textbook (11B), which also relates to governance (see section 5.8 below):

'Scientists do not always have the power to make the decisions about energy use – these decisions are made by governments. Governments have to weigh up ethical, social and economic considerations as well as the likely impact on the environment'.

4.8 Gender and energy labour market

No mention or reference to gender in the context of energy labour market is made in any of the textbooks analysed. There is no consideration at all in any of the sources of any issues that could be linked up to the topic of labour market (e.g. of jobs or careers in the energy sector) and inform a discussion about professionals working in energy. There is mention in some of the textbooks, for instance, of the word 'scientist' or 'scientists', often in the context of production and examination of evidence for climate change. But again, in English, these are 'gender-neutral' terms (see quotation above in section 5.4).

4.9 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)

No references to gender in relation to energy practices are made in any of the textbooks, although the scope for doing so was noted in section 5.1 (i.e. the absence of gender differentiation in the context of biomass collection and use in Sub-Saharan Africa). But some of the sources do address issues around energy consumption, in various settings and different purposes, including reducing the use of fossil fuels, improving energy security, and diversifying the energy mix. The following passages illustrate claims about the need to conserve energy or improve efficiency:

'Energy conservation is important in protecting precious supplies of energy...Using energy efficient devices, like kettles that only boil one cup of water, or turning off appliances when not in use (rather than using standby buttons) can also help conserve energy in the home' (10B)

'The use of LED light bulbs, washing machines that wash clothes at 30 degrees C or lower and thermostats on central heating systems that can be controlled using a mobile phone, are all ways in which homes and workplaces can be made more energy efficient' (10B)

'The demand for energy can be reduced by conserving and making energy use more efficient:

- conserving energy is about changing our behaviour as consumers; e.g. driving less, drying clothes on a washing line instead of in a dryer*
- if something is energy-efficient, it does the same job but using less energy; e.g. low-energy light bulb' (4A)*

4.01 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy

There were no examples in any of the textbooks analysed of gender references in the context of energy citizenship and energy democracy and 'prosumerism'. These themes are not themselves directly addressed in them, although there is reference to environmental activists, such as Greenpeace, and their campaigns to ditch the use of fossil fuels (see the discussion on section 5.2.1) .

4.02 Gender and energy governance

There were no instances in any of the textbooks analysed of gender being addressed in the context of energy governance and in sociotechnical change. But in relation to energy issues, there is sometimes reference to aspects of governance. The following passage in a Science textbook (11B) illustrates this:

'Ethical considerations are to do with whether something is morally right or wrong. An example is making sure that energy resources are plentiful for the future. Although it would not affect us, it would be wrong to cause problems for future generations.

Social considerations concern how they affect people. Fossil fuel power stations need to be built to power factories and so provide people with jobs.

Economic considerations involve money. Although a particular energy resource might not be as harmful to the environment it might be too expensive to produce' .

5 TEMPORALITIES

Although there were references to historical development of production, distribution and use of energy sources in the UK (i.e. coal mining), gender was never addressed in them. There was no reference to gender either in any discussion of energy production, distribution and use in the future. But on occasion there was reference to past and current energy production history and strategies, as illustrated by the following quotes:

'In the UK, and many other countries, the energy mix has changed significantly over time. As sources of energy are discovered, exploited and exhausted, the way a country generates its electricity will also need to change. For example, the UK had plentiful supplies of accessible coals, so this was used in the earliest power stations. The invention of nuclear power stations, combined with the availability of cheaper coal from countries such as Poland and government disputes with miners, saw the beginning of mines being closed in the 1970s. This led to a decline in the use of coal, which accelerated the discovery of reserves of oil and natural gas in the North Sea and resulted in the closure of most of the UK's coal mines in the 1980s'. (3B)

'In the 1960s, British companies searched for oil and gas in rocks underneath the North Sea, leading to Britain becoming self-sufficient in oil and gas for a while'. (10B)

'Clean coal technology has enabled coal-fired power stations to produce less pollution and CO₂ by removing the pollutants when the coal is burned. However, in the UK they will all close by 2025' (10B)

'Many power stations in the UK have been converted to burn biomass as well as coal'. (10B)

'Wind power is the most widely used renewable in the UK, with nearly 7000 onshore and offshore wind turbines producing almost 10% of the UK's electricity' (10B)

6 LANGUAGE

As discussed in section 5.1, gender 'blindness' in the use of language was found to be pervasive in the textbooks analysed. Often the word 'people' is used as a collective form of address when addressing energy and the variety of associated themes, rather than differentiating on the basis of gender where there might be scope for it, as shown above.

Every so often, use was made of 'we', 'our', 'us' (collective pronouns) in a way that suggests inclusivity to elicit a sense of responsibility and urgency regarding the use of energy and the need to change patterns and practices of production and consumption, including recycling, and personal 'carbon footprint', as in the two passages below:

'There are an awful lot of people on our planet, and they all need food, water and energy. No one's quite sure how the human population will change in the future, and how that'll affect the availability of the things we need. If we're going to keep up with the world's energy needs, we'll need to start thinking about increasing our supplies' (4A)

'From powering our laptops, and smartphones, to heating our houses and boiling our water, we are all using an increasing amount of energy each year. Global population increase and rising levels of economic development mean that this pattern is repeated across the world' (3B)

7 MISSING THEMES

Quite obviously, the theme that is missing in the textbooks analysed is gender itself. Yet, it should be included in the teaching of energy in secondary education in the UK and elsewhere, giving appropriate emphasis on important differences regarding, for instance, gender norms, roles and behaviour regarding access to, use, management and governance of energy production, distribution, use, management and governance, taking account of the different spaces where these apply (e.g. domestic and household spheres; public spaces; etc). This would help draw attention to issues of justice, equality, and sustainability in energy, energy systems and energy transitions, issues that are themselves largely absent from the textbooks, but should be integrated into the teaching of energy. It would also help encourage girls and young women to develop a deeper interest in the great variety of themes and topics linked to energy systems and energy transitions with a view to encouraging them to pursue careers in the field of energy and technological innovation in energy.

8 OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES

The very structure of most textbooks examined (i.e. short sections rather than whole chapters) along with use of short paragraphs or bullet points seems suggests that

teaching/learning in England on energy themes and topics is focused on preparing students for examination, which limits the scope for more meaningful analysis of content and language use (e.g. rather 'fractured'). Moreover, given the limited use of textbooks in the classroom in secondary education and the virtual absence of gender considerations in the teaching of energy in textbooks, it is difficult to gauge the extent to which gender is really present or absent in secondary education teaching. The use of other methodologies might help provide a clearer picture, such as for instance, interviewing students and teachers, classroom observation, and analysing teaching materials produced by the teachers themselves to use in the classroom.

9 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM

Integrating a gender perspective into compulsory education on energy in England would, require making mandatory the integration of a gender perspective into all the subjects in the National Curriculum that have a component on energy which, as seen here, are mostly Geography, Science and also Design and Technology.

Conversely, energy could be created as a subject on its own right in the National Curriculum for secondary education and one that also integrates a gender dimension. Its content could be structured around both the physical and societal dimensions of energy systems (e.g. properties, production, distribution, consumption, management, governance), and associated themes as contained in the 'frames' discussed above (e.g. global warming, climate change, sustainability, etc).

Gender integration into the theme of energy in secondary school textbooks could also be achieved by highlighting the contributions by both men and women to the development of all subjects that cover the theme of energy, to encourage in particular, girls and young women to develop greater interest STEM fields and pursue them in higher education.

Finally, secondary education textbooks could make much greater use of case-studies (drawing on the vast body of scholarly sources) on energy in all its dimensions in different contexts (e.g. how energy access affect women in the Global South; the role of women in the renewable energy sector, etc).

REFERENCES

DfE (2013a) Science programmes of study: key stage 3 - National curriculum in England, National curriculum in England, Department for Education. Available at:
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7d563de5274a2af0ae2ffa/SE_CONDARY_national_curriculum_-_Science_220714.pdf. (Accessed 28/04/2024).

DfE (2013b) Design and Technology programmes of study: key stage 3 - National curriculum in England, Department for Education. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7c99ebed915d6969f46087/SE_CONDARY_national_curriculum_-_Design_and_technology.pdf. (Accessed 03/05/2024).

DfE (2014a) The national curriculum in England Key stages 3 and 4 framework document, National curriculum in England, Department for Education. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/national-curriculum> (Accessed 07/05/2024).

DfE (2014b) Science programmes of study: key stage 4 - National curriculum in England, Department for Education. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7efc65ed915d74e33f3ac9/Science_KS4_PoS_7_November_2014.pdf. (Accessed 07/05/2024).

DfE (2014c) Geography programmes of study: key stage 3 - National curriculum in England

Department for Education. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-curriculum-in-england-Geography-programmes-of-study/national-curriculum-in-england-Geography-programmes-of-study#key-stage-3>. (Accessed 09/05/2024).

DfE (2014d) Geography: GCSE subject content - National curriculum in England

Department for Education. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a7d5754e5274a33be64898e/GCSE_Geography.pdf. (Accessed 09/05/2024).

DfE (2015a) Combined science GCSE subject content - National curriculum in England

Department for Education. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5cd2b8b4ed915d50b6c44ffa/Combined_science_GCSE_updated_May_2019.pdf. (Accessed 10/05/2024).

DfE (2105b) Design and Technology GCSE subject content - National curriculum in England

Department for Education. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a815e06e5274a2e87dbd3ec/GCSE_design_technology_subject_content_nov_2015.pdf. (Accessed 10/05/2024).

DfE (2018) Charging for school activities- Departmental advice for governing bodies, school leaders, school staff and local authorities. Available at:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5af99c8ae5274a25e78bbe30/Charging_for_school_activities.pdf. (Accessed 25/04/2024).

Guidance Note

- DfE (2017) *Speech: Importance of Core Knowledge Sees Return of Textbooks*, Department for Education, UK. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/speeches/nick-gibb-importance-of-core-knowledge-sees-return-of-textbooks> (Accessed 05/05/2024).
- DfE (2018) *Charging for school activities: Departmental advice for governing bodies, school leaders, school staff and local authorities*. Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5af99c8ae5274a25e78bbe30/Ccharging_for_school_activities.pdf (Accessed 06/05/2024).
- Kulakiewicz, A, Long, R, and Roberts, N (2021) *Inclusion of Sustainability and Climate Change in the National Curriculum*, Debate Pack, House of Commons Library, London. Available at <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CDP-2021-0166/CDP-2021-0166.pdf> (Accessed 05/05/2024).
- Leon, B (2021) *Why are English schools not using textbooks?* Education Blog. Available at: <https://educationblog.buckingham.ac.uk/2021/05/16/why-are-english-schools-not-using-textbooks-by-professor-barnaby-lenon/#:~:text=In%20England%2010%25%20of%2010,Korea%2C%2092%25%20in%20Taiwan.> (Accessed 15/05/2024).
- Ofqual (2020) *GCSE, AS and A levels A guide for students in England*, Office of Qualifications and Examinations Regulation. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/gcses-as-and-a-levels-a-guide-for-students-in-england/asdf>, (Accessed 06/05/2024).
- Roberts, N (2021) *The School Curriculum in England*, Briefing Paper No 06798, House of Commons Library, London. Available at: <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/SN06798/SN06798.pdf> (Accessed 06/05/2024).
- Sibieta, L, and Jerrim, J (2021) *A Comparison of School Institutes and Policies Across the UK*, Education Policy Institute/Nuffield Foundation/UCL, London. Available at: <https://epi.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/EPI-UK-Institutions-Comparisons-2021.pdf>; (Accessed 13/05/2024).
- Oates, T (2014) *Why Textbooks Count*, Policy Paper, University of Cambridge Local Examinations Syndicate. Available at: <https://www.cambridgeassessment.org.uk/Images/181744-why-textbooks-count-tim-oates.pdf> (Accessed 13/05/2024).
- Oates, T, Mouthaan, M, Fitzsimons, S, and Beedle, F (2021) *Changing Texts: An international review of research on textbooks and related materials including a specific focus on Sweden*, Research Report, Cambridge University Press and Assessment. Available at:

<https://www.cambridgeassessment.org.uk/Images/649893-changing-texts-an-international-review-of-research-on-textbooks-and-related-materials.pdf>.
(Accessed 18/05/2024).

APPENDIX 2. GERMAN NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

Marie Bakalovic, Clemens Striebing, Fraunhofer IAO, Germany

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Aims:

This study aims to explore how energy is taught in school textbooks, with a particular focus on examining any potential energy-gender nexus. Specifically, it seeks to determine if gender-sensitive language is used in the context of teaching energy concepts.

Methodology:

- i. Selection of Federal States:
 - i. Two "Bundesländer" (federal states) were chosen for comparison.
- ii. Curriculum Research:
 - i. The curriculum of the selected federal states was analyzed to identify the subjects in which energy is taught.
- iii. Preliminary Textbook Scan:
 - i. A preliminary scan of textbooks from the three largest publishing houses was conducted, focusing on the 5th/6th and 9th/10th grades.
- iv. Textbook Selection:
 - i. Textbooks that include content on energy were selected for further analysis.
- v. Textbook Analysis:
 - i. The selected textbooks were thoroughly analyzed to assess the presence of an energy-gender nexus and the use of gender-sensitive language.

Main Conclusions:

The analysis revealed that there is not a significant energy-gender nexus in the textbooks. Gender is rarely mentioned, and the texts are generally written in a factual manner without referencing gender. Topics such as energy resources and climate change are frequently discussed. However, the textbooks often do not explain why energy and related topics are relevant to humans beyond the context of climate change and its adverse effects. It should be noted that this lack of contextualization is not consistent across all textbooks.

1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

1.1 Educational system in a country-brief characteristic

Responsibility for Educational Programs

The German educational system is decentralized, with coordination primarily occurring at the level of the federal states ("Länder"). This decentralization results in some variation between states, as each state has its own curricula and regulations, and some states experiment with educational reforms.

The Ministry of Education and Cultural Affairs establishes national educational standards and guidelines, providing a framework that outlines general goals, competencies, and minimum standards for education (Edelstein, 2023; Bildung Im Schulalter – BMBF, n.d.). The federal states then formulate their own curricula with the recommendations of the Ministry, meaning that for example, Bavaria and Berlin have differing curricula (LehrplanPLUS - Gymnasium - 5 - Geographie - Fachprofile, n.d.; (Landesinstitut für Schule und Medien Berlin-Brandenburg & Senatsverwaltung für Bildung, Jugend und Familie, 2018). An example for this would be, that in Bavaria agriculture is taught with a regional framework.

To achieve a more coherent education policy, the states' education ministers exchange information and coordinate efforts through the Conference of Education Ministers ("Kultusministerkonferenz"). The curricula are periodically revised to incorporate new educational research, adapt to changing societal needs, and align with technological and pedagogical developments.

Structure of the School System

The German educational system is structured into three tiers: primary, secondary (I, II), and tertiary education. After completing primary school (up to the 6th grade in Berlin and Brandenburg, and up to the 4th grade in other federal states), students choose among different types of secondary schools based on their academic performance and career goals.

The secondary schools include:

Mittelschule: Emphasizes practical skills and prepares students for vocational training.

Realschule: Offers a broader education with a focus on technical and administrative subjects.

Gymnasium: Prepares students for the Abitur and higher education.

Primary and secondary education is mandatory up to the 9th or 10th grade, depending on the federal state.

1.2 Energy education

Public Opinion on Energy and Renewable Energy

Summarizing public opinion on energy and renewable energy is complex. There is a significant movement among the youth prioritizing renewable energy and climate change in political discussions, called Fridays for Future, originating from Sweden. Public opinion is polarized, with right-wing groups generally favoring fossil fuels and left-wing groups advocating for increased use of renewable energy. In the 2024 European elections, for example, the AFD was of the opinion that man-made climate change did not exist, whereas the Linke party believed that the EU's current climate targets were not enough (Edmundts, 2024). These parties are one of the most right wing and left wing parties respectively.

Coverage of Energy in Educational Materials

Educational materials address energy issues across various subjects, including geography and the sciences. The primary focus is on energy sources such as fossil fuels (oil, gas, coal) and renewables (especially solar, wind, and water). Hydrogen and nuclear energy receive less attention, though some books do mention geothermal energy.

Climate Change in Textbooks

Many textbooks discuss climate change, particularly the greenhouse effect, distinguishing between natural and human-induced impacts. While the subcode "gas emission" is not frequently found, the books highlight climate change-related risks such as droughts, floods, and heavy rainfall. A few textbooks mention potential positive effects of climate change, such as the possibility of growing potatoes in Greenland.

"Spring is currently starting 14 days earlier in the year. This means that the growing season is changing and it is now possible to grow agricultural products that previously had to be imported at great expense. Some farmers are already starting to grow potatoes, which was previously unthinkable." (*TERRA Geographie 9/10. Ausgabe für Berlin und Brandenburg. Schülerbuch Klasse 9/10, 2018*)

"Rising temperatures and the melting of the polar ice caps are creating opportunities, for example: opportunities for agriculture in northern regions and countries such as Greenland and Iceland due to rising average temperatures and longer growing seasons." (*Seydlitz Geographie 10. Schülerband. Für Gymnasien in Bayern, 2022*)

Side note: The Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz, nukleare Sicherheit und Verbraucherschutz conducted a study on climate change education in German schools and universities (*Stand der Klimabildung und Maßnahmen Zur Stärkung in der Bildungspraxis | Umwelt Im Unterricht: Materialien und Service für Lehrkräfte – BMUV-Bildungsservice | Umwelt Im Unterricht, o. D.*). Germany committed to promoting Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) by signing the United Nations Sustainability Agenda in 2015. The study found that the focus on climate education varies across federal states, with an emphasis on scientific foundations, human causes, and technical measures. However, topics like natural causes, climate policy measures, and individual actions are less covered. There's a notable lack of content

on the socio-economic impacts of climate change. Geography is the primary subject addressing climate education, but teacher training and timely resources are insufficient. Universities also lack comprehensive coverage of climate change topics, particularly socio-economic impacts and individual actions. To address these gaps, a 20-point plan was formulated, focusing on handouts and guidelines, education plans, networking, and further training and development. (*Stand der Klimabildung und Maßnahmen Zur Stärkung in der Bildungspraxis | Umwelt Im Unterricht: Materialien und Service für Lehrkräfte – BMUV-Bildungsservice | Umwelt Im Unterricht, o. D.*).

Energy Governance and Transition

Energy governance is frequently discussed, especially regarding CO₂ emissions and laws aimed at reducing them through taxes.

“Carbon dioxide emissions are the highest in the world in relation to the number of inhabitants. By joining the Kyoto Protocol in 2007, Australia committed itself to reducing greenhouse gases and set itself the ambitious goal of becoming a solar power world power.” (Flath, 2017)

“The idea is captivating: politicians determine the amount of greenhouse gases (GHG) that may be emitted. The economy must regulate how this is implemented. Certificates are issued and traded, with a reduction of 1.74 percent every year. This is intended to make emission rights a scarce commodity. The market determines the price and companies are given an incentive to modernize and develop energy-efficient processes.” (*Diercke Geografie 9 / 10. Schülerband. Gymnasien. Berlin und Brandenburg, 2017*)

“The amendment to the EEG adopted in July 2022 stipulates that at least 80% of electricity must come from renewable energies by 2030. The law guarantees that two percent of the land area in Germany will be earmarked for the construction of wind turbines. Photovoltaics are also to be expanded. By 2030, the installed photovoltaic capacity is to reach 215 gigawatts (cf. 2022: 63 GW) and the share of the electricity mix is to increase to 30 From 2026, the expansion rates are to be increased to 22 gigawatts (GW) per year.” (*Seydlitz Geografie 9 / 10 . Schülerband. Für Berlin und Brandenburg, 2023*)

The concept of energy transition is mentioned, though more implicitly, with some books addressing tipping points and the challenges and difficulties that stand in the way of energy transition.

“However, due to the tense situation on the electricity market and fears of a supply freeze for Russian gas, it was decided to allow the operation of three nuclear power plants until spring 2023.” (*Seydlitz Geografie 9 / 10 . Schülerband. Für Berlin und Brandenburg, 2023*)

Energy-Related Competences

Students are primarily taught about energy sources, with some coverage of energy infrastructure and significant emphasis on sustainability and recycling.

The technology of energy sources is explained quite rudimentary and with a bigger focus on renewable energy.

Guidance Note

“When wind hits the rotor blades, the rotor turns on its axis. The movement of the wind is converted into a rotary motion. The rotating axis transmits the movement to a generator. As with a bicycle dynamo, this generates electrical energy. As wind is always blowing, it is a renewable energy source.” (*Erlebnis Naturwissenschaften 5/6. Schülerband. Für Berlin und Brandenburg, 2021*)

“With photovoltaics, solar energy is converted directly into electrical energy, for example for a solar-powered cell phone charging station. This requires solar cells. Large systems, such as those installed along highways, are effective for feeding electricity into the grid. Solar collectors, for example on house roofs, use the sun's heat and heat water for heating or hot water supply. In years with little sunshine, the proportion of electricity generated from photovoltaic systems decreases sharply”. (*TERRA Geographie 9/10. Ausgabe für Berlin und Brandenburg. Schülerbuch Klasse 9/10, 2018*)

“The energy contained in moving water can be converted using various power plants. There are run-of-river power plants, pumped storage power plants and tidal power plants. Regardless of the type of power plant, the energy is always converted by a generator, just like a wind turbine. The only difference is where the flowing water comes from. In run-of-river power plants, turbines are driven by a river. The river has a similar function to the wind in a wind turbine.” (*Natura/Schülerbuch 5. Schuljahr, 2017*)

“Through refining, crude oil in industrialized countries is processed into light and heavy fuel oil, as well as kerosene and gasoline.” (*TERRA Geographie 9/10. Ausgabe für Berlin und Brandenburg. Schülerbuch Klasse 9/10, 2018*)

“Fracking is a way of extracting additional natural gas and oil reserves. For example, it does not involve drilling for ordinary gas fields, but for layers of rock that contain countless small gas bubbles. In order to access these bubbles, the rock under the ground has to be broken up. To do this, a lot of water with toxic chemicals is pressed into the rock. The gas escapes towards the earth's surface and is collected there.” (*Seydlitz Geographie 6. Schülerband. Realschule. Bayern, 2018*)

“In thermal power stations, thermal energy is generated by the combustion of coal or gas or by radioactivity. This vaporizes water. The steam is produced under high pressure and flows through a turbine. It is then set in motion. Here too, a generator converts kinetic energy into electrical energy.” (*Natura/Schülerbuch 5. Schuljahr, 2017*)

Some textbooks explain workgroups, enabling students to participate in sustainability projects.

2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1) Gender Sensitivity in Energy Education

The schoolbooks do not present energy education in a gender-sensitive way. Gender representation is mostly evident in pictures and photographs, where males predominantly

appear as scientists, field workers, or students using energy. Some photographs depict climate change and renewable energy demonstrations, showing both men and women. The texts are not written in a gendered way, raising the question of whether they are gender-neutral or gender-blind. Given that German is a highly gendered language, with job titles explicitly indicating gender through the suffix "-in" for females, the lack of specific job references in the textbooks results in an impersonal portrayal of energy issues. In general, energy is depicted primarily as a technical system, with minimal reflection on its social aspects and contexts.

2) Representation and Opportunities in Energy Sectors

The non-gendered writing style could be interpreted as gender-sensitive and, thus, promoting interest of all students with regards to energy-related issues. However, it is important to recognize that girls and women remain underrepresented in STEM fields. Therefore, one could argue that the texts should actively promote interest among women in energy sources, transition, and climate change to address this disparity.

3) Encouragement for Women in the Energy Sector

There is no specific encouragement for women to work in the energy sector within the textbooks, nor is there any for men. While men are more frequently depicted in images, the text itself makes no gender distinctions. Given the underrepresentation of women in STEM subjects and the historical discouragement they have faced, both implicitly and explicitly, there is a case for the textbooks to provide additional encouragement for women to pursue careers in energy and related fields.

3 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Corpus of Text

A preliminary scan of all the schoolbooks for the chosen subjects, grades, and federal states was conducted through the websites of the three major publishing houses (Cornelsen, Westermann, and Klett). For the schoolbooks that appeared to mention the energy sector, visits were made to the infopoints in Berlin for a more precise examination. After identifying the relevant books that addressed energy, climate change, and related topics, these books were either scanned at the infopoints or gifted for further analysis at home.

3.2 Sample Characteristics

The books were selected based on the extent to which they mentioned the energy sector. The primary criterion for inclusion was whether the subject was covered across at least two pages. Subjects were chosen according to the curriculum. The 5th and 6th grades were included to analyze how younger students are introduced to energy concepts, as the science subjects at this level are foundational (referred to as

"Naturwissenschaften" or "sciences"). The 9th and 10th grades were chosen to examine the content for older students, but before they begin to specialize in courses from the 11th grade onwards.

Content related to the energy sector and/or gender was coded, with a primary focus on chapters about energy sources, as these sections specifically address the energy sector. Visual elements such as pictures, caricatures, and photographs were also coded.

In total, 16 books were analyzed. A total of 843 top-level codes were applied, with "Energy Sources" being the most frequent. In total, 295 pages were scanned, including the front page of each book. Not every page contained coded units, but overall, 2,098 codes were applied.

3.3 Qualitative Data Analysis Driven by the Codebook

Familiarity with the codes and schoolbooks was established prior to analysis. A methodical approach was employed, with each book coded individually. To ensure accuracy, only segments that explicitly matched the established codes were coded, avoiding assumptions or misinterpretations. This careful process ensured that every coded segment was directly relevant to the corresponding code.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections

No rich material illustrating an energy-gender nexus was found in German schoolbooks. The text is almost completely gender-neutral. Only two passages used gendered language: one involving a male worker discussing his job, and another where an expert talked about opportunities in renewable energy. The field worker only uses masculine words (e.g. he describes how men are screwing on the drill pipe, using the word "Ärzte" which is either the generic masculine or only means about men). It is not clear, if only men are working at the drilling rig he works on. The expert for renewable energy did not necessarily speak in a gender sensitive way. He used the term "young people" once but does speak to the students in any other way. Occasionally, terms like "humans" are used, which can be seen as gender-neutral but do not differentiate by age or gender. These terms were used by experts discussing topics such as soft tourism and job opportunities in renewable energy.

In pictures, men are depicted more frequently than women, especially in expert or worker roles. Six instances show men in relation to energy use (e.g., using tablets) or as workers/experts. There is one photograph of a woman as a climate activist, but no images of women working in the energy sector. In the text, four men working in the energy sector are mentioned, whereas there are references to two female climate scientists and one male climate activist. The code for individual actors was used 33

times for men, 10 times for women, and 3 times for persons whose gender was not recognizable. The code for groups was used 9 times for men, 5 times for women, and 24 times for mixed groups, with one instance where the gender was not recognized.

In conclusion, since the energy sector and renewable energy are not frequently discussed in terms of their relation to people, they are not presented as having a gender nexus.

4.2 Energy – gender nexus through frames

The texts did not present gender significantly differently across various contexts such as the economy, labor market, climate change, security, poverty, technology, and governance. Most books focused exclusively on the energy system or climate change. In one instance, an expert mentioned the labor market for renewable energy without differentiating between male or female roles by using the term “young people” which is inclusive.

“In order to find a secure job later on, young people can be encouraged to take an interest in the wide range of employment opportunities in this sector.” (Diercke Geografie 9 / 10. Schülerband. Gymnasien. Berlin und Brandenburg, 2017)

In visual content, men were predominantly shown using technology, with several images depicting individual men using devices like tablets. No images showed individual women using technology. However, there were pictures of mixed groups where both genders used the same technology

Both men and women were equally represented in photographs of climate change demonstrations.

4.3 Gender and energy technology

Since gender was seldom addressed, there were no noticeable differences in how it was presented across different technologies of energy production or distribution.

4.4 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)

Gender was mentioned in relation to fossil fuels four times, whereas it was mentioned only once in relation to renewable energy. However, there was no discernible difference in how gender was presented between these different energy sources.

4.5 Gender and energy labour market

The schoolbooks analyzed showed minimal discussion of gender-specific issues like the pay gap or skills gap in relation to the energy sector. Gender was rarely mentioned critically or in depth. Men were prominently depicted in various work-related contexts, such as in fossil fuels or as explorers, while women were underrepresented, mainly appearing in roles using technology or as a climate activist unrelated to energy work.

Textually, men were mentioned in the energy labor market context twice: one as an expert discussing renewable energy opportunities and another as an oil rig worker

describing his job. Both of these books are for the subject Geography. The field worker explaining his job on a drilling platform is for the 6th grade for Realschulen in Bavaria. The expert talking about job opportunities is for the 10th grade in Berlin and is used in Gymnasiums. On is for the 6th grade in Bavaria and is used. Women were referenced as climate scientists in similar contexts, but gender-specific discussions were absent. Both these instances were in one schoolbook which is used in Bavaria for the 10th grade in Gymnasiums for the subject Geography.

When discussing the energy sector as a workplace, gender neutrality prevailed. Opportunities in renewable energy and traditional sectors like oil were presented without gender differentiation.

Observations:

1. **Pay Gap and Skills Gap:** Not addressed in relation to gender within the schoolbooks.
2. **Gender and Professional Roles:** Men predominated in managerial, analytical, and labor roles related to energy, while women were depicted more in supportive or advocacy roles like climate activists.
3. **Energy Sectors as Places for Work:** Gender distinctions were not emphasized in discussions about career opportunities within different energy sectors.

Overall, the schoolbooks maintained a neutral stance on gender in the energy sector, lacking substantial engagement with gender-specific issues or promoting gender diversity in energy professions.

4.6 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)

Regarding gender and energy-related social practices, there were no specific differences observed in how gender was presented. The schoolbooks did not address social practices related to energy in a manner that differentiated by gender. Topics that could potentially involve gender aspects, such as household energy use or community energy practices, were not discussed in relation to gender roles or perspectives.

Topics like transportation, particularly e-mobility, were discussed in terms of their mechanics and functionality, whereas everyday activities such as cooking or heating were not mentioned.

In summary, the schoolbooks did not delve into gender-specific implications or differences in relation to energy-related social practices, maintaining a neutral stance on these aspects throughout their content.

4.7 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy

In the analyzed schoolbooks, there was a notable absence of content related to energy social innovation, prosumerism, and new energy practices. These topics were

scarcely mentioned, with limited exploration beyond basic group projects on sustainability, recycling, and water conservation.

Regarding gender representation in climate activism, instances where gender was explicitly mentioned predominantly highlighted female climate activists. This was evident in text references to female activists and one photograph depicting a female climate activist.

However, there were no specific differences observed in how gender was presented in the context of energy activism or social innovation related to energy communities, new energy practices, or prosumerism. The overall lack of coverage in these areas in the schoolbooks precluded deeper analysis of gender dynamics or disparities within these contexts.

In conclusion, while female representation in climate activism was noted, the broader spectrum of gender dynamics within energy-related social innovation and prosumerism was largely overlooked in the analyzed educational materials.

4.8 Gender and energy governance

The portrayal of gender in German schoolbooks regarding energy policy and sociotechnical change revealed few specific differences or considerations:

1. **Gender in Energy Policy:** There were no notable differences observed in how gender was presented in discussions on energy policy. Male politicians were predominantly mentioned, but gender was not a highlighted aspect of these discussions.
2. **Gender in Roles in Sociotechnical Change:** Similarly, there were no distinct differences noted in how gender was represented among innovators or successful leaders in energy sociotechnical change. The schoolbooks did not emphasize gender roles or discuss gender implications in relation to innovation or leadership within the energy sector.

Overall, the schoolbooks maintained a neutral stance on gender in their portrayal of energy policy and sociotechnical change. They focused primarily on environmental and technological aspects without exploring gender-specific perspectives or roles in depth.

5 TEMPORALITIES

In the analysis of German schoolbooks, temporal aspects such as past and future were rarely discussed in relation to gender within the context of energy.

1. **Temporal Aspects and Gender Energy Nexus:** There were no specific aspects of temporalities discussed in the schoolbooks that highlighted gender within the energy nexus. References to past energy systems primarily focused on historical usage without addressing gender roles or their impact on current energy practices.
2. **Gender-Energy Nexus in Past and Future Perspectives:** Gender issues related to energy were not contextualized in terms of past traditional roles

shaping current energy use or future aspirations for gender equality in the energy sector. The schoolbooks did not explore how historical gender roles influenced contemporary energy practices or discuss future scenarios where gender equality could impact energy transitions.

- 3. Acceleration and Urgency of Change:** Discussions on gender-energy nexus did not emphasize acceleration or urgency of change. While future implications of climate change and energy policies were mentioned, gender considerations in relation to the urgency of energy transitions were not addressed.

Overall, the schoolbooks maintained a neutral stance on gender within temporal contexts related to energy discourse. They primarily focused on factual information about energy systems and policies without integrating gender-specific perspectives on historical influences or future aspirations for gender equality in the energy sector.

6 LANGUAGE

Gender-sensitive language was minimally integrated into the descriptions of energy content in German schoolbooks, as observed in the coding analysis:

- 1. Usage of "Humans":** The term "humans" ("Menschen") was used four times, which was coded under gender-neutral terms. This term is inclusive as it encompasses all genders without specifying any particular gender.
- 2. Gendered Language Instances:** Gendered language, such as "Bürger und Bürgerinnen" (citizens), and "Wissenschaftler und Wissenschaftlerinnen" (scientists), was used twice. These instances were coded under feminatives, indicating a specific effort to include both genders in the language.
- 3. Gender-Neutral Terms:** The phrase "young people" ("junge Leute") was used once, coded under gender-neutral terms. This reflects an inclusive approach to language, avoiding gender-specific references.

Inclusive Language in Energy Content

Overall, the language used to describe energy content in German schoolbooks tends to be gender-neutral and inclusive. The predominant use of "humans" and occasional inclusion of feminine forms like "Bürger und Bürgerinnen" and "Wissenschaftler und Wissenschaftlerinnen" demonstrates an effort to acknowledge and include all genders. This approach aligns with current movements towards gender-inclusive language in German society, where efforts are made to represent women and non-binary individuals alongside men in linguistic expressions.

However, it's important to note that descriptions of human roles in energy contexts are infrequent in the schoolbooks analyzed. When language addressing humans is used, it generally employs impersonal and neutral terms like "humans," which avoids specifying gender unless necessary. This reflects a tendency towards inclusive language practices but also highlights a broader trend of neutralizing gender in educational materials.

7 MISSING THEMES

Several crucial energy-related themes were notably absent in the analyzed German schoolbooks:

1. **Energy Citizenship:** There is a lack of content addressing energy citizenship, which involves engaging individuals in energy decision-making and fostering community involvement.
2. **Energy Independence:** The books primarily discuss energy dependence but do not explore strategies for achieving energy independence or resilience against external energy disruptions.
3. **Human-Centered Energy Practices:** Important topics such as sustainable energy practices, recycling, water conservation, and dietary habits related to energy consumption are insufficiently covered.
4. **Energy Availability:** The concept of energy availability, including factors influencing it and its impact on society, is not addressed in the schoolbooks.

The German schoolbooks reviewed lack several crucial energy-related themes. They notably omit discussions on **Energy Citizenship**, which involves engaging individuals in energy decision-making and community involvement. Additionally, there is a lack of exploration into **Energy Independence**, sustainable practices like recycling and water conservation, and understanding energy availability and its societal impacts. These topics are essential for fostering informed citizenship, empowering communities to adopt sustainable energy solutions, and preparing students to address current and future energy challenges effectively. Integrating these themes into energy education is crucial for equipping students with the knowledge and skills needed for sustainable development.

8 OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES

Did you observe any other relevant issues you want to reflect on? Any issues that might be specific for your national educational context)

9 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM

In exploring energy education, a critical observation emerges regarding the representation of energy systems and their relevance to humans. The analyzed texts notably lack a human-centered approach, which is pivotal for fostering personal connection and understanding among learners. By sidelining the human factor, the information presented becomes less relatable, potentially hindering students' ability to grasp the significance of energy in their lives and future.

A stronger human-centred approach should consider the consumers and producers of energy in their differentiated roles. A generalisation of people simply as "human" negates the needs and interests arising from their different social (gender) roles, as does a one-sided view of the energy system from a male perspective.

Guidance Note

Energy, fundamentally intertwined with people's daily existence and the trajectory of societies, should be portrayed as such in educational materials. Highlighting this connection not only enhances comprehension but also underscores the urgency and relevance of energy-related topics in shaping sustainable futures.

Moreover, there is a call to depart from conventional narratives about energy and its sources. Embracing a holistic and systemic approach in discussing energy opens new avenues for critical thinking and dialogue. By breaking away from familiar paths, educators can stimulate innovative perspectives and deeper insights into the interconnectedness of energy systems with environmental, social, and economic dimensions.

In essence, advocating for a more human-centric portrayal of energy and encouraging holistic discussions can enrich energy education. This approach not only enhances comprehension but also empowers students to critically engage with complex energy issues and contribute meaningfully to sustainable energy transitions.

Annex 1. A table of themes occurring in textbooks

<i>The most visible topics/ themes (based on codes). e.g.</i>	<i>No. of occurrence</i>	<i>Subject</i>	<i>Grade/ level of education</i>
Energy sources	882	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Gender	303	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Climate Change	270	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Energy Infrastructure	137	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Temporal references	128	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Energy Governance	51	Geography	9 th /10 th grade
Energy Practices	49	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade
Type of Energy	45	Geography, General sciences	5 th /6 th and 9 th /10 th grade

Annex 2. Missing topics/themes

Missing topics/ themes (based on codes). e.g.
Context
Figurative Language
Related ideas
Gender Sensitive Language
Sustainable resource management
Health
Economy
Energy independence
Energy citizenship
Energy availability
Security

SOURCES

- Bendel, M. (2017). *TERRA Geographie für Bayern. Ausgabe für Realschulen. Schülerbuch 5. Schuljahr: Ausgabe für Realschulen ab 2016.*
- Bildung im Schulalter - BMBF.* (o. D.). Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung - BMBF. https://www.bmbf.de/bmbf/de/bildung/bildung-im-schulalter/bildung-im-schulalter_node.html
- Breibisch, M., Reisle, K., Wachter, S. & Zitzelsberger, U. (2018). *Unsere Erde 6. Jahrgangsstufe - Realschule Bayern - Schülerbuch.*
- Dendorfer, U., Maier, W., Röckl, F., Sinterhauf, R. & Wimmer, F. (2017). *NUT - Natur und Technik 5. Jahrgangsstufe - Mittelschule Bayern - Schülerbuch.*
- Diercke Geografie 9 / 10. Schülerband. Gymnasien. Berlin und Brandenburg: Ausgabe 2016.* (2017).
- Diercke Geographie 10. Schülerband. für Gymnasien in Bayern: Ausgabe 2017.* (2022).
- Edelstein, B. (2023, 21. Juli). *Das Bildungssystem in Deutschland.* bpb.de. <https://www.bpb.de/themen/bildung/dossier-bildung/163283/das-bildungssystem-in-deutschland/>
- Emundts, C. (2024, 29. Mai). EU-Wahlprogramme: Wie die Parteien zur Klimapolitik stehen. [tagesschau.de. https://www.tagesschau.de/europawahl/parteien_und_programme/klimapolitik-100.html](https://www.tagesschau.de/europawahl/parteien_und_programme/klimapolitik-100.html)
- Erlebnis Naturwissenschaften 5/6. Schülerband. für Berlin und Brandenburg: Ausgabe 2021.* (2021).
- Flath, M. (2017). *Unsere Erde - Berlin, Brandenburg.*
- Fokus Biologie - Neubearbeitung - Schulbücher im Paket - 5. . .* (o. D.). Cornelsen Verlag. <https://www.cornelsen.de/produkte/fokus-biologie-neubearbeitung-schulbuecher-im-paket-5-jahrgangsstufe-natur-und-technik-bio-naturwiss-arb-9783060119066>
- Landesinstitut für Schule und Medien Berlin-Brandenburg & Senatsverwaltung für Bildung, Jugend und Familie. (2018). *Framework Curriculum 1-10 compact.* <https://bildungserver.berlin->

brandenburg.de/fileadmin/bbb/unterricht/rahmenlehrplaene/rlp1-10/RLP_kompakt_1-10_Englisch.pdf

LehrplanPLUS - Gymnasium - 5 - Geographie - Fachprofile. (o. D.).

<https://www.lehrplanplus.bayern.de/fachprofil/gymnasium/geographie/5>

Natur und Technik 5./6. Schuljahr. Naturwissenschaften - Berlin/Brandenburg - Schulbuch. (2023).

Natura/Schülerbuch 5. Schuljahr: Ausgabe Bayern ab 2017/Schwerpunkt Naturwissenschaftliches Arbeiten. (2017).

Seydlitz Geografie 9 / 10 . Schülerband. für Berlin und Brandenburg: Ausgabe 2023. (2023).

Seydlitz Geographie 6. Schülerband. Realschule. Bayern: Ausgabe 2016. (2018).

Seydlitz Geographie 10. Schülerband. für Gymnasien in Bayern: Ausgabe 2016. (2022).

Stand der Klimabildung und Maßnahmen zur Stärkung in der Bildungspraxis | Umwelt im Unterricht: Materialien und Service für Lehrkräfte – BMUV-Bildungsservice | Umwelt im Unterricht. (o. D.). UiU. <https://www.umwelt-im-unterricht.de/hintergrund/stand-der-klimabildung-und-massnahmen-zur-staerkung-in-der-bildungspraxis/>

TERRA Geographie 9/10. Ausgabe für Berlin und Brandenburg. Schülerbuch Klasse 9/10. (2018).

TERRA Geographie 10. Schulbuch Klasse 10. Ausgabe Bayern Gymnasium. (2022).

Unsere Erde 10. Jahrgangsstufe. Gymnasium Bayern - Schülerbuch. (2022).

APPENDIX 3. ITALIAN NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

Fabiola L. Falconieri¹, Antonio De Nicola¹, Tatiana Patriarca¹, Vittoria Maria Peri¹, Valentina Tudisca², Adriana Valente²

1. ENEA
2. CNR-IRPPS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The full compulsory education period was chosen as field of analysis. Since, in Italy, pupils are supposed to be exposed to the same learning opportunities and should attain the same learning goals, while preparing for their future study and career choices, we wanted to investigate if content of textbooks adopted in compulsory education were somehow contributing to discouraging girls from choosing STEM, and in particular from developing an interest in energy issues and careers.

The main source of reference for understanding how energy is taught in Italian compulsory school are the Indicazioni Nazionali 2012, the national education framework establishing the general goals for skills development and learning objectives of each discipline included in school curricula, from ECEC to ISCED level 3, and the integration regulations introducing Civic Education as a new transversal discipline in 2020. Energy is not a subject by itself, but in accordance with Indicazioni Nazionali 2012, science subjects have to deal with it as a physic phenomenon, while technology and geography are to deal with energy issues, such as the transformation of resources, its environmental impact, and its relevance for mankind survival. Teachers of any subjects are also tasked with contributing to develop content for the Civic Education areas of teaching, and STEM subjects appear to be well suited for the “Sustainable development, environmental education, knowledge and heritage protection and of the territory” area of study. So we made the hypothesis that relevant energy content should be searched not only in textbooks of technology and geography, but also sciences (including biology, chemistry, earth science) and mathematics.

Each book was skimmed to single out the paragraphs dealing with energy, which were firstly associated with the codes describing the sematic context (category from 1.open coding to 10.Energy governance), and then associated with the specific codes (from 11.Energy sources to 21.Context). Separate analysis were carried out for each school level (ISCED levels 1, 2 and the first 2 years of level 3) which nevertheless depicted very similar situations as far as the energy-gender nexus. The rare occurrences where gender codes applied were not meaningful and could not provide a basis for further comments. Finally, in all textbooks analysed we could not find occurrences of gender misrepresentation or imbalance. Another aspect that is

completely absent from the textbooks we analysed, and is closely related to the gender issue, is energy as a professional field. Girls, and boys as well, are not given any information or conceptual tool to consider energy careers, and so they cannot perceive and debate the gender nexus with challenges and opportunities they may encounter in their future adult life.

The report finally questions whether gender neutrality in school texts, though originally introduced to answer Gender Equality's concerns, may not contribute to a sort of blindness to the issue, a blindness that leaves girls and boys unaware and so more susceptible to gender bias and stereotypes perpetuated in their social environment, not necessarily at school, rather in the family or among peers. Presenting science, in general, and energy specifically as gender neutral is a traditional approach in the global North, that is being increasingly challenged by the Gendered Innovations approach. Recent literature is showing how the energy issue is not a gender neutral one, and that the gender factor may be the relevant one for the adoption of solutions and virtuous behaviour by consumers and citizen (<http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/case-studies/energy.html>). The literature (T. Breda et al. 2020) on the so-called gender-equality paradox in STEM, (increased gender differences in participation in STEM careers arise in countries that have more gender equality), is another aspect to be considered and suggests that the hypothesis that, in STEM or energy learning at school, gender neutrality may be conducive to some gender blindness should be further investigated.

1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

1.1. Educational system in Italy - brief characteristics

For a detailed presentation of the Italian school system, main reference is EURIDICE, European Education and Culture Executive Agency, at [Overview \(europa.eu\)](https://euridice.europa.eu/). A synthesis is provided here: the Italian school system is governed on the basis of two principles: the principle of subsidiarity and the principle of school autonomy. The central authorities, namely the Ministry of Education and Merit, MiM (<https://www.miur.gov.it>) and the Ministry of University and Research, MUR (<https://www.mur.gov.it>) are responsible for the general administration of education at national level, each for their relevant fields: MiM for ECEC (Early Childhood Education and Care) and ISCED levels up to 4; MUR for ISCED level 5 and above. Regions have joint responsibility with the central authority for the organisation of ECEC, the school calendar, the distribution of schools in their territory, the right to study at higher level, and exclusive legislative competence in the organisation of the regional vocational education and training system. Local authorities have responsibility for the maintenance of schools' premises, the transport of pupils, merging or establishment of schools, from ECEC to upper secondary education. Finally, schools have a high degree of pedagogical autonomy: they define their curricula in compliance with the MiM Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 (see 2.2), arrange teaching school time and class organization, and may widen the educational offer.

Italy adopts a common core curriculum provision: after successfully completing primary education (ISCED level 1), all students progress to lower secondary level (ISCED level 2) where they follow the same general common core curriculum. Full-time compulsory education (highlighted by a pink bar in the diagram below) starts at 6 years of age and ends at 16 years of age, so it includes the ISCED level 1, level 2 and the first two years of level 3.

1.2. Energy education in Italy

The so called Indicazioni Nazionali 2012, (https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/51310/DM+254_2012.pdf) are the national education framework establishing the general goals for skills development and learning objectives of each discipline included in school curricula, from ECEC to ISCED level 3. They are the main source of reference for understanding how energy is taught in compulsory school.

Energy education in Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 for the first cycle of instruction:

Although in the science curriculum energy is traditionally dealt with as a physics concept, some novelty were introduced that reflect a new approach toward the energy issue and related themes:

- technology, a new subject which studies how mankind can operate and transform resources and the environment to ensure survival and the satisfaction of our needs. As far as energy is concerned, at the end of the first cycle, pupils are supposed to be aware of the transformation processes of resources, of energy consumption and their environmental impact.
- geography, which studies the relationships of human societies with each other and with the planet earth, relating economic, legal, anthropological, scientific and environmental issues, also includes learning paths that introduce students to themes such as climate change and environmental impacts, that are related to the energy issue.

Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 for the second cycle of instruction:

the same approach is adopted; while science is to deal with energy as a physics phenomenon, it is geography the elective subject to approach themes such as sustainable development, climate change and the energy issue. This is a general provision for all kind of schools in the first two years of ISCED level 3, that is during the compulsory period. On the other hand, the study of technology is discontinued, and only technical and vocational and training schools provide further teaching in specific technology sectors, in accordance with their programmes.

Over time the Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 have been modified or integrated with more guidelines and regulations addressing specific issues, among which the most relevant for understanding the educational framework within which energy is taught are:

- in 2018, the introduction of Education to Citizenship and Sustainability, (<https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/0/Indicazioni+nazionali+e+nuovi+scenari/>) with reference to the objectives set by the UN in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development;
- in 2020, the introduction of Civic Education, (Law no. 92 of 20th Aug. 2019, "Introducing civic education at school") as a new transversal discipline with three main areas of teaching, (the Italian Constitution; Sustainable development, environmental education, knowledge and heritage protection

and of the territory; Digital Citizenship), in all learning cycles (ECEC; first cycle; second cycle); that was followed by the Act of Political-institutional Direction for the year 2022, (https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/5407202/Atto+di+indirizzo+politico+istituzionale+MI_anno+2022.pdf/0eee30b9-22b8-0246-e227-bf693be43719?t=163180277742) that identifies "Education for sustainability" among the Ministry's priorities over the next three years and establishes the teaching of Civic Education "an indispensable condition for sustaining the ecological and cultural transition of the country".

- the MiM Guidelines for the STEM Disciplines, October 2023, (<https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/0/Linee+guida+STEM.pdf/2aa0b11f-7609-66ac-3fd8-2c6a03c80f77?version=1.0&t=1698173043586>) that provide guidance on the realization of new didactical pathways for STEM teaching in all learning cycles and, for the first time, acknowledges that girls may not have equal opportunities for developing their interest and skills in STEM.

2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS

We choose to select as field of research the full compulsory education period, when children are supposed to be exposed to the same learning opportunities and should attain the same learning goals, while preparing for their future study and career choices; still, there is a large consensus in literature that the gender gap in STEM becomes more apparent when specialization begins and students make choices about which subject to study (UNESCO, 2017). Consequently, we wanted to investigate if content of textbooks adopted in compulsory education were somehow contributing to discouraging girls from developing an interest in energy issues and careers.

In particular we questioned:

- Whether content related to energy education (i.e., processes of energy production, storage, use and management) is presented in a gender-sensitive way;
- Whether representation of energy issues creates equal opportunities for students to develop their knowledge and skills in energy-related sectors;
- Whether and how content related to the energy transition encourages women to participate in it;

3 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTING AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Corpus of texts

In Italy, data on textbook adoptions are not publicly accessible due to commercial reasons (A. Valente et al. 2022), consequently, to identify a significant corpus of texts we adopted the following qualitative criteria:

- Subject relevance
- Publisher popularity
- Date of issue
- Budget

Subject relevance:

A major criterium for choosing the textbooks was the relevance of the subjects, as described in the Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 and revised in 2019 with the introduction of Civic Education. Being a transversal discipline, Civic Education tasks all teachers with contributing to develop content on one of its three areas, and STEM teachers, whose subjects were traditionally conceived as very distant from social and historical themes are engaged in the "Sustainable development, environmental education, knowledge and heritage protection and of the territory" area of study; consequently, since 2020, new updated version of textbooks have been issued, including Civic Education themes and study suggestions. As a consequence though energy is not a subject by itself, energy content is scattered across different subjects. So, we made a first hypothesis, that relevant energy content for our investigation should be searched within an area created at the intersection of three main semantic fields, namely, gender, STEM (here the acronym is also referring to school subjects) and sustainability (here relevant subjects are civic education and geography). The hypothesis can be represented with the following diagram:

Consequently, relevant textbooks are: sciences (including biology, chemistry, earth science), maths, technology, and geography.

The publisher popularity:

We made a preliminary online search to retrieve papers useful to understand the governance of the school publishing industry, and particularly if there were mechanism of regulation of the educational sector had as far as content presentation and gender stereotypes.

As far as pedagogical content, the publishing educational sector complies with the MiM Indicazioni Nazionali 2012 (https://www.miur.gov.it/documents/20182/51310/DM+254_2012.pdf), as amended with the introduction of Civic Education, and as far as formats with the Ministry regulations D.M. n. 781 of 27, September 2013, (https://www.istruzione.it/allegati/decreto_libri_digitali.pdf) on the different types of textbooks, integrative digital resources and pedagogical criteria;

Most relevantly, the sector has its own governance codes, that both specifically address gender and minority discrimination:

The Self-regulation Code for the Educational Publishing Sector, by Associazione Italiana Editori, the Italian association of publishing houses, AIE, (https://www.aie.it/Portals/38/Allegati/CodiceAutoregolamentazioneScolastica_gen2011.pdf?ver=OYJEY23kwSz6gmYtz056Ag%3d%3d) 2011;

POLITE self-regulation code to ensure that in the design and production of textbooks and teaching materials for schools, attention is paid to the development of gender identity with a view to promoting equal opportunities for men and women, (<https://www.aie.it/Portals/38/Allegati/CodicePolite.pdf>), 1999.

The POLITE project in 1999 was an early initiative of school publishers that aimed to revise textbooks and promote fair opportunities for boys and girls. The ensuing AIE Self-regulation Code for the Educational Sector is mandatory for all members and has specific provision for preventing biases, stereotypes and minority discrimination, at: Sector D. Rules of behaviour – I. The publisher responsibility - art. 15.

The publisher, while not interfering with the cultural and scientific approach of the work, is to assess that the information given respects the plurality of ideas and cultures and that the content does not involve any discrimination related to gender, the race, language, religion, political opinions, and personal and social conditions of individuals.

(https://www.aie.it/Portals/38/Allegati/CodiceAutoregolamentazioneScolastica_gen2011.pdf=OYJEY23kwSz6gmYtz056Ag%3d%3d , translation by ENEA).

We then had informal talks with teachers, during which they were asked to relate their experience in using textbooks and gender stereotypes. All teachers were aware of the gender gap, although they consider it a major challenge for STEM in general, not as specifically referred to the energy issue. Teachers also confirmed what the preliminary search of the sector governance was suggesting, that is that as far as content textbooks were more or less equivalent. They provided us with lists and links to the digital version of the books they were using, and most reported Zanichelli publishing house as the most referenced for the scientific subjects.

Date of issue

As new provisions are issued by the Ministry of Education and Merit to update the Indicazioni Nazionali 2012, textbooks need to be revised accordingly. Only issues from the year 2020 were taken into consideration for the text analysis.

Budget

Since there was no specific budget for this task, in the analysis we included the books provided by the teachers. We thank Zanichelli for providing a set of books, including science subjects (ISCED level 2 and 3) and technology (ISCED level 2).

3.2 Sample characteristics

Text table

textbook	subject	ISCED level	Students' age	Publisher	Date of issue	N.of coded segment	Pages
Missione futuro scienza	science and technology	1	10-11	Pearson I pinguini	2020	5	70-71; 84; 90-91
Missione futuro GEOGRAFIA	geography	1	9-10	Pearson I pinguini	2020	6	32-35
Amica terra	science and technology	1	10-11	Giunti scuola	2024	9	10-11

Guidance Note

textbook	subject	ISCED level	Students' age	Publisher	Date of issue	N.of coded segment	Pages
Viva imparare	science and technology	1	10-11	Giunti scuola	2023	6	51
Pianeta Tecnologia	technology	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2023	26	17; 21; 215; 217; 230-232; 233-237; 242; 250; 266; 274-277; 280-281; 284-285 319; 356; 366; 410
Pianeta Tecnologia disegno	Technical drawing	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2023	NONE	-----
Scienze in Agenda A	Science	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2022	3	96-97; 312-313; 364-365
Scienze in Agenda B	Life on earth	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2022	NONE	-----
Scienze in Agenda C	The human body	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2022	NONE	-----
Scienze in Agenda D	science – the earth	2	11-14	Zanichelli	2022	7	250-251; 253-256; 260-264
Go! Geografia oggi	geography	2	11-14	Mondadori	2022	8	52; 53; 58; 59; 60; 61; 210
Algebra multimediale.blu	Maths and statistics	3	14-16	Zanichelli	2024	2	60; 120;
Chimica sostenibile	chemistry	3	14-16	Zanichelli	2024	5	101; 141; 207
Biologia.a	Biology and agriculture	3	14-16	Zanichelli	2024	2	195
Geografia in 30 lezioni	geography	3	14-16	Zanichelli	20	28	89; 90; 91; 93; 94; 97; 99;101-103;

For each text shown in the Text table a detailed book sheet is provided in the enclosed excel file:

- Primary School ISCED1,
- First level secondary school (ISCED2), apart from the books: Scienze in Agenda B, life on earth; Scienze in Agenda C, the human body; and Pianeta tecnologia technical drawing, since no relevant content was found during the preliminary book skimming.
- Secondary school (ISCED3)

3.3 Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook

We used as unit of analysis the paragraph; consequently we singled out the paragraphs dealing with energy, and firstly associated them with the codes describing the semantic context provided (category from 1.open coding to 10.Energy

governance), secondly we associated them with the specific codes provided (from 11.Energy sources to 21.Context).

Since the first book skimming, it was apparent that some of the provided categories/codes were to be most frequently applied while others had rare occurrences. We wanted a graphic tool to immediately and intuitively represent the situation: counting as 1 each occurrence of a specific main context category we were able to obtain radar diagrams, or spider graphs, that immediately represents the situation clearly. We had different diagram for context categories and content specific codes, for each of the ISCED level. Our primary focus was on the codes referring to gender (15.Individual actor; 16.Group of actors; 17.Professional role; 18.Other roles) unfortunately they were very rarely or never applied, consequently no further analysis on the nexus with energy context or content was possible.

4 RESULTS

Separate analysis were carried out for each school level (see specific chapters below), which nevertheless depicted very similar situations as far as the energy-gender nexus.

On the whole:

4.1. Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections

No energy- gender nexus was found

4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames

No energy- gender nexus was found

4.3 Gender and energy technology

No energy technology- gender nexus was found

4.4 Gender and energy sources (fossil fuels vs RES sectors)

No energy sources- gender nexus was found

4.5 Gender and energy labour market

No energy labour market- gender nexus was found

4.6 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)

No social role or energy consumption- gender nexus was found

4.7 Gender as related to energy citizenship and energy democracy

No energy citizenship- gender nexus was found

The above implies that no straight answers can be provided for the 3 questions framed at 3. main research questions, but see 11. Conclusion for further considerations.

5 TEMPORALITIES

No energy-gender nexus was found

6 LANGUAGE

The Italian language distinctly provides two grammatical genres, the masculine and feminine forms, for most of the terms (nouns and adjectives, with related articles and pronouns), while only in minority cases exist terms that express the two forms, male and female, while in the Italian language the neutral form is not provided. However, the use of the language has privileged the male-only to indicate situations in which both male and female terms are present; it is the so-called unmarked masculine, also called "over-extended" as it entails an extension of the male gender functions, frequently justified on the basis of claims of neutrality, which in fact leads to a misgendering. Other means to avoid gender reference are impersonal constructions and gender unmarked pronouns and words, such as *persona*, pl *persone* (in English: person, pl. people).

Examples of unmarked masculine:

Quotes from *Geografia in 30 lezioni*:

capitolo: le fonti di energia non rinnovabili

- I **deattori** sottolineano i pericoli legati alla produzione del nucleare
- Per questo motivo è in corso un acceso dibattito tra sostenitori e **deattori**

Translation:

Chapter: non renewable energy sources

"**Detractors** underline the dangers linked to nuclear production

For this reason there is a heated debate between supporters and **detractors**

capitolo: le fonti di energia non rinnovabili

- scorie radioattive, altamente tossiche per **l'essere umano** e l'ambiente
- agenti chimici che sono ritenuti pericolosi per **l'essere umano** e l'ambiente

Translation

Chapter: non renewable energy sources

- radioactive waste, highly toxic to **humans** and the environment";
- chemical agents which are considered dangerous to **humans** and the environment

Quotes from Go! Geografia oggi

capitolo: Temi di storia e cittadinanza/Lo sviluppo sostenibile

- In **molti** si chiesero cosa sarebbe accaduto quando queste risorse, per natura limitate, si fossero esaurite

Translation:

Chapter: History and citizenship issues/Sustainable development

- **Many** wondered what would happen when these resources, by nature limited, were exhausted

Capitolo: Temi di storia e cittadinanza/Lo sviluppo sostenibile

- avrebbero presto esaurito le risorse a disposizione del genere umano

Translation:

Chapter: History and citizenship issues/Sustainable development

- would soon have exhausted the resources available to **mankind**

Comments:

- detrattori (English: detractors), plural of detrattore, in the plural form can be used as unmarked masculine;
- molti (English: many), plural of molto, in the plural is only used as unmarked masculine;
- essere umano (English: humans) and genere umano (English: mankind) are only used in the form of unmarked masculine;

Examples of non-gendered words

Quote from Viva imparare:

Capitolo: ENERGIA E FORZE / LABORATORIO DI BASE / L'energia e le sue fonti

- Per ottenere l'energia che ci serve per riscaldare illuminare le nostre case, per volgere attività industriali, per far funzionare auto, macchinari, computer **noi** utilizziamo diverse fonti di energia.

Translation:

Chapter: ENERGY AND FORCES/ BASIC LAB / Energy and Its Sources "

To obtain the energy we need to heat and light our homes, to carry out industrial activities, and to power cars, machinery, and computers, **we** use various energy sources.

Quote from Missione futuro geografia:

Capitolo: I mutamenti climatici

- Più consumiamo, più inquiniamo e più surriscaldiamo la terra.

Translation:

Chapter: Climate change

- The more **we consume**, the more **we pollute** and the more **we overheat** the earth.

Quotes from Missione futuro scienze:

Capitolo: Non lasciare impronte

- Preferire i mezzi pubblici all'auto è un'ottima scelta per l'ambiente: più persone la fanno più si riduce il loro impatto, perché tra più **persone** si divide il peso di CO₂ prodotta.

Translation:

Chapter: Don't leave footprints.

- Preferring public transportation to cars is an excellent choice for the environment: the more **people** make it, the lower their impact, as the CO₂ emissions are divided among more passengers.

Capitolo: IO E .. L'OBIETTIVO N° 7

- Per raggiungere l'obiettivo 7, gli stati si sono impegnati a:
- garantire a più **persone** l'accesso a servizi energetici moderni e affidabili, con impianti sicuri ed efficienti;

Translation:

Chapter ME AND .. [SDG] GOAL NO. 7.

- To achieve Goal 7, states have committed to:
- ensuring access to modern and reliable energy services with safe and efficient facilities to more **people**.

Quote from Amica Terra:

Capitolo: L'ENERGIA E LE FORZE/ EDUCAZIONE CIVICA – La produzione di energia
In alcuni Paesi in via di sviluppo dell'Africa e dell'Asia, infatti, le **persone** vivono ancora oggi senza energia elettrica.

Translation:

Chapter "ENERGY AND FORCES/ CIVIC EDUCATION – Energy Production"

In some developing countries in Africa and Asia, **people** still live without electricity today.

Quotes from Pianeta tecnologia:

Capitolo 1 – che cos'è l'energia; Lezione 3 – il sole; Verso la fotosintesi artificiale

- **Noi** dobbiamo fare molto meglio!

Translation:

Chapter 1 - What is energy; Lesson 3 - the sun; Towards artificial photosynthesis

- **We** must do much better!

Capitolo 3 – le macchine e i motori; Lezione 3- le macchine motrici; Cittadinanza verde, l'automobile elettrica

- l'automobile non scarica gas nocivi in atmosfera durante il suo funzionamento, diminuendo il forte inquinamento che affligge tutte le città del mondo e che ogni anno uccide decine di migliaia di **persone** nella sola Italia

Translation:

Chapter 3 - machinery and engines - Lesson 3- Driving machines - Green citizenship, the electric car

- during operation the car does not discharge harmful gases into the atmosphere, so reducing the high levels of pollution that afflict all cities in the world and that kill tens of thousands of **people** every year in Italy alone

Comments:

- the pronoun noi (English: we), which is non gendered and inclusive is used to refer to "us as everybody", not to a specific group;
- persona pl. persone, (English: person, pl people) is a feminine noun which is gender neutral.

Examples of impersonal language construction:

Quote from Missione futuro geografia:

capitolo: I mutamenti climatici

- Per produrre elettricità, per far funzionare le fabbriche, per mettere in moto auto e aerei **si usano petrolio e carbone**.

translation:

Chapter: Climate change

- **Oil and coal are used** to produce electricity, to run factories, to start cars and aircraft.

Quote from Scienze in agenda A:

Capitolo A12 – i principi della termodinamica; Lezione 3 - le forze del moto circolare; Pensa sostenibile: una cascata di energia

Nel nostro pianeta esistono diversi modi con cui ricavare l'energia utile per le attività umane, mantenendo un basso impatto ambientale. **Si sfruttano fonti di energia definite e rinnovabili** perché si rigenerano in maniera illimitata o abbastanza velocemente da non rischiare di esaurirsi entro poche generazioni.

Translation

Chapter A12 - the principles of thermodynamics; Lesson 3 - the forces of circular motion; Sustainable thinking: a cascade of energy

On our planet there are several ways to obtain useful energy for human activities, maintaining a low environmental impact. **Specific, renewable energy sources are exploited** because they regenerate unlimitedly or fast enough to avoid the risk of depleting within a few generations.

Quote from Scienze in Agenda D:

Capitolo D8- l'impatto umano sull'ambiente; Lezione 1 – le risorse da tutelare; Le alternative energetiche

Per migliorare le condizioni di vita a livello globale **occorre** anche impegnarsi per ridurre gli sprechi e per usare nel modo più efficiente possibile l'energia che viene prodotta e distribuita

Translation:

Chapter D8- Human impact on the environment; Lesson 1 - Resources to be protected; Energy alternatives

Efforts to reduce waste and to use as efficiently as possible the energy that is produced and distributed are also **required** to improve global living conditions.

Quote from Chimica Sostenibile

Capitolo 12 – Il PH e le ossidoriduzioni; Introduzione: l'energia circolare

- Per rendere possibile un'economia circolare bisogna passare all'uso generalizzato di fonti di energia rinnovabile.

Translation:

Chapter 12 - PH and redox; Introduction: Circular energy

- In order to make a circular economy possible, we need/it is needed to switch to the widespread use of renewable energy sources.

Comments:

- the “Si passivante” makes a passive sentence impersonal, since the indirect object, that is the agent, is removed
- in Italian verbs that indicate necessity, occurrence, appearance are called “improperly impersonal verbs” and they have as subject an entire subordinate sentence: the verb *occorrere* (English: require) has as subject “impegnarsi per ridurre gli sprechi” (English: efforts to reduce waste); the verb *bisognare* (English: it is needed) has as subject “passare all'uso generalizzato” (English: to switch to widespread use)

7 MISSING THEMES

Energy as a professional field is completely absent from the textbooks we analysed. This is really relevant for question 3. Whether and how content related to the energy transition encourages women to participate in it. Since the issue is not dealt with, no answer can be provided, nevertheless a point is to be made: if girls, and boys as well, are not given any information or conceptual tool to consider energy careers, they cannot perceive and debate the gender nexus with challenges and opportunities they may encounter in their future adult life, see 10. Conclusions.

The other missing themes are:

6.Security, the code was never applied in all ISCED levels.

7.Eenergy independence, not dealt with in ISCED 1

8 OTHER RELEVANT ISSUES

All STEM textbooks in ISCED 2 and 3 had introductory pages dedicated to the AGENDA 2030 and the SDG's, which were not analyzed since energy was not directly dealt with. Most of the chapters/passages we did analyze instead, were then associated with some specific SDG, namely:

- SDG 13 Climate action, 15 occurrences
- SDG 7, Affordable and clean energy, 13 occurrences
- SDG 9, Industry innovation and infrastructure, 2 occurrences
- SDG 12, Responsible consumption and production, 2 occurrences
- SDG 11, Sustainable cities and communities, 1 occurrence
- SDG 17, Partnership for the Goals, 1 occurrence

Specific analysis per ISCED levels:

Primary schools (ISCED level 1)

In primary school, science and technology are usually dealt with in one volume; geography is dealt with in a separated volume. For each text shown in the Text tables 1, a detailed book sheet is provided in the enclosed excel file, Primary School.

While the books were firstly skimmed through to ascertain the relevant pages, it was immediately apparent that to cater for the interest of so young pupils, the complexity of the energy issue had been simplified and the discourse had been constrained to few essential concepts. We wanted a tool to immediately and intuitively represent the situation: counting as 1 each occurrence of a specific main context category we were able to obtain the following radar diagram that immediately represents the situation clearly:

Spider graph 1

The energy issue is contextualized within some recurrent semantic areas, which are consistent with the context defined by the Min regulations see 2.2 energy education in Italy:

2. Climate change, quote from Missione Futuro Geografia

Capitolo: I mutamenti climatici

Che legame c'è tra i nostri consumi, l'inquinamento e il surriscaldamento della terra? Per capire questo legame bisogna capire che cos'è l'effetto serra.

Translation:

Chapter: Climate change

What is the link between our consumption, pollution and the overheating of planet earth?

To understand this link you need to understand what the greenhouse effect is.

9. Energy citizenship, quote from Amica terra

Capitolo: L'ENERGIA E LE FORZE/ EDUCAZIONE CIVICA – La produzione di energia

Il 18 Febbraio è la giornata mondiale del risparmio energetico nata per discutere dei problemi collegati alla produzione e all'utilizzo dell'energia. A fine Marzo invece si celebra l'ora della terra, un evento promosso dal WWF per sensibilizzare sui problemi energetici: le persone sono invitate a spegnere le luci per un'ora e vengono spente anche le luci di edifici di tutto il mondo come il Colosseo A Roma e la Torre Eiffel a Parigi.

Translation:

Chapter: ENERGY AND FORCES/ CIVIC EDUCATION - Energy production

February 18 is the world day of energy saving, established to discuss the problems related to the production and use of energy. At the end of March, the Earth Hour is celebrated, an event promoted by the WWF to raise awareness about energy problems: people are invited to turn off the lights for an hour and around the world the lights of buildings such as the Colosseum in Rome and the Eiffel Tower in Paris are also turned off.

It is worth mentioning that some of the relevant paragraphs we associated to 9. Energy citizenship category are actually part of lists of recommendations for the pupils to act as aware citizens and change unsustainable daily routines, so we introduced a new code:

9.7 other; 9.7.1 Consumer action, lists of recommended activities, found in Missione Futuro Geografia. The chapter is labelled as "Civic Education; Global objectives" and marked with SDG 13 climate action. Quote:

Capitolo: Miei passi... per il cambiamento, nessuno escluso!

Cosa puoi fare tu per dare una mano al nostro pianeta e realizzare questo obiettivo? Indica con una X i passi che ritieni importante fare e sui quali pensi di poterti impegnare

- Vado a piedi, in bicicletta, con i mezzi pubblici.
- Spengo la luce quando non è necessaria.
- Tratto con cura gli oggetti e materiali che ho a disposizione di tutti i giorni.
- Non compro qualcosa di nuovo ogni volta che mi viene voglia.
- Mi vesto in maniera adeguata alla temperatura per non usare inutilmente riscaldamento e condizionatore.
- Non compro materiali usa e getta.

Translation:

Chapter: My steps... toward change, no one excluded!

What can you do to help our planet and achieve this goal?

Mark with an X the steps that you consider important to take and you think you can commit on

- I walk, ride a bicycle, use public transport.
- I turn off the light when I don't need it.
- I take care of things and materials I use every day.
- I don't buy something new every time I feel like it.
- I dress appropriately to weather temperature to avoid unnecessary heating and air conditioning.
- I do not buy throw-aways.

8. Energy availability, quote from Missione Futuro scienze

Capitolo: IO E .. L'OBIETTIVO N° 7

l'energia elettrica è essenziale sia per la produzione industriale, sia per la nostra vita quotidiana. Non tutti i paesi del mondo hanno la possibilità di accedere a una rete efficiente di energia elettrica.

Guidance Note

Translation:

Chapter: Me and [SDG] OBJECTIVE No. 7

Electricity is essential both for industrial production and for our daily lives. Not all countries in the world have access to an efficient electricity network.

3. Sustainable resources management, quote from Missione futuro scienze

Capitolo: Risparmiare energia

Inoltre, le fonti tradizionali, come sappiamo, sono destinate a esaurirsi, anche se gli esperti non concordano sul quando (ma c'è chi dice già in questo secolo!)

Translation:

Chapter: energy saving

Moreover, traditional sources, as we know, are destined to run out, though experts do not agree on the when (but some says even in this century!)

10. Energy governance,

Capitolo: Risparmiare energia

Da diversi anni la normativa europea prevede che i dispositivi elettrici riportino la classe energetica, che va da A+++ (massima efficienza J) a G (massimi consumi L).

Translation:

Chapter: energy saving

For several years now, European legislation has required that electrical devices are labelled with their energy class, ranging from A+++ (maximum efficiency J) to G (maximum consumption L).

4. Economy, quote from Missione Futuro scienze

Capitolo: risparmiare energia

Dunque, il costo economico è basso, ma il costo ambientale è altissimo

Translation:

Chapter: Saving Energy

So the economic cost is low, but the environmental cost is very high

5. Health, quote from Amica Terra

Capitolo: L'ENERGIA E LE FORZE/ EDUCAZIONE CIVICA – La produzione di energia

Queste fonti di energia producono sostanze inquinanti e polveri pericolose per l'ambiente e per l'essere umano.

Translation:

Chapter: ENERGY AND FORCES/ CIVIC EDUCATION - Energy production

These energy sources produce pollutants and dust that are dangerous to the environment and to human beings.

Most relevant is that the diagram shows areas that are completely neglected:

6. Security, and 7. Energy independence.

We did the same with the first level specific codes

Spider graph 2

It is immediately clear that the text had 6 segments that were gender marked:
15. Individual actor, all 6 occurrences were images, found in:

- Missione Futuro science, 5 images some showing people doing recommended actions: Choosing A+ appliances; choosing the bicycle; other people doing the washing

Guidance Note

- Missione Futuro geography 1 image, the portrait of young climate activist, Greta Tumberg

Another image, market as 16. group of actors, mix, was found in Amica terra, introducing Civic Education:

Most relevant is that the area 17. Professional roles and 18. Other roles are both neglected.

First grade secondary school (ISCED level 2)

For the context main categories, we obtained:

Spider graph 3

Consistently with Min regulations (see 2.2 Energy education in Italy), the most popular context to introduce students to the energy issue are:

2.Climate change

It is worth mentioning that we had to introduce some new codes to describe relevant context:

- 2.2.1 Climate justice, unequal impacts of climate change on poor or vulnerable populations; 1 occurrence found in Pianeta tecnologia

Quote from Pianeta tecnologia

Sezione A – Dalla ruota all'auto elettrica; Capitolo2 - Pianeta terra, sostenibilità, tecnologia; Lezione 2 - Effetto serra e cambiamento climatico; L'effetto serra dovuto alle attività umane

Le emissioni di gas serra sono principalmente prodotte dai cittadini più ricchi che hanno a disposizione grandi quantità di energia, ma i danni climatici sono estesi a tutti gli abitanti del mondo, in particolare quelli più poveri.

Translation:

Section A - From the wheel to the electric car; Chapter 2 - Planet earth, sustainability, technology; Lesson 2 – The greenhouse effect and climate change; The greenhouse effect due to human activities

Greenhouse gas emissions are mainly produced by the wealthiest citizens who have large amounts of energy available, but climate damage is suffered by all the inhabitants of the world, especially the poorest ones.

10.Energy governance

Quote from Pianeta tecnologia, (10.1 energy transition)

Sezione D – dalle fonti energetiche alle centrali; Capitolo 1 – che cos'è l'energia; Lezione 9 – la necessaria transizione energetica

Per favorire il passaggio dalle fonti di energia fossile a quelle rinnovabili è necessario invertire progressivamente le proporzioni abbassando, nei consumi finali, la frazione di combustibili a vantaggio di quella elettrica. Questo è possibile e sta già avvenendo per tre motivi:

-esistono già delle tecnologie elettriche efficaci e competitive, in particolare fotovoltaico ed eolico

-i motori elettrici sono molto più efficienti di quelli a combustione interna, quindi nettamente preferibili

-è già possibile sostituire i combustibili sia nel settore dei trasporti (auto elettriche) sia nel riscaldamento (pompe di calore elettriche)

Translation:

Section D - from energy sources to power plants; Chapter 1 - what is energy; Lesson 9 - the necessary energy transition

To facilitate the transition from fossil to renewable energy sources, it is necessary to progressively reverse their proportions by reducing the fraction of combustion fuels to the advantage of electricity in final usage. This is possible and is already happening for three reasons:

Guidance Note

- there are already effective and competitive electric technologies, in particular photovoltaics and wind
- Electric motors are much more efficient than internal combustion engines, therefore clearly preferable
- Fuels can already be replaced in both transport (electric cars) and heating (electric heat pumps).

9. Energy citizenship

It is worth noting that we applied the new code 9.7.1 Consumer action, lists of recommended activities, and introduced a new one: 9.7.3 Geopolitics and conflicts, referring to political conflicts, found in GO! Geografia oggi

quote from Pianeta Tecnologia

Sezione A – Dalla ruota all'auto elettrica; Capitolo 2 - Pianeta terra, sostenibilità, tecnologia

Lezione 2 - Effetto serra e cambiamento climatico; Cittadinanza verde: come puoi contribuire tu alla lotta al cambiamento climatico

Cosa puoi fare tu per dare il tuo contributo all'abbattimento delle emissioni di CO2?

- Spostati a piedi e utilizza il più possibile la bicicletta e i mezzi di trasporto pubblici per muoverti in città
- Riduci il consumo di carne, specie quella bovina
- Utilizza i dispositivi elettronici con moderazione: un video streaming comporta un grande consumo di energia e quindi produce molta CO2
- Quando possibile, preferisci l'utilizzo della rete WIFI alla rete telefonica sullo smartphone. Il consumo di energia diminuisce quando il trasmettitore è vicino all'apparecchio ed è connesso alla rete via cavo e non tramite ripetitori.
- Sostituisci i dispositivi elettronici solo quando necessario: la loro fabbricazione comporta grandi consumi energetici e quindi grandi emissioni di CO2
- Parla con i tuoi genitori e proponi loro di stipulare un contratto di elettricità rinnovabile per il consumo di casa: le offerte sono tantissime.

Translation:

Section A - From the wheel to the electric car; Chapter 2 - Planet earth, sustainability, technology

Lesson 2 - Greenhouse effect and climate change; Green citizenship: how you can contribute to the fight against climate change

What can you do to help reduce CO2 emissions?

- Move on foot and use as much as possible the bicycle and public transport to get around the city
- Reduce meat consumption, especially beef
- Use electronic devices in moderation: video streaming consumes a lot of energy and therefore produces a lot of CO2

- Whenever possible, when using your smartphone prefer the WIFI to the telephone network. Energy consumption decreases when the transmitter is near the cellular device and is connected to the network via cable and not via repeaters.
- Replace electronic devices only when necessary: their manufacture involves large energy consumption and therefore large CO2 emissions
- Talk to your parents and suggest them to subscribe a renewable electricity contract for home consumption: there are plenty of offers

Quotes from GO! Geografia oggi (9.7.2Debate, issues about which there is no general agreement)

Capitolo: Risorse minerarie e fonti energetiche

- Una menzione a parte merita l'energia atomica, economica ma osteggiata dall'opinione pubblica internazionale per il rischio di incidenti e per il difficile smaltimento delle scorie radioattive.

Translation

Chapter: Mineral resources and energy sources

A special mention must be made to atomic energy, which is economical but opposed by international public opinion due to security risk and the difficult disposal of radioactive waste.

Capitolo: Temi di storia e cittadinanza/Lo sviluppo sostenibile

- la decisione dei paesi OPEC di chiudere i rubinetti del petrolio fu motivata da questioni politiche... la riduzione delle forniture di greggio fu un avvertimento agli USA e ai loro alleati europei a non appoggiare più Israele

Translation:

Chapter: History and citizenship issues/Sustainable development

the decision of the OPEC countries to close the oil taps was motivated by political issues... the reduction of crude oil supplies was a warning to the US and its European allies not to support Israel anymore.

3.Sustainable energy resources

Quote from Pianeta tecnologia

Sezione E – abitare nel villaggio globale; Capitolo 2 – la pianificazione sostenibile; Lezione 2 la pianificazione territoriale sostenibile; Processi verdi: la rete del teleriscaldamento

-...Il vantaggio è che un unico impianto emette complessivamente meno sostanze inquinanti rispetto a tante singole caldaie perché è più efficiente, ha filtri che depurano i gas prodotti prima che escano dal camino, e subisce controlli frequenti e una manutenzione più regolare.

Translation:

Section E - Living in the global village; Chapter 2 - Sustainable planning; Lesson 2 Sustainable spatial planning; Green processes: the district heating network

Guidance Note

...The advantage is that a single plant emits less pollutants overall than many individual boilers because it is more efficient, has filters that purify the gases produced before they exit the chimney, and undergoes frequent inspections and more regular maintenance.

5.Health

Quote from Go! Geografia oggi

Capitolo: Giappone/Economia

due esplosioni nei reattori [di Fukushima] hanno prodotto fughe radioattive che hanno contaminato un'area vastissima e costretto le autorità a far evacuare la popolazione

Translation:

two explosions in the [Fukushima] reactors produced radioactive leaks that contaminated a very large area and forced the authorities to evacuate the population

The radar graph showing the specific energy content:

The codes:

15. Individual actor, had 2 occurrences, they are images:

15.1 woman: a girl riding a bicycle

15.2 man: a boy riding a bicycle

16. Group of actors, had:

- 2 occurrences in Pianeta tecnologia, both 16.3 mix., both referring to the inclusive use of noi (English: we) (see above 7. language)

- 1 occurrence in Go! Geografia oggi: it was an image of the Kyoto conference, also associated to 16.2 men and 17. Professional role, politicians.

18. Other roles, had 0 occurrences.

Second grade secondary school, first 2 years (ISCED level 3)

These are the context:

Spider graph 5

Guidance Note

The graph shows the relevance of geography as a subject addressing the energy issue, while in scientific subject books it is a marginal area of interest. The most popular context are:

10.Energy governance

In Chimica Sostenibile, for the context 10.Energy governance, we applied the subcode 10.1Energy transition twice associated to the concept of circular economy. A new code was then introduced:

4.Economy, 4.6 other, 4.6.1Circular economy

Quote (Please note that in the text the expression “transizione ecologica”, in English: ecological transition, is used with a broad meaning including energy transition, so we did not consider introducing a new specific code):

CAPITOLO 6 – I legami tra gli atomi

Introduzione: La chimica 4.0 per l'**economia circolare**

Spesso si associa la parola chimica ad inquinamento industriale o alle plastiche nei mari, come se la chimica fosse di per sé dannosa per l'ambiente. In realtà la chimica è fondamentale per raggiungere gli obiettivi della **transizione ecologica**, come la neutralità carbonica, cioè il pareggio tra la quantità di anidride carbonica emessa e quella assorbita.

La chimica può contribuire alla transizione ecologica in molti settori, per esempio:

- nell'edilizia, con la produzione di materiali capaci di abbattere il consumo di energia degli edifici;
- nella mobilità, con la produzione di nuovi materiali per diminuire i consumi, come polimeri capaci di ridurre l'attrito degli pneumatici con l'asfalto
- nella filiera alimentare, con la progettazione di nuovi imballaggi e sistemi di conservazione capaci di ridurre gli sprechi alimentari,

L'odierna chimica 4.0 ha davanti a sé varie sfide:

- I nuovi materiali usati nei processi produttivi devono essere riciclabili
- L'energia usata negli impianti industriali deve provenire da fonti rinnovabili
- Nei processi produttivi non bisogna usare sostanze pericolose per l'ambiente o per la salute.
- Il trattamento dei rifiuti deve essere efficiente così da ridurre le sostanze non riciclate.

Per questo i chimici 4.0 devono costruire dai rifiuti molecole che possono essere smontate e a loro a volte riciclate, In altre parole, i chimici 4.0 applicano anche alle molecole principi dell'**economia circolare**.

Translation:

CHAPTER 6 - The links between atoms

Introduction: Chemistry 4.0 for the **circular economy**

Often the word chemistry is associated with industrial pollution or plastics in the seas, as if chemistry itself was harmful to the environment. In fact, chemistry is essential for achieving **the ecological transition's** objectives, such as carbon neutrality, that is, the balance between the amount of carbon dioxide emitted and the absorbed one

Chemistry can contribute to the **ecological transition** in many fields, for example:

- in construction, producing materials that can reduce the energy consumption of buildings;
- in mobility, producing new materials to reduce consumption, such as polymers that can reduce the friction of tyres with asphalt
- in industrial food chains, designing new forms of packaging and storage systems to reduce food waste,

Today's chemistry 4.0 faces several challenges:

- New materials used in production processes must be recyclable
- Energy used in industrial installations must come from renewable sources
- No substances dangerous to the environment or health should be used in production processes.
- Waste treatment must be efficient so as to reduce non-recycled substances.

For this reason, chemists 4.0 must build molecules from waste that can be disassembled and sometimes recycled, In other words, chemists 4.0 also apply to molecules principles of **circular economy**.

2.Climate change

It is worth mentioning that in Biologia.a the concept of climate mitigation is introduced; there are 2 occurrences (no others were found in the entire corpus) codified as 2.2.2Mitigation; both are in the same chapter, one is in the text, the other is in the caption of an image of a wind turbine

Quote:

CAPITOLO 8 – Ecologia, Ambiente e Sostenibilità; 8.3 Il clima e il riscaldamento globale
Le misure di mitigazione puntano a ridurre le emissioni di gas serra.

Didascalia: Produzione di energia grazie a un sistema eolico, le misure di mitigazione prevedono il passaggio dai combustibili fossili alle fonti di energia rinnovabili.

Translation:

CHAPTER 8 - Ecology, Environment and Sustainability; 8.3 Climate and Global Warming
Mitigation measures aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

Caption: Energy production through a wind system, mitigation measures require switching from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources.

9.Energy citizenship

In Geografia in 30 lezioni similar patterns as in Go! Geografia oggi, were found.
Quotes:

9.7.2 Debate,

Capitolo: Il nucleare

-...Per questo motivo [rischi del nucleare] è in corso un acceso dibattito tra sostenitori e detrattori

Guidance Note

Translation:

Chapter: Nuclear energy

-...For this reason [nuclear risks] there is a heated debate between supporters and detractors

9.7.3 Geopolitics and conflicts

Capitolo: Il settore energetico e gli equilibri internazionali

Gran parte delle risorse energetiche del pianeta si trovano in aree politicamente instabili. Le maggiori contese tra gli stati ruotano intorno al petrolio e al gas naturale, mentre il carbone non crea situazioni di conflittualità... Il petrolio è stato tra le cause delle 2 guerre combattute in IraQ nel 1990-1991 e tra il 2003 e il 2011... sono state definite per questo motivo "guerre del petrolio"... l'oro nero viene usato dai paesi sia come arma di pressione politica, per rivendicare il proprio ruolo all'interno delle dinamiche internazionali, sia per finanziare le guerre in atto

Translation:

Chapter: The energy sector and global stability

Much of the planet's energy resources are in politically unstable areas. The major disputes between states revolve around oil and natural gas, while coal does not create situations of conflict... Oil was among the causes of the 2 wars fought in Iraq in 1990-1991 and between 2003 and 2011... were defined for this reason "oil wars"... black gold is used by countries both as a weapon of political pressure, to claim its role within the international dynamics, both to finance the ongoing wars

4.Economy

Quote from Geografia in 30 lezioni

Capitolo: Il settore energetico e gli equilibri internazionali

Fattori come le guerre e l'instabilità politica nei paesi produttori influenzano il prezzo del petrolio... anche l'aumento e il calo della produzione mondiale di greggio, le decisioni dell'OPEC o l'introduzione di dazi commerciali - questi con l'obiettivo di danneggiare l'economia degli stati importatori - possono influire sul prezzo del petrolio

Translation:

Chapter: The energy sector and global stability

Factors such as wars and political instability in oil-producing countries affect the price of oil... also the increase and the decrease of crude oil global production, the decisions of the OPEC, or the introduction of taxes on commerce - with the objective of damaging the economy of the importing states - can affect the price of oil

5.Health

Quote from Geografia in 30 lezioni

Capitolo: Le fonti di energia non rinnovabili/Shale oil e shale gas

Il fracking presenta molti rischi ambientali: in primo luogo consuma enormi quantità di acqua, trattata con agenti chimici che sono ritenuti pericolosi per l'essere umani e

l'ambiente. 5.1 Inoltre comporta un eccessivo sfruttamento del suolo e l'inquinamento delle falde acquifere

Translation:

Chapter: Non-renewable energy sources/Shale oil and shale gas

Fracking presents many environmental risks: first it consumes huge amounts of water, treated with chemical agents that are considered dangerous for humans and the environment. 5.1 It also leads to over-exploitation of the soil and pollution of the aquifers

8. Energy availability

Quote from Geografia in 30 lezioni

Capitolo: Le fonti di energia non rinnovabili/Produzione e riserve dei combustibili fossili
I combustibili fossili sono destinati ad esaurirsi: si stima che le riserve mondiali di petrolio si esauriranno

entro 50 anni e quelle di gas naturale entro 60; le riserve di carbone, invece, dureranno circa un secolo. Tuttavia, grazie ad avanzate tecnologie di esplorazione ed estrazione, si scoprono regolarmente nuovi giacimenti.

Translation:

Chapter: Non-renewable energy sources/Production and reserves of fossil fuels

Fossil fuels are going to run out: it is estimated that world oil reserves will be exhausted within 50 years and natural gas reserves within 60; coal reserves, instead, will last about a century. However, thanks to advanced exploration and extraction technologies, new deposits are regularly discovered.

The radar graph showing the specific energy content codes:

Spider graph 6

15. Individual actor; 16. Group of actors; 17. Professional role; 18. Other roles, all had 0 occurrences. They were associated neither to text nor images. Actually, no images featuring humans were found in the pages where energy was dealt with. So the energy-gender nexus does not appear in any of the analysed textbooks.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM

The analysis carried out clearly shows that all textbooks were accurately checked and gender misrepresentation or imbalance avoided. The rare occurrences of gender codes are not meaningful and cannot provide a basis for further comments. So, referring to our corpus of texts, our hypothesis diagram is to be amended effacing the gender semantic area:

This may be the result of publishers compliance with the Polite and the Self-regulatory Code and be considered as a positive achievement, but some further considerations are also necessary: presenting science, in general, and energy specifically, as gender neutral is a traditional approach in the global North that is being increasingly challenged by the Gendered Innovations approach.

Recent literature is showing how the energy issue is not a gender neutral one, and that the gender factor may be the relevant one for the adoption of solutions and virtuous behaviour by consumers and citizen. (<http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/case-studies/energy.html>).

Another aspect that is completely absent from the textbooks we analysed, and is closely related to the gender issue, is energy as a professional field. Girls, and boys as well, are not given any information or conceptual tool to consider energy careers, and so they cannot perceive and debate the gender nexus with challenges and opportunities they may encounter in their future adult life.

The question we feel compelled to raise is if effacing gender from school texts may not contribute to a sort of blindness to the issue, a blindness that leaves girls and boys unaware and so more susceptible to gender bias and stereotypes perpetuated in their social environment, not necessarily at school, rather in the family or among peers.

Allegedly, our corpus of texts is limited in number and the analysis we carried was restricted to the energy content, which means we did neglect entire chapters; still, considering the literature on the so-called gender-equality paradox in STEM (T. Breda et al. 2020), (increased gender differences in participation in STEM careers arise in countries that have more gender equality), that hypothesis should be further investigated.

REFERENCE LIST

www.miur.gov.it Italian Ministry of Merit MiM

<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/> EURIDICE network

https://www.istruzione.it/educazione_civica/ MiM web site dedicated to civic education

www.aie.it Italian association of publishing houses

<https://www.giuntiscuola.it/> Giunti Publisher's webpage dedicated s to school

<https://www.mondadorieducation.it/> Mondadori publisher's webpages dedicated to school

<https://it.pearson.com/docenti/primaria.html> Pearson publisher's webpages dedicated to primary school

<https://online.scuola.zanichelli.it/> Zanichelli publisher's webpages dedicated to school

<http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu> Stanford University's website dedicated to the Gendered Innovation approach

Raccomandazioni per un uso non sessista della lingua italiana, extract from A. Sabatini, *Il sessimo nella lingua italiana*, 1987, retrieved 8th July 2024 at https://www.funzionepubblica.gov.it/sites/funzionepubblica.gov.it/files/documenti/Normativa%20e%20Documentazione/Dossier%20Pari%20opportunit%C3%A0/linguaggio_non_sessista.pdf

The structure of the European education systems Schematic diagrams Eurydice – Facts and Figures 2023/2024, EURIDICE, European Education and Culture Executive Agency, 2023

Cracking the code: girls and women's education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), UNESCO, 2017

Breda T, Jouinia, E., Nappc C. Thebaulta, G., 2020 "Gender stereotypes can explain the gender-equality paradox", Downloaded from <https://www.pnas.org> by 79.56.213.99 on April 15, 2024 from IP address 79.56.213.99.

Valente A., Tudisca V., Caravita S., "The public discourse on immigration in Italian school textbooks", *Mondi Migranti* 1/2022

Guidance Note

Enclosed files

PrimarySchool.exl

FirstGradeSecondary.exl

SecondarySchool.exl

APPENDIX 4. POLISH NATIONAL REPORT ON ENERGY- GENDER NEXUS IN THE SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

Paulina Sekuła, Tadeusz Rudek, Aleksandra Wagner, Marta Warat

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report explores the intersection of energy issues and gender representation in Polish school textbooks. The primary aim is to examine whether content related to energy production, storage, use, and management is presented in a gender sensitive way, and whether it encourages equal opportunities for all students in the context of the energy transition and women's participation in energy sectors.

CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

The Polish education system is centrally managed by the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. The system is characterized by centralized governance and decentralized administration, with local governments managing the administration and running of schools, while the national level sets curricula and oversees pedagogical supervision. There are multiple textbooks for school education available on the Polish market that are approved by the authority. Teachers and schools can choose them according to their preferences. In practice, there are few most popular publishing houses that dominate in the educational sector.

Education in Poland is compulsory for children aged 7 to 18, with primary education spanning eight years and secondary education divided into various types, including general secondary schools, technical secondary schools, and vocational schools. Higher education includes bachelor's, master's, and PhD programs.

Energy Education in Poland

Energy education in Poland is incorporated across different subjects such as Geography, Physics, Biology, and Civic Education. However, it is not uniformly integrated, with significant emphasis on coal phase-out and energy transition debates. The curriculum aims to prepare students for future professions and lifestyles, including those influenced by energy transition issues.

Despite the importance of energy transition in public discourse, the integration of energy education in school curricula is fragmented. Textbooks often include references to energy within specific subjects but lack a cohesive approach to teaching energy-related competences, especially in relation to social practices and professional opportunities.

Research Questions

1. Is energy education content presented in a gender-sensitive manner?

2. Does the representation of energy issues create equal opportunities for students in energy-related sectors?
3. Does the content encourage women's participation in the energy transition?

Methodology

The study analyzed 16 textbooks from primary and secondary education, focusing on subjects where energy issues are discussed. Using qualitative data analysis software (MAXQDA), the researchers conducted an abductive coding procedure to identify themes and patterns related to the energy-gender nexus.

Key Findings

- The analysis revealed a lack of explicit references to gendered aspects of energy transition in the textbooks. Gender equality was indirectly mentioned only in relation to the Sustainable Development Goals.
- Textbooks predominantly depicted energy as an abstract physical phenomenon, with a strong focus on technical aspects like electricity and power infrastructure. The macro economy perspective is also noted. Social and human aspects of energy production and consumption were underrepresented.
- Visuals in textbooks often reinforced traditional gender roles, with men depicted in professional contexts (e.g., scientists, engineers) and women in domestic settings. Non-stereotypical representations were rather rare.
- Language is neutral avoiding forms detecting gender.

Conclusions

The findings indicate a need for more inclusive and comprehensive energy education that addresses gender perspectives and encourages diverse participation in the energy sector. Integrating gender-sensitive content and practical energy issues into the curriculum could better prepare students for future challenges and opportunities in energy-related fields.

1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

1.1 Educational system in a country- brief characteristics

The education system in Poland is centrally managed by the Ministry of National Education and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education. Both Ministries were established on January 1, 2024 when the previous Ministry of Education and Science was divided into two separate Ministries responsible for general and vocational primary and secondary education and higher education. Both Ministries are responsible for setting and implementing the national educational policy and supervision of the activities of educational institutions regarding their compliance with the law and proper use of the public funds. The Ministry of National Education is also responsible for the structure of the school system, setting curricula and governing centralized exams while the local governments (district (powiat), which is an intermediate local government) is responsible for the administration of education and the running of schools. The relevant district authorities have also impact on the staffing of management positions in schools and the organisation of competitions for this purpose. Excluded from the district's responsibilities in the field of education is pedagogical supervision, which is exercised by the school superintendent at the regional (voivodship) level. This division of responsibilities between the national and local government creates a specific system of centralized governance and decentralized administration.

The state provides funding for primary and secondary school, as well as public higher education institutions. In case of primary and secondary schools, local government decides how to divide and use funds. They also use their own income to provide funding for the school system which causes the discrepancies between different localities concerning infrastructure or e.g. support for children.

The education system in Poland has been shaped and transformed since 1989, with the most recent important changes between 2017-2023. It is divided into the three key stages:

Primary education: 8-year primary school

- Grades I-III – early stage; focus on basic, general knowledge; integrated subjects
- Grades IV-VIII – second stage; subject-based teaching, including Polish, foreign language, mathematics, history, knowledge of society, security education, physical education, computer science, religion or ethics (optional), physics, chemistry, geography, nature/biology, art, music, formation hour, an education for family life (optional).

Secondary education:

- 4-year general secondary school
- 5-year technical secondary school
- 3-year Stage I sectoral vocational school
- 2-year Stage II sectoral vocational school

- 3-year special school preparing for employment

Higher education:

- First- cycle programmes
- *licencjat* (equivalent of Bachelor's degree) - 3 year programmes
- *inżynier* (equivalent of Bachelor's degree) – 3 - 4 year programmes
- Higher education: Master programmes (mostly 2 years)
- Higher education: PhD programmes (4 years)

Education in Poland is compulsory for children from 7 to 18 years of age, with a mandatory one-year pre-school class for 6-year-olds. However, for students aged 15-18, the education can be organized either at school or in non-school setting (e.g. in a form of apprenticeship). At the end of primary and secondary school, the external examinations are organized. The exam – especially the one after the secondary school (called *matura*) is of great importance for educational paths as they give access to the further stage of education and have impact on the choice of particular school.

In addition to public schools and higher education institutions, there are also non-public schools which are fee-based. Despite the increase of non-public schools, there is still a domination of public sector.

1.2 Energy education

The energy transition has been an important topic in the Polish public debate in recent years, and the dominant socio-technical imaginaries are significantly shaped by the issue of coal phase-out (Rabiej- Sienicka et al. 2022; Kuchler&Bridge 2018). The decarbonisation of the economy based on coal and lignite is discussed as one of the key challenges for the future. The impending changes have a profound impact on the labour market and social practices. As the curricula for primary and secondary education define, "the task of school is to prepare students for their choice of education and profession". It can be expected that energy transition issues will be included in the programme as a possibility for professional activity and an important dimension of future lifestyles.

Surprisingly, energy education is scattered in different subjects, which, despite the ideas of blocked education, remain the main units of organising teaching and learning in Polish schools.

The overview of the detailed educational content defined by the curricula leads to the identification of several subjects in the last two years of primary education and the first two years of lower secondary education as the reference for further analysis. These subjects were Geography, Physics, EDB (Education for Safety), Biology, Chemistry, History, Civic Education (Wiedza o społeczeństwie), Contemporary History (introduced in 2022). The analysis of widely used textbooks results in including in the sample only those fragments that refer to energy in connection with the social dimension of the process of producing, distributing, storing or consuming energy. The fragments describing energy as a pure physical phenomenon referring to the theory or energy as biological functions (feeding, breathing) was excluded.

An overview of the analysed documents' profiles shows that energy issues, as defined above, are most often presented in Geography and Physics textbooks, and less often in History and EDB. Surprisingly, energy is hardly considered within the framework of civic education or contemporary history (HIT).

Although various organisations - NGOs (e.g. Greenpeace, Energy Planet or the Centre for Civic Education) or business companies (Orange) have provided the guides for teachers and the scenarios for lessons dedicated to energy saving, renewable energy resources as offering new job opportunities, this perspective of teaching about energy in relation to social practices has not been included in the textbooks, nor is it directly recommended by the ministerial curricula.

It should be noted that many schools have implemented the programmes offered by energy companies and realised as CSR actions, or cooperate with NGOs offering ecological education. Some of the schools reported their own contribution to the energy transition, such as the installation of solar panels, reporting on energy savings, etc. However, these initiatives remain voluntary and additional activities (often proposed by the individual teachers) to meet public expectations rather than following the Ministry's strategic plans. This approach was not recognised in the textbooks analysed.

2 MAIN RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The analysis of Polish school textbooks was driven by the following research questions:

- 1) *How content related to energy education, i.e. processes of energy production, storage, use and management, is presented in a gender-sensitive way?*
- 2) *Whether representation of energy issues creates equal opportunities for students to develop their activities in energy-related sectors?*
- 3) *Whether and, if so, how the content related to the energy transition encourages women to participate in it?*

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 The logic of research design

The collecting data, coding and analysis were realised in 01.12.2023- 01.07.2024.

First, we carefully analysed the most recent core curriculum for subjects in primary school and high school and technical school for the last two classes of primary school and the first two classes of high school and technical school to judge whether specific keywords were included. These keywords were: energy, environment, resources, electricity, nuclear, atomic, and electric.

The analysis of keyword emergence in primary and high school textbooks reveals significant insights into how energy-related topics are integrated across various subjects. In primary school, Physics and Geography stand out with high occurrences of the keyword's "energy" and "environment," reflecting a strong emphasis on these concepts within the curriculum. Physics textbooks, in particular, show a notable focus

on practical applications of electricity and energy, with 25 mentions of "energy" and 28 mentions of "electric." Geography also highlights environmental issues, with 43 instances of "environment," indicating an integrated approach to teaching about ecological and energy resources.

In high school and technical school, the trend continues with Physics maintaining a predominant focus on energy concepts, evidenced by 55 mentions of "energy" and 28 of "electric." Chemistry also emerges as a critical subject, with 27 mentions of "energy" and 23 of "environment," suggesting a comprehensive exploration of energy resources and environmental impact. Geography in high school further emphasizes environmental education, with 87 mentions of "environment," alongside a significant discussion on energy production and nuclear energy.

The data indicates that while primary education introduces foundational concepts of energy and environment, high school education delves deeper into the complexities and practicalities of these topics, preparing students for more advanced understanding and discussions. The presence of keywords like "nuclear" and "atomic" in high school subjects, although less frequent, points to a curriculum that begins to address more sophisticated aspects of energy production and its broader implications. Overall, the curriculum across both educational stages reflects a progressive buildup of knowledge, equipping students with essential insights into energy and environmental issues critical for their academic and real-world applications.

Later on, based on the visibility of these keywords in the curriculum, we selected the following subjects for further examination: physics, geography, history, social studies, education for safety, entrepreneurship, chemistry, history and the present.

After selecting the subjects, we conducted an initial query in the library to assess whether all available official textbooks for these subjects included any information about energy. The relevant chapters and pages in those textbooks were noted by the JU team. Based on this initial query, we compiled a final list of textbooks (see *table 1 & 2*) and commissioned a professional query from the Jagiellonian University Library (Biblioteka Jagiellońska) to scan the relevant chapters of these textbooks. The professional unit of the library provided us with digitized OCR scans of the textbook chapters, which were then imported into the data analysis software MAXQDA.

3.2 Corpus of texts

In this study, the corpus of texts serves as the basic dataset for analysis. The corpus consists of a carefully curated collection of textbooks, carefully selected to meet the research objectives. The textbooks were selected on the basis of specific criteria in order to capture the period of teenagers' lives when they have to make critical decisions about their education and career paths. The last two years of primary school (before the choice of upper secondary school or technical college) and the first two years of upper secondary school or technical college, when young people are choosing their specialisation path, before the last exam (*matura*). This approach ensures the relevance and diversity of the educational content. The selected textbooks and their respective educational levels are as presented in the Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1 - analysed textbooks**Primary school (7th and 8th grade)**

<i>Subject and grade</i>	<i>Title of the textbook in polish</i>	<i>Publisher</i>	<i>Year</i>
Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)	Spotkania z Fizyką 8	Nowa Era	2021
Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)	Planeta Nowa 7	Nowa Era	2023
Education for safety: Grade 7 & 8 (Primary School)	Żyję i działam bezpiecznie	Nowa Era	2021

Table 2- analyzed textbooks for high school and technical school**High school (1st and 2nd grade)**

<i>Subject and grade</i>	<i>Title of the textbook in polish</i>	<i>Publisher</i>	<i>Year</i>
Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level	Odkryć fizykę 2	Nowa Era	2020
Geography: Grade 1 (High School and Technical School) - advanced level	Oblicza geografii 1 (rozszerzony)	Nowa Era	2019
Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level	Oblicza geografii 2 (podstawowy)	Nowa Era	2020
Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School) – advanced level	Oblicza geografii 2 (rozszerzony)	Nowa Era	2020
History Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) - basic level	Poznać przeszłość 2	Nowa Era	2023
Education for Safety: Class 1 (High School and Technical School)	Żyje i działam bezpiecznie	Nowa Era	2023
Entrepreneurship: Class 1,2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School)	Krok w przedsiębiorczość	Nowa Era	2020
Chemistry: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level	To jest chemia 2: podstawowy	Nowa Era	2021
History and the present: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School)	Historia i Teraźniejszość 2 (poziom podstawowy)	WSiP	2023
History: Class 2 (High School and Technical School) - basic level	Historia 2	WSiP	2020
Education for Safety (High School and Technical School)	Edukacja dla Bezpieczeństwa	WSiP	2022
Chemistry Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – advanced level	Chemia: podręcznik cz. 2 (podstawowy)	Pazdro	2020
Chemistry: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level	Chemia: podręcznik cz. 2 (rozszerzony)	Pazdro	2020

These textbooks were selected to cover both primary and secondary education levels, providing a comprehensive overview of the subjects. Each text was scanned to the digitized – OCR form and uniformly formatted to facilitate systematic analysis in data analysis software.

All together we have analysed and coded 988 pages in 16 textbooks. We have chosen a paragraph as a unit of analysis, and the number of the coded fragments was 2474.

3.3. Qualitative data analysis driven by the codebook

The data analysis was conducted following a systematic procedure driven by the provided codebook (see *Attachment 1*). The codebook, along with the digitized OCR content of the textbook chapters provided by the Jagiellonian University Library, was imported into the MAXQDA software. This setup allowed for efficient and organized data management.

The analytical work was collaboratively divided among all members of the gEneSys team at the Jagiellonian University. Each team member was assigned a specific portion of the data to code, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the entire dataset. After the initial coding, each coded segment was sent to another colleague for verification and review, ensuring accuracy and consistency in the coding process.

Upon completion of the individual coding tasks and subsequent reviews, all the coded data were consolidated into a single file. This comprehensive file provided a unified dataset for final analysis. We employed an abductive coding procedure, allowing for the addition of new codes as significant themes and patterns emerged during the analysis. This flexible – open ended approach ensured that the analysis remained thorough and adaptive to the data's nuances.

The analysis of the texts selected for further investigation was based on abductive coding. This kind of flexible qualitative data analysis approach allows researchers to develop new theories about their data based on existing theories and concepts. Following the dense relational network of concepts in energy transition fields (see De Nicola et al, 2023) , informed by the previously conducted SLR of scientific and grey literature (see de Nicola et al. 2023), and inspired by the Report on Gender perspective into energy – shifts(Diaz-Chaves, Evans 2023) we distinguished the key code categories that could shape the energy-gender nexus in educational materials. At the same time, being aware of the fundamental differences between the European educational systems, we decided to keep open the possibility of using these categories in a contextual way and of generating new codes directly from the research material. Coding and analysis were carried out using MaxQDA software.

4 RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS

4.1 Energy- gender nexus in analysed texts– general observations and reflections

In none of the analysed textbooks were there any explicit references to gendered aspects of energy transition and/or climate change. Gender equality was only once referred to indirectly, when – for an additional assignment - students were invited to identify which of the Sustainable Development Goals (only illustrated with the 17 official SDG icons and not even roughly explained/defined) should be pursued in order to reduce the occurrence of environmental conflicts (“human-environmental conflict”, Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School) – advanced level).

However, a thorough analysis allows for tracing some gendered aspects of teaching energy, related both to textbooks' images and exemplifications. In physics textbooks energy is depicted as an abstract, physical phenomenon, with a focus on electricity and such energy infrastructures as power stations and devices for energy storage. When energy practices are introduced they relate to energy consumption, mainly through transport and manufacturing and to a much lesser degree through household practices (the latter are better represented in the primary school physics textbook). Other energy practices are almost absent, with the exception of a few mentionings of energy saving relating exclusively to the use of energy-saving light bulbs.

Most images are either diagrams or mechanical-related illustrations with engines, vehicles and powerplants.

Fig. 1 A comparison between electric current and water flow .[Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

Fig 2. Nuclear power plant .[physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)]

Fewer illustrations relate to the living world, are of a biological character and people oriented. While it is a long-lasting and well-established tendency to depict energy (as other physical phenomena) as objective and impersonal, at the same time to capture students' interest in particular subjects, they must be viewed by them as relevant, as relating directly to their lives and life issues. With focus on one type of exemplifications/illustrations one might miss the opportunity to provide real-world/contextual relevance for different groups of students. There might be gender differences in what is seen as relevant, with girls more often than boys preferring physics content that is related to social and human concerns (Hollins et al. 2006).

When humans are pictured in the physics textbooks, men are more often depicted in their professional roles, as inventors, scientists and specialists (e.g. an electrician repairing high-voltage installation, women are more often portrayed in the household contexts (e.g. a girl watering a garden, and a woman lying on floor being electrocuted after careless use of hair dryer (or as a pupil at schools).

Fig 3. Women and men in traditional roles [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)]

There are fewer non-stereotypical depictions of gender roles, and they include a young man ironing clothes [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)] and a woman electroradiology technician operating MRI (Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level).

Fig 4. Non-stereotypical gender images ([Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level) (left), [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)](right)

In geography textbooks the perspective on energy is different and more diverse, with focus on energy production as an important branch of national industries, but also on

its negative environmental and health impacts. Most attention is paid to fossil fuels, their past and current role in the Polish and world energy production, but also on their negative environmental impact. However, the renewable energy sources are also widely discussed, with the focus on their growing share in global electricity generation. The discussion of pros and cons of expanding RES and nuclear energy is as well introduced. In one of the analysed geography textbooks for high schools the discussion on energy sources is directly linked to the issues of energy security and independence. As for other than production energy practices the focus is on energy consumption through transport (of energy, goods and people), but not that much through household practices. More attention is instead paid to energy savings as an important aspect of both manufacturing, policy making and private life. The used images are diverse and include both diagrams, mechanical-related and people-oriented illustrations. People are depicted in groups, mostly in their professional roles, but also when commuting and protesting against nuclear power. Pictures of professional activities reflect existing gender segregations in labour market/sectors, with men working in ICT, electronics, and car industry and women more often occupying (low-paid) positions in clothing industry and pharmaceutical manufacturing. The pictures also reproduce gender stereotypes of research and experimental work as male.

Fig 5. Research and experimental work as male [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)] (left), [Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

In the rest of the analysed textbooks single perspectives of energy are discussed. In the history textbooks energy is covered in the chapters on industrial revolution in the XVIII century and the introduction of – then innovative - steam engines in coal mines, steelworks and textile factories allowing for the advancements in energy efficiency. Human actors (both men and women) are mainly illustrated in groups as physical workers. From the perspective of the Education for safety energy is discussed through the frames of technology security and energy availability as well as health risks stemming from nuclear radiation and air pollution. In Entrepreneurship textbooks the focus is on the energy trade being the subject to national and international regulations. The chemistry textbooks introduce the problem of processing of fossil fuels, its negative environmental impacts and alternatives: nuclear energy and renewables. The History and the Present textbook adds a framework of recent developments in

international agreements on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and moving away from fossil fuels.

4.2. Energy – gender nexus through frames

In none of the selected frames gender-related context is present. Moreover, the selected frames are not equally represented throughout the analysed textbooks, with economy, and climate change widely discussed and poverty and labour market almost absent.

The single most developed frame through which energy is analysed is economy with the focus on industry, including manufacturing processes and technologies. This frame is used mostly in the geography textbooks, where the historical and current global and national industry transformations had been linked to the changes in energy production and consumption as well as in the energy balance towards the growing use of renewable energy sources. The role of energy-efficient production technologies in the reduction of raw materials and energy demand is stressed.

“Electricity production and consumption are increasing worldwide, but the rate of growth is slowing down in countries with high levels of development. Almost 75 per cent of the world's electricity is produced from non-renewable sources. The share of renewable sources in the structure of energy production and consumption worldwide and in Poland is steadily increasing”. (Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level),]

While there is a strong focus on economy, the issues of labour market in energy related sectors are not actually discussed. While selected pictures illustrate (mostly gender segregated) jobs in energy-related sectors, in none of the textbooks are discussed such issues as changing in the national and global labour markets or job opportunities due to development of new energy technologies. The topic is covered by only general statements that the high-tech industry is “characterised by a predominance of highly qualified workers” and “contributes to the creation of modern jobs” [Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level).

The analysis of energy through the framework of climate change is also very well represented in the analysed textbooks. The negative environmental consequences of the emission of greenhouse gases being the side effect of electricity and heat production as well as the are widely discussed mainly in the geography and – to much lesser extent – in chemistry textbooks. Particular environmental disasters, such as earthquakes resulting from mining activities or contamination of sea water due to failure of oil storage reservoirs, are mentioned to raise awareness of the profound impact of energy production (and industrial activity in general) on the Earth ecosystems. Taking this into account it is surprising how the role of energy governance (both nationally and globally) in mitigating climate change and/ or energy transition is little discussed. Out of various aspects of the energy governance (including appropriate oversights, legal and regulatory framework, inclusive and effective institutions and civic engagement and empowerment, Verma 2022) the role of national and international institutions and legal frameworks in setting standards and obligations as well as facilitating implementation of energy saving technologies is sporadically mentioned:

“Effective prevention of environmental pollution requires a great amount of money, an appropriate state policy and the environmental awareness of society as a whole”. [Geography Grade 8 (Primary School)]

"The Report of the Club of Rome, published in 1972 and entitled Limits to Growth, was significant in shaping the idea of sustainable development. Its authors pointed out that the increase in consumption of the Earth's natural resources was accelerating rapidly and that they would soon be exhausted." [Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

"The search for new energy sources also appears to be a necessity because of the obligations to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases, including CO₂, into the environment. According to declarations, by 2049 Poland should abandon mining and the use of coal, the combustion of which is one of the main causes of environmental pollution." [History and the present: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School)].

The security perspective on energy is applied mostly in the Education for safety textbooks and to a much lesser extent in Geography and History and the Present. State control of the energy sector, investments in diversification of energy supply and "increasing the share of renewable sources in the energy production structure" [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)] are emphasized as measures for maximising national energy security. Terrorist attacks (including cyber-attacks) on strategic infrastructure including power plants are discussed as important contemporary risks. A separate security thread is linked to the risks of the nuclear power production. Both historically (through reference to the Chernobyl and Fukushima nuclear power plant disasters) and in reference to present day, nuclear power plants are depicted rather as a potential ecological threat than a measure for enhancing energy security and independence.

The problem of energy poverty or energy inequalities is only signalled with the identified paradox that "[d]espite the fact that global electricity production is steadily increasing, there are still almost one billion people on Earth without access to electricity. As many as 19 of the 20 countries considered least developed in terms of access to electricity are in Africa (as of 2019). This mainly includes countries in central and eastern Africa, including Tanzania, Somalia, Zambia and Mozambique." ([Geography Grade 2 (High School)]).

Fig.6 Energy poverty [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)]

4.3 Gender and technology or energy resources

The technology in the material analysed is usually presented without people. The textual layer is dominated by statistics and other numerical data, while the visual representation is dominated by images of large objects - coal mines, coal-fired power stations, giant wind farms and water turbines.

Fig 7. Large energy objects (Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School))

The exception is PV panels, which are shown on smaller objects such as houses or other buildings more often than in the form of large-scale PV farms. However, they tend to be depicted without people.

Fig. 8 PV panels [Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)]

Rarely, and usually in a historical context, do we find images depicting miners and describing their working conditions. This has less to do with technology than with the physical labour of people. These people are usually men, although it is mentioned in passing that in the XIX century young men, women and children were employed as workers in the mines.

"However, coal mining was still primarily based on the physical labour of people, so that until the middle of the nineteenth century whole families - men, women and children - often worked in the mines". [History: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School - basic level)]

Fig. 9. Physical labour (Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School))

However, there are some differences noted in the representation of transport when discussed in the context of energy. The socio-technical imaginary of transport in transition is often objectified through the electric car. This kind of advanced technology, even when described without reference to gender, is sometimes

portrayed using the male image. This is the case, however, when e-cars are related to the technology of design or production.

Fig. 10. Advanced technology [Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)]

Women's images are more likely to be used to portray industries traditionally associated with women, such as food, textiles or healthcare, and less likely to be associated with advanced technologies.

Fig 11. Women dominated sectors [Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)]

We can find more gender diversity when the e-vehicles are handed over together with their end users.

4.4 Gender and energy labour market

The nexus of gender and energy labour market is not directly discussed in the analysed textbooks. However, gender inequalities are visible in two different contexts. Firstly, the role and position of women in the development of industry is discussed. Examining the historical perspective, the Industrial Revolution is presented as providing women with opportunities in the labour market [History Grade 2 (High School and Technical School - basic level)] While the increase in the women workforce is noted, the degrading conditions of their work are also described. Women, as well as children, often received lower salaries than men and were offered poor hours and dangerous workplaces.

Women's visibility in the labour market during the transition to new forms of industry is described in the textbooks as declining [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)]. Due to technology development, plants were no longer dependent on cheap labour force, but on human resources

shaped by education, experience, competences, or creativity. This change also applies to the energy sector where new job opportunities are mentioned in connection with the development of nuclear energy. As in other sectors of the new economy, they require highly qualified specialists. Considering gender inequalities in STEM education, energy-related programmes including textbooks convey a message of high-technology industry as suffering from gender imbalance, especially in the managerial position. Although this is not directly written in the textbooks, the gender inequalities in the labour market are seen in the images included in the textbooks [e.g. Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)]. The images below are illustrative: men are still presented in better paid sectors of industry, while women in manual work.

Fig. 12 [Geography: Grade 7 (Primary School)]

Miejsce tradycyjnego przemysłu w strukturze zatrudnienia na Śląsku zajmuje obecnie produkcja samochodów.

Secondly, gender inequalities in the labour market are indirectly described in the context of division between developed and developing countries. In case of the latter, women are still presented in the textbook as cheap workforce in a textile industry, as illustrated in the image from the textbook for Geography.

Fig. 13 [Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

Gender inequalities are illustrated in the context of transition between different forms of industry, both in historical and geographic perspectives, rather than in the energy sector. While the differences between women and men are mostly depicted in the images included in the textbooks, there is no *discussion of gender issues or challenges*. At no point, the energy sector is described as unequal or quite opposite, as encouraging women to consider their career paths in it.

4.5 Gender and social roles related to energy consumption (transport, cooking, heating, etc.)

The analysed textbooks do not discuss roles related to energy consumption undertaken by women or men, neither regarding their role as prosumer nor consumer. Gender aspects do not occur in relation to tasks performed in private, family, or household context, but it is present in the descriptions of public sphere. In the latter, the gendered character is visible in the following roles, indicating how women are men are expected to act, behave, dress or speak:

Inventor – 23 coded fragments	Academic / scientist – 18 coded fragments
Physical worker – 10 coded fragments	Activist -2 coded fragments
Student – 1 coded fragment	

The gender character of these roles is not directly discussed, but is rather present through images. They are not accompanied by evidence-based comments highlighting gender differences or similarities, but rather focus on the activities presented in the images. Second, many fragments related to the nexus of gender and social roles in the analysed textbooks are coded with at least two codes (e.g. inventor and academic/scientist) which is important while thinking about the coverage of the topic of social roles in the energy system.

The most common social roles performed by women or/and men that appear in the textbook are inventor and academic/scientist. They are presented primarily from the historical perspective, which focusses on their achievements in STEM. In the context of our analysis focussing on the nexus of gender and energy sector, this time perspective is very interesting, as it shows that historically there were almost no women in this field. In this way, a student gets the message that there were no women in the history related to energy field and that the history is told from male-centred perspective. For example, a student learns about Luigi Galvani, Alessandro Volta, Georg Ohm, Dominique Arago, André Marie Ampère, Hans Christian Oersted [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)] [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)], Enrico Fermi and Georg Brandt [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)], James Watt [History: Class 2 (High School and Technical School – advanced level)], Thomas Newcomen [History Grade 2 (High School and Technical School- basic level)]. Even if a group of inventors or academics/scientists appear in the context of energy transformation or industry, it is referred to in a masculine way. This further supports the findings already discussed in previous chapters on gender bias in relation to language used in textbooks. The exception from this dominant picture is the medicine and pharmacy where both figures – men and women – are depicted either in a mixed or gender-segregate groups (women and men separately) (e.g. [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)]). The only mention of a woman is in relation to the industrial revolution and women's struggle for equal rights as a result of frequent protests against working conditions.

The growing consciousness of English society also contributed to the beginning of the struggle for women's equality. Mary Wollstonecraft, the author of treatises on the need to educate girls, is considered the forerunner of this idea and the author of treatises on the need to educate girls [History Grade 2 (High School and Technical School - basic level)].

The dominance of men in the sphere of innovation and science is contradicted by the image related to the role of the student. Bearing in mind that there is only one coded fragment in all analysed textbooks, the images of a single photo of a girl working with electric circuits [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)] can be interpreted as a step to recognise the importance of inclusion of girls in subjects related to science, technology or energy.

Slightly less often is the role of physical worker mentioned in the textbooks. Women are presented in images referring to textile industry, household appliance manufacturers, food (especially fruits and vegetables) processing plants. Importantly, many images are taken from the Global South or Asian countries where a cheap women labour force is available. Men, on the other hand, are presented in high-tech, well-developed plants or plants based on modern technologies [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School- basic level)]. This reinforces the image of women as providing cheaper labour, in tedious work requiring manual precision as discussed in the previous chapter of this report.

Finally, the analysis of activism is presented as providing a space for women's voice and perspectives. The images included in the textbooks refer to protests e.g. against the nuclear power plant [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – basic level)] or against constructing a coal power plant in Kenya [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)]. The former depicts three men and two women in Lubiatowo

(village) holding the yellow banner with the sign NO to the atom and the latter presents an image of black protesting women. Although the analysed material mentions the word 'protests' 116 times, apart from the above quote about women's rights, it does not play on the connotations of gender and social rights/protections and social inequalities.

To sum up, there is not much in the analysed textbooks about social innovation and prosumerism (apart from 3 mentions of energy clusters, which are more like communities of local entrepreneurs who come together to produce energy for their own needs and for the local government), and not at all about gender issues. In technological innovation and social innovation in energy, there is a significant male bias, with women's contributions either linked to historical struggles for rights or absent. In reference to prosumerism, gender issues are not addressed, reflecting a gap in the material's coverage of contemporary gender dynamics in energy practices.

4.6 Gender and energy governance

In the case of energy governance, which is mentioned only a few times in the textbooks, the gender perspective is not taken into account at all. This result is not surprising, given that the number of mentions of 'world women' in all the data analysed is only 16, and none in the case of energy governance. The only mention of a woman in all the data was the figure of former German Chancellor Angela Merkel - as an important European politician - and the figure of Mary Wollstonecraft, author of treatises on the need to educate girls. In all textbooks, women are presented as consumers, workers (in factories), with one exception in relation to life sciences, where we can find a representation of women in science.

Fig. 14 [Geography: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – advanced level.)]

5 TEMPORALITIES

The temporal aspects of energy issues are most visible in relation to its production. History textbooks present energy production as linked to the physical power in the past. The great weaves of industrialisation are portrayed as linked to rapid civilisational development and associated with increasing aspirations for life, leading to women's emancipation and human rights awareness. The other themes offer the perspective of climate change, closely linked to the phasing out of coal and the use of renewable energies. The energy transition is thus looked to the future, while technological development is portrayed as the main helper in achieving climate neutrality. There is

a strong implication that current problems such as energy storage or carbon capture can be solved in the next future thanks to technological innovation:

“Batteries - large and small, constructed in dozens of ways - will be the technological (and economic) hit of the coming decades. The earth will be transformed into a vast storehouse of electricity.” ([ysics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

Or

“Batteries from bacteria or rolled up a curate of unusual ideas for storing energy are not lacking. Some of them are complete futurology, which is not to say that they are not being researched. Take, for example, a battery that will never actually need to be replace, because after 200 000 discharges it will be as good as new. A substitute for such a cell has been created by researchers at the University of California, Irvine” Physics, Secondary Education [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]

The technology development is portrayed as the main force determining the future of society across analysed textbooks. The dimension of social practices and patterns of human activities as shaping the future is absent or its efficiency is openly negated:

“Reducing energy consumption on a global scale is very difficult. This is because it is hard to imagine that people will reduce their energy consumption and accept such radical moves as giving up lighting, air conditioning or the use of mobile phones. Almost certain is the opposite scenario, in which energy demand will increase. This is why measures are needed to at least limit the rate of growth, such as: introduction of energy-efficient production technologies, modernisation of transmission networks to reducing energy losses during transmission, promoting and subsidising insulation of buildings and modernisation of heating installations, reducing street lighting in cities at night,” 05 Geography , Secondary education [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School– advanced level)].

Although gender aspects are not discussed at all in relation to the future, nor in relation to the opportunities for a more equal society, the untapped potential of human creativity, nor the challenges related to existing inequalities, it can be assumed that the strong focus of the high-tech industry and the lack of gender-sensitive language in textbook communication (using scientists and engineers in the masculine forms in the Polish language) will not help to overcome the under-representation of women in future energy-related sectors.

It can be assumed that energy education, scattered over different subjects, shares technological determinism between its two temporal horizons: past and future. Teaching about the past- the history present technology development as driven by the men and contribute to understanding of innovation mainly in terms of technology. When looking into the future, energy education remains gender blind in the sense that it does not recognize gender aspects as important for the future development of society.

6 LANGUAGE

At the verbal level, sex/gender is not present in the energy narratives, regardless of the analysed textbook. Terms such as 'gender'², 'gender equality', 'women' or 'men' do not appear in the text. One already mentioned exception is 'gender equality' as one of the sustainable developmental goals presented in a geography textbook. The other are few passages on the Industrial Revolution appearing in the history textbooks. With reference to difficult working conditions in factories and coal mines it is mentioned that “*until the mid-nineteenth century whole families - men, women and children - often worked*” [History Grade 2 (High School and Technical School Primary)]. It is also mentioned that the growing social awareness at that time allowed for “the beginning of the struggle for women’s equal rights [History: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School - basic level)].

While the Polish language has grammatical masculine and feminine genders and the linguistic experts encourage the broader use of feminine forms³, feminatives are used very rarely in the analysed textbooks and the plural masculine forms are used as generic forms, e.g.

“**Uczniowie** chcieli sprawdzić, w jaki sposób natężenie prądu zależy od przyłożonego napięcia” („**The (men) students** wanted to find out how the intensity of the current depends on the voltage applied”, [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)])

“**Uczniowie** badali (...)” („**The (men) students** examined (...), [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)])

“(...) **robotnicy** godzili się na pracę w wyjątkowo złych warunkach” („the (men) workers accepted to work in extremely poor conditions”; [History: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) - basic level,]).

This is in line with the linguistic rules and customs governing the use of Polish masculine and feminine forms. In the case of plurals, if a group of individuals includes both men and women, the plural of the masculine form can be used. This means that a plural expression such as “uczniowie” (men students) is ambiguous: it may refer to a group of only men, or to all students irrespective of gender. In this context, a more gender sensitive way of referring to a gender-mixed group would be using a split construction of: “uczniowie i uczennice” (men and women students). While this latter construction is more and more popular in academic and political discourses, it is still relatively rare in everyday language and in the textbooks under analysis. One of the very few

² In Polish language the differentiation between 'sex' and 'gender' are not easily traced, as both terms are identified with the same word “płeć”.

³ The Council for the Polish Language (2019) recognised that “there is a need for greater, possibly complete symmetry of masculine and feminine personal names in the Polish vocabulary. The use of feminatives in speech, for example the alternating repetition of feminine and masculine nouns (Polki and Polacy - Women Poles and Men Poles), is a sign that speakers feel the need to increase the visibility of women in language and texts. However, there is no need to use constructions like Polish women and Polish men, men and women students in every text and sentence, as masculine forms can refer to both genders.

exceptions of using paired plurals including a feminine is in the instruction for an assignment in the geography textbook:

*“Zastanów się, w jaki sposób możesz przyczynić się do zmniejszenia presji człowieka na środowisko. Zaproponuj kilka działań proekologicznych, które możesz realizować samodzielnie lub z **kolegami i koleżankami z klasy**”* (Think about how you can contribute to reducing human impact on the environment. Suggest some environmentally friendly activities that you can carry out on your own or with your men and women classmates). [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level,0)]”

As for the other aspects of inclusivity of the energy content it is worth analysing whether complex issues are explained in an accessible way.

Given the abstract nature of energy, physics textbooks use metaphors, analogies and illustrations for facilitating students' learning. Contrary to expectations, these metaphors and analogies are almost absent in the primary school textbooks and their variety is introduced in high school textbooks. Most of them are mechanistic as in the comparisons of 1) the movement of electrons in a wire to the movement of the bicycle chain links [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)] amperage to traffic density [Physics: Grade 8 (Primary School)] and 3) a battery to a pump [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School) – basic level]]. They are somehow balanced by other, natural/biological, analogies, when electric current is compared to water flow, and a battery – to a human heart (both in [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)]).

In the assignment or experiment instructions direct and indirect forms of expression are used interchangeably. The examples of direct forms include:

*“**Imagine** that you want to use the energy of flowing water to power machines (...)”*, [Physics: Grade 2 (High School and Technical School – basic level)];

*“**Recall** which energy resources are categorised as fossil hydrocarbons. **Note** that these include oil and natural gas. **Find** the lines on the graph that show the proportion of oil and natural gas. **Note** only to the period covered - the second half of the 20th century. **Analyse** the course of both lines carefully. **Estimate** in which years the trend was upward and in which years the trend was downward”*. [Geography: Grade 2 (Secondary School and Technical Secondary School – advanced level)].

They are used interchangeably with such indirect forms as “it is worth (...)”, “it is necessary to (...)”

7 MISSING THEMES

The material analysed led to the conclusion that gender issues are absent from energy education, while energy education is marginal and dispersed.

Although the curricula defined by the Ministry of Education define the preparation of students for their choice of education and profession as the main task of school education, the potential of preparing for the energy transition as a new opportunity for both men and women remains untapped.

The lack of a gender perspective can be observed at all levels of content organisation: from the macro perspective of energy governance (labour market, entrepreneurship, policy-making) to educational standards, business processes and

everyday practices. Gender inequalities are neither reported nor discussed. There are no visible efforts to encourage young women to overcome existing stereotypes and consider their professional development in energy-related sectors.

The lack of a social practice perspective makes the energy problem appear as a responsibility of the state, regional or international bodies, without recognising the importance of human behaviour and individual choices in the energy transition.

The technological lens of defining innovation excludes social innovation from the field of interest, which doesn't increase the potential of human creativity in thinking about the alternative future.

Energy issues, framed as economic factors and mainly related to technology, are insufficiently linked to the climate change perspective. Decarbonisation is presented as the dominant path, without recognising the other problems associated with energy production, such as water scarcity, rare minerals or land conflicts.

There is a significant lack of civic education on energy governance, prosumerism and energy democracy. There is no support for bottom-up initiatives or citizen participation in energy governance at the local or regional level.

The frame of sustainability understood through the SD Goals is not used to teach about energy. Energy issues are not discussed in the context of poverty, labour and transport inequality, rarely in relations to health problems, responsible consumption, water and land use, community rights, global value chains, justice or partnership.

8 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATION POLICY MAKERS ON INTEGRATING GENDER PERSPECTIVE INTO COMPULSORY EDUCATION ON ENERGY SYSTEM

The creation of innovative, gender-sensitive education can provide ground-breaking results for the energy transition by mobilising the untapped potential of all citizens to contribute to it. However, it is a delicate and complex issue: currently, the language and manner of energy education reflect the authors' efforts to avoid any form of gender discrimination. As a result, energy education is highly technical, abstract and lacks a people-centred approach.

We therefore recommend that curricula include more content on energy issues with their social dimensions: different practices of energy production, distribution and consumption. Presenting energy as an inseparable aspect of everyday life, related to individual behaviour, consumer choices, employment opportunities but also to collective imaginaries and patterns of social practices, can open new spaces for understanding the sustainable, people-centred transition.

In this context, energy education materials could explicitly address gender perspectives. We recommend including discussions on how energy issues uniquely affect different genders and highlighting the role of women in energy production, management and policy-making.

The next suggestion is to include case studies and examples of women professionals in the energy sector to provide role models for girls, and to revise existing textbooks to include balanced gender representation and ensure that both men and women are represented in different professional roles related to energy.

The next step is to include stories and profiles of women who have made significant contributions to the energy sector to inspire women students.

Textbooks provide the basic information and help to structure the teaching programme, but we recommend going further and developing supplementary teaching materials that focus on the social dimensions of energy, including how energy policies and practices affect men and women differently. This could stimulate classroom discussions on gender equality in the context of energy. Facilitated debates and projects would allow students to explore gendered aspects of energy consumption, production and policy. This can be a good starting point for encouraging schools to adopt gender-responsive policies and practices in their approach to energy education. This can include setting up gender-balanced energy clubs or societies and supporting initiatives such as the installation of renewable energy systems in schools, where both boys and girls are equally involved in the planning and implementation phases.

A very important and neglected aspect of energy education in Poland is energy policy. A gender-inclusive programme could include advocacy for gender mainstreaming in national and local energy policies. The educational content should then reflect these policies and prepare students to deal with them.

By adopting these recommendations, Poland's educational system can foster a more inclusive and equitable environment that empowers all students to engage with and contribute to the energy sector, ensuring that both boys and girls are equally prepared for the challenges and opportunities of the energy transition.

Annex 1. A table of themes occurring in textbooks

<i>The most visible topics/ themes (based on codes). e.g.</i>	<i>No. of occurrence</i>	<i>Subject</i>	<i>Grade/ level of education</i>
Social acceptance	7	Geography	High school
Social acceptance	7		
Energy poverty	1	Geography	High school
Energy poverty	2	History	High school
Energy poverty	3		
Energy safety	2	Physics	High school/Primary School
	9	Geography	High school
	1	History and the present	High school
Energy safety	12		
Energy inequalities	4	Geography	High school
Energy inequalities	4		
	11	Geography	High school
Energy savings	11		
Energy innovation	7	Physics	High school/primary school
	3	History	High school
	3	Geography	High school
Energy innovation	13		
Energy efficiency	3	History	High school
	18	Geography	High school
	1	Chemistry	High school
Energy prosumption	1		
Energy consumption	4	Chemistry	High school
	1	Entrepreneurship	High school
Energy consumption	5		
Energy production	7	Geography	High school/Primary school
	6	Chemistry	High school
	4	History and the present	
	5	History	High school/Primary school
	1	Entrepreneurship	High school
Energy production	23		
	9	Geography	High school
	2	Education for safety	Primary school
	1	History and the present	High school
Energy independence	12		

<i>The most visible topics/ themes (based on codes). e.g.</i>	<i>No. of occurrence</i>	<i>Subject</i>	<i>Grade/ level of education</i>
Pollution/Smog	32	Geography	High school/primary school
	1	Education for safety	High school
	1	Chemistry	High school
Pollution/Smog	34		
Health risks	6	Physics	Primary school
	25	Geography	Primary school/ High school
	1	Chemistry	High school
Health risks	32		
	55	Geography	High school
	3	Education for safety	Primary school/ High school
	9	Chemistry	High school
	2	History and the Present	High school
Climate change	71		
Technology security	2	Geography	High school
	2	History and the Present	High school
	20	Education for safety	Primary school/ High school
	1	Chemistry	High school
Technology security	25		

Annex 2. Missing topics/themes

<i>Missing topics/ themes (based on codes). e.g.</i>
Energy justice
Energy poverty
Energy community
Energy prosumerism
Energy savings
Digitalisation

REFERENCES

De Nicola, A., D'Agostino, G., Fresilli, B., Peri, V. M., Patriarca, T., Leonardi, N., Luzi, D., Mirenda, C., Pecoraro, F., PISACANE, L., Marchesini, N., Tagliacozzo, S., Cellini, M., Crescimbene, C., Sekuła, P., Wagner, A., Warat, M., Striebing, C., Loos, S., Diaz-Chavez, R., Evans, Y. (2023). D.1.1 - Systematic literature review of the studies at the nexus of gender equality and sustainable energy systems and ontology of energy systems. gEneSys Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10610382>

Diaz- Chavez R., Evans Y., (2024) D.5.2 – Report on Gender Perspectives into Energy-SHIFTS, gEneSys Horizon 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10664606>

Hollins, M., Murphy, P., Ponchaud, B. and Whitelegg, E. (2006) *Girls in the Physics Classroom: A Teachers' Guide for Action*. London, Institute of Physics

Kuchler, M., Bridge, G., Down the black hole: Sustaining national socio-technical imaginaries of coal in Poland, Energy Research & Social Science, Volume 41, 2018, Pages 136-147, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.04.014

Rabiej- Sienicka, K., Rudek T., Wagner A., Let it Flow, Our Energy or Bright Future: Sociotechnical imaginaries of energy transition in Poland, Energy Research & Social Science, Volume 89, 2022, 102568, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2022.102568.

The Council of the Polish Language, 2019 Stanowisko Rady Języka Polskiego przy Prezydium PAN w sprawie żeńskich form nazw zawodów i tytułów (25 XI 2019 r.) [Position of the Council of the Polish Language at the Presidium of the Polish Academy of Sciences on the feminine forms of names of professions and titles], https://rjp.pan.pl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1861:stanowisko-rjp-w-sprawie-zenskich-form-nazw-zawodow-i-tytulow.

Verma Piyush 2022 Energy governance: Four ways to succeed, <https://www.undp.org/blog/energy-governance-four-ways-succeed>.

|

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326